

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF THE ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL
BANKS DURING AND AFTER THE 2008/09 FINANCIAL CRISIS: EMPIRICAL
EVIDENCE FROM THE KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA

By

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ABSTRACT

The effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis have been researched widely. A growing body of research claims that the effects of the crisis were limited to USA and other developed countries because of their close business ties. Another body of research, however, claims that almost every part of the world was impacted by the crisis because the world economy is intertwined. While the conflicting findings and claims persist, some of researchers claim that the Islamic Banks (IBs) were not impacted by the crisis because they did not engage in conventional banking practices that exposed the banking industry to the crisis. To bridge the gap, the thesis evaluates the effects of the crisis on the Saudi banking industry by comparing its effects on Saudi Conventional Banks (CBs) with its effects on Saudi Islamic Banks (IBs) between 2006 and 2017. Mixed research method that combined quantitative data with qualitative one was used to evaluate the extent to which the Saudi banking industry was impacted or not impacted by the crisis. The quantitative data, which was in form of secondary data, was obtained online from three IBs and three CBs whereas qualitative data was obtained from 40 research participants (20 participants working in each type of bank). Both ROE and ROA were used to measure banks' performances. The thesis established that both Saudi IBs and CBs were impacted negatively by the crisis; hence, their ROA and ROE declined during the crisis. Further analysis indicated that the banks were in the processes of recovering from the crisis, but IBs had recovered faster than CBs. The thesis concluded that banks' unique characteristics did not protect the Saudi IBs from the crisis because the Saudi banking industry was impacted by changes in oil prices and other factors other than the crisis that impacted the banks in developed countries. The thesis recommends that additional measures aimed at protecting both IBs and CBs should be developed to protect the Saudi banking industry from financial crisis in the future. Additionally, it recommends that effective measures aimed at diversifying the Saudi economy should be developed to protect the Saudi banking industry from financial crisis.

DEFINITION OF THE TERMS

To help the reader understand how the various concepts and terms are utilized in the study, this part of the thesis defines the main terms and concept utilized in the study. The various terms and concepts are defined the way they are utilized in the study; as such, their definitions might deviate slightly from their usual definitions.

Islamic Banks (IBs) These are the banks that follow Islamic business practices in their banking processes. As a result, they do not charge interests on loans in line with Sharia business practices. In addition, they prohibit banks from engaging in gambling and other uncertain business practices (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017).

Conventional Banks (CBs) Unlike the IBs, that follow Islamic business practices in their banking processes, CBs do not follow such practices in their business processes. As a result, they charge interests on loans and even allow uncertain banking practices some of which are not allowed among IBs (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017).

Financial crisis This relates to the financial distress that occurred between September 2008 and mid 2009 within the US financial sector before spreading to other parts of the US economy and other parts of the world (Thakor, 2015). In line with the study's focus, the effects are limited to banking sector, which is the study's main area of focus. As a result, the other areas of economies, which were impacted by the disaster, are excluded from the analysis.

Contagion theory A theory concerned about the way movements in financial assets co-move in different parts of the world simultaneously

without necessarily any direct link between them (Rigobon, 2016).

Spillover theory A theory concerned about the way effects in one part of the world spread to other parts of the world by leaking out (Rigobon, 2016).

Decoupling theory A theory, which is concerned about the way different countries in the world separate themselves from others, in their business and other practices (Dullien et al., 2010).

Sharia boards The boards tasked with providing advices related to acceptable Sharia banking practices and ensuring that the guidelines are implemented in IBs in the right way. The members are appointed by shareholders at the start of every financial year and they are expected to issue reports at the end of the years relating to the way IBs follow or do not follow Islamic business practices (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017).

Credit Default Swaps (CDSs) The derivative instruments that CBs developed prior to the crisis to redistribute credit risks. They were literally privately negotiated mutual contracts promising buyers to compensate them in the event that loans and mortgages were defaulted (Terzi & Ulucay, 2011).

Collateralized Debt Obligation (CDO) The asset-backed securities that were backed either by bank loans, mortgages or corporate bonds. The funds used to purchase underlying assets were obtained from debt obligations. Although they were special purpose vehicles for investing in different pools of assets, they were common among CBs because they engaged in uncertain businesses.

Mortgage-Backed Securities (MBS)

The mortgages pooled together and then sold to investors as diversified portfolios. Since they were diversified, they were considered less risky than mortgage contracts; hence, they were common prior to the crisis (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017).

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ATMs	Automatic Teller Machines
CBs	Conventional Banks
CDO	Collateral Debt Obligation
CDSs	Credit default Swaps
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease 2019
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Council
IBs	Islamic Banks
KSA	Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
MBS	Mortgage Backed Securities
NCB	National Commercial Bank
ROA	Return on Assets
ROE	Return on Equity
SAMA	Saudi Arabian Monetary Authority
SBB	Saudi British Bank
SIB	Saudi Investment Bank
UAE	United Arab Emirates

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1: Thesis' Background

The 2008/09 financial crisis that started in USA before spreading to other parts of the world had notable effects on the US financial sectors and other parts of the world (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). According to Seidu (2009), the financial crisis was so great to the extent that the world economy lost about fourteen trillion dollars within a span of two years. This loss was not limited to financial sector alone, but it also spread to other industries as well. In USA, the effects spread to equity market before spreading to other parts of the world (Kayed & Hassan, 2011). In addition, it resulted in nationalization, sale and even bankruptcy of about 485 banks within a short period (Boyes, 2009; Khan, 2009). The effects were so great that they endangered the world financial system with a total collapse (Thakor, 2015). As a result, most of the governments throughout the world were forced to bail out large uninsured financial institutions.

According to Dymski (2013), the 2008/09 financial crisis was more or less like the 1930s great depression. According to Seidu (2009), it forced governments throughout the world to create urgent rescue packages from national treasuries to support their financial systems. This later led to sovereign debt crisis that followed as soon as the crisis was over (Mayes, 2011; Khan, 2009). It even resulted in a period of recession especially among the developed countries and even impacted the Icelandic economy the most because it depended largely on banking sector (Boyes, 2009). Alongside the above, majority of the people especially those working in the financial sector lost their jobs whereas others lost their investments and savings (Ganic, 2012; Warde, 2012).

Despite the notable effects that the 2008/09 financial crisis had on world economy, researchers differ on the degree of its effects on various parts world. Some such as Boyes (2009) and Khan (2009) claim that its effects were restricted to USA and developed nations because of their close business ties whereas others such as Warde (2012) claim that it spread throughout the world without sparing even the developing nations. While this is the case, most of the researchers believe that the crisis impacted

almost every part of the world in one way or the other. Nevertheless, some of the researchers argue that IBs were never impacted by it because they did not offer the toxic assets that contributed to the development of the crisis in USA (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). The few ones who claim that IBs were affected by it in one way or the other maintain that they survived the first phase of the crisis implying that the effects were felt afterwards (Warde, 2012). While the debate on the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on different parts of the world continues, new sets of studies continue to emerge that contradict the previous findings.

Kassim and Abd Majid (2010) claim the interest-free banking system adopted by IBs protected them from the exogenous shocks that emanated from financial crisis. While such an argument appears plausible, it would be important to note that different sectors of world economy were impacted by the crisis even though most of them did not depend on interest rates charged on banks (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). Alqahtani and Mayes (2017) argue that the crisis impacted the bank sector in an unprecedented manner because central banks in different parts of the world including KSA were forced to implement reactionary measures. Some of the reactionary measures included reducing their interest rates (Kayed & Hassan, 2011). This measure, which was prevalent throughout the world, aimed at increasing the supply of money through monetary policies (Abdelbaki, 2010). However, it resulted to other unprecedented outcomes such as inflation, which hurt national development even further. Even though the thesis does not evaluate the extent to which such measures impacted the Saudi economy, the unprecedented outcomes depict the extent to which the Saudi bank sector was not spared by the crisis. As a consequence, it was vital for the thesis to be conducted to evaluate the extent to which the Saudi bank sector was impacted or not impacted by the crisis.

Researchers have evaluated the effect that the 2008/09 financial crisis had on IBs and CBs. At global level, Zehri, Abdelbaki and Bouabdellah (2012) evaluated the way IBs and CBs performed during the crisis in different parts of the world. They established that accounting ratios were perfect discriminators of the effects of the crisis on those banks. At regional level, Hasan and Dridi (2010) compared and contrasted the way IBs and

CBs from the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries performed during the crisis. In contrast to researchers who asserted that IBs were not affected by the crisis, they established that both types of banks were affected differently by the crisis. They went ahead to attribute the differences in effects and performance to the business models that both types of banks used in their banking practices. Ganic (2012) went a step further to evaluate the effects of the financial crisis on western Balkans' banking sector by comparing the way banks in different countries were affected by the crisis. The author established that even though the effects of the crisis were not absolute in most of the countries, the credit growth, asset quality and profitability of the banks that took part in the study were affected by the crisis showing that both types of the banks were impacted by the crisis.

In Malaysia, Abdulle and Kassim (2012) evaluated the way both types of banks were impacted by the crisis. Unlike the other authors, they did not establish any significant difference between the profitability and credit worth of both types of banks during the crisis. Nevertheless, they established that IBs held more liquidity assets than their counterparts during the crisis; hence, they were less exposed to liquidity risks. This could mean that the Saudi IBs like their Malaysian counterparts were not impacted by the crisis. However, similar studies have not been conducted in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA); hence, it was necessary for the current study to be conducted to determine the way both types of banks were impacted or not impacted by the crisis. This was important in determining the measures that should be put in place to protect the sector from a similar crisis in the future.

Shafique, Faheem and Abdullah (2012) evaluated the effects of the crisis on IBs. They established that even if IBs were vulnerable to the crisis, the banks were not impacted significantly by the crisis because their systems were interest-free. Similarly, Al-smadi, Hamdan and Almsafir (2013) compared and contrasted the way Malaysian IBs and CBs performed during the 1997 Asian financial crisis and the 2008/09 global financial crisis. With the help of business growth, operational efficiency, profitability and liquidity measures, they established that IBs performed better than their conventional counterparts because their systems were competent.

Despite the conflicting results from previous studies, it would be worth noting that studies conducted so far identify a profit-sharing mechanism on banks' deposits as the best mechanism for insulating financial systems from effects that emanate from interest rate fluctuations (Kassim & Abd Majid, 2010). However, it would be imperative to acknowledge the fact that both Islamic and conventional banking practices are susceptible to different types of risks. As a result, it would be wrong to presume that the Islamic banking practice would not expose IBs to financial risks. While this is the case, a historical overview of the financial crisis shows that financial crises are more often than not preceded by huge leverages on asset prices and balance sheets for financial intermediaries (Thakor, 2015). Additionally, they are preceded by financial liberalization and financial innovations that rely heavily on returns from favorable economic conditions. Nonetheless, it is not always possible to maintain favorable economic conditions as practical applications have demonstrated.

Most of the studies that evaluate the effects of the crisis on Islamic states argue that the extent to which individual states were impacted or not impacted by the crisis depended on two factors. The first group of studies argues that it depended on the role of financial sectors on individual states (Kayed & Hassan, 2011). Accordingly, they use the M2 ratio, types of credit that financial institutions advances to non-financial institutions and amounts of deposits to determine the effect that the crisis had on individual economies throughout the world or in different parts of the world. In contrast, the second group of studies argues that the effects of the crisis depended on the degree of openness of national economies. They claim that the higher the level of openness the higher the effect of the crisis on individual state, and vice versa (Abdelbaki, 2010). Although the thesis does not evaluate the level of openness in KSA, it appreciates the fact that Saudi CBs were vulnerable to the crisis because they were relatively open to conventional banking practices practiced in USA and other parts of the world (Kayed & Hassan, 2011). In addition, it appreciates the fact that the Saudi economy was relatively open to international market; hence, it suffered the spillover effects of the crisis.

Abdelbaki (2010) argues that the effects of the crisis on IBs depended on the level of liberalization of financial sector in each country. He thereby divides the countries into

three groups namely; Arabic countries with high level of financial and economic liberalization, those with moderate levels of liberalization and those with least levels of liberalization. He argues that IBs from Islamic states with high levels of financial liberalization were affected by the crisis more than their counterparts from countries with low levels of liberation. In spite of this, it would be worth noting that the degree of the effects of the crisis depended on the extent to which individual countries depended or did not depend on oil and its related products (Kayed & Hassan, 2011). Accordingly, the extent to which Saudi bank industry was affected or not affected by the crisis depended on the level of financial liberalization in the country and the extent to which the sector depended on oil.

Alongside the above, it would be worth noting that measures taken by government were also critical in minimizing the effects of the crisis. The general expectation would be that if the government did not implement the requisite measures, then the bank sector was impacted negatively by the crisis. However, if the government was quick to implement requisite measures, then the effects of the crisis were minimal (Boyes, 2009). A quick overview of the measures that the Saudi government took in response to the crisis shows that the government was able to invest part of its money in the financial sector as a way of boosting it (Abdelbaki, 2010). In addition, the government joined the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and started implementing most of its recommendations on financial sector among other things. Accordingly, it is possible that the effects of the crisis were minimized or they were barred from affecting the country negatively.

Even though KSA was not the epicenter of the crisis, the country was not spared by the spillover effects emanating from the crisis. Abdelbaki (2010) argues that the crisis resulted to decrease in oil prices, which obviously impacted negatively the Saudi economy and banking sector because both of them relied heavily on the oil industry. In addition, it forced the Saudi government and other governments in the world to reduce their national budgets as a way of safeguarding their economies from the effects of the crisis (Abdelbaki, 2010). The unfortunate thing with decreased national budgets was that it impacted Saudi economy and banking sector negatively by decreasing the

demand for oil and its related products, which were paramount to Saudi economy and bank sector. While the debate on the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on different economies of the world continues, understanding the effects that the crisis had on Saudi banking industry is critical because it does not only highlight what happened, but it also highlights the areas that contributed to the crisis. Such an understanding is critical because it identifies what went wrong and even go ahead to suggest what can be done in the future to prevent the occurrence of a similar financial crisis and even minimizing its effects on banking sector in case it occurs in the future (Jaffar & Manarvi, 2011).

1.2 Statement of the problem

A preliminary review of the previous studies showed that a number of factors contributed to the financial crisis. However, the toxic mortgages that were issued to low-income earners, scant regulation, easy credit and low interest rates were identified as the main factors (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). In spite of this, the financial crisis was so great to the extent that the world economy lost about four trillion dollars within a span of two years (Seidu, 2009). The loss was not limited to financial sector alone, but it also spread to other sectors as well. At a country level, it reduced the US equity market so sharply whereas in KSA and other parts of the world, the central banks were forced to reduce their interest rates (Kayed & Hassan, 2011). This demonstrates the extent to which the Saudi economy was not spared by the systematic effects of the crisis. In USA, about 485 banks were nationalized, sold or even declared bankrupt because of the intensity of the crisis (Boyes, 2009; Khan, 2009). Other governments were forced to create urgent rescue packages from national treasuries to support their financial systems, which later led to sovereign debt crisis that followed as soon as the crisis was over (Mayes, 2011; Khan, 2009). This led to periods of recessions among developed economies of the world especially the western ones between 2008 and 2009 (Ganic, 2012; Warde, 2012).

Even though KSA was never affected significantly by the 2008/09 financial crisis like USA and other developed countries, very few studies have been conducted in KSA to determine the way Saudi CBs were affected by it in comparison to Saudi IBs. The unfortunate thing is that the few that have been conducted so far do not address

themselves to this issue directly despite studies from different parts of the world differing on the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on IBs. Ghassan, Alhajhoj and Alaoui (2013), for instance, evaluated the impact of the crisis on Saudi economy in general. While they were able to demonstrate that the crisis had notable effects on national net-exports; hence, impacted negatively the economic growth in the kingdom, they did not evaluate the way banking industry in the kingdom was impacted by the crisis. Similarly, Tabash and Dhankar (2014) evaluated the stability of IBs in KSA during the crisis using trend analysis. While they showed IBs to be relatively stable during the crisis, they did not compare the way they performed in comparison to their conventional counterparts. The thesis was conducted to bridge the research gaps by evaluating the impact that the crisis had on Saudi CBs in comparison to their Islamic counterparts.

1.3: Thesis' motivation

One could argue that different parts of the world were not affected by the 2008/09 financial crisis and even go ahead to argue that Saudi Arabian banking sector was not affected by it in any way. Nevertheless, an argument of this nature would introduce unnecessary dispute among various researchers in the midst of the diverse studies that have been conducted so far to depict the way various parts of the world including KSA were affected by the financial crisis (Ghassan, Alhajhoj & Alaoui, 2013; Kayed & Hassan, 2011; Shafique, Faheem & Abdullah, 2012). The notion that different parts of the world were affected by the financial crisis is based on the fact that even though national economies and banking sectors are independent of each other, they are intertwined in one way or the other and they operate in similar environments (Rigobon, 2016). As a result, an impact that is felt in one part of the world is transferred to other parts of the world systematically even though the magnitude of the effect might differ from one region to the other (Agénor & Pereira da Silva, 2018). This might be considered by some people to be a subtle point, but it is an imperative one in the financial sector and banking in particular; hence, the need to evaluate the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on the Saudi banking sector.

The thesis compares and contrasts the way Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the 2008/09 financial crisis with a view to determine whether there was significant

difference between them. The study presumes that the notable differences between IBs and CBs contributed to the way both types of banks were impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis. Accordingly, the second chapter, which addresses itself to the banking and finance context in KSA looks at the major differences between the two types of banks and the way they developed historically before looking at the way both of them were affected by the crisis. Similarly, even though the empirical data focuses much of its attention on the way different banks in KSA were affected by the financial crisis; it also seeks to understand the way various people working in banks view the effects of crisis on their respective banks and Saudi banking industry in general especially after the crisis occurred.

1.4: Thesis' Focus

The thesis restricted its main focus to the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on the Saudi banking industry. Special attention was directed towards the banks' unique characteristics and the way the banks' characteristics exposed or did not expose Saudi banks to the crisis. Furthermore, to gain a better understanding of the way both types of banks were impacted or not impacted by the crisis, it directed special attention to the view of different groups of stakeholders. The process entailed obtaining their views especially those related to developments that were made following the crisis. This was intended to inform the additional developments that should be implemented in the industry to strengthen it with a view to protect it from potential effects that may emanate from similar crisis in the future.

1.5 A brief description of the methodology

To understand the way various banks in KSA were affected by the financial crisis, the study utilized mixed methods. This entailed combining secondary data with qualitative data, but separating them throughout the data analysis process before combining them in data presentation and interpretation. The secondary data was collected from the banks' official websites and financial reports whereas the primary one was collected through face-to-face interviews with critical banks' employees. The banks' Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE), which were calculated from banks' financial

statements were utilized to measure the banks' levels of efficiency and performances during and after the crisis.

The banks with higher profitability ratios were considered to perform better than their counterparts with lower profitability ratios. The Altman z-scores were utilized to measure the insolvency risks of the banks included in the analysis. The banks with scores above 3 were regarded to be safe whereas those with scores between 2.7 and 2.99 were regarded to be in gray region and those with values below 1.8 were regarded to be in distress region (Erfani & Vasigh, 2018). To gain a meaningful picture of the way Saudi banks were impacted by the crisis; primary data was also collected from critical people working in the banking industry. These were the people with experience and expertise in Saudi banking industry that were able to suggest the reasons behind some of the notable changes that were identified in the industry during and after the crisis.

1.6 Thesis' aim, objectives and research questions

The thesis' overall aim was to advance an understanding of the way Saudi banking industry was affected or not affected by the 2008/09 financial crisis by comparing the way IBs and CBs were impacted or not impacted by it at individual level. However, to understand the overall impact, there was the need to evaluate the way both types of banks differed from each other structurally and the manner in which their differences either exposed or protected them from the systematic effects of the crisis. This was critical especially in the midst of conflicting findings from previous studies some of which suggested that IBs were never impacted by the crisis whereas others negated this claim. As a result, the second chapter, which put things into context, evaluated the banking differences between the two types of banks and even went ahead to look at the way the difference developed historically. On the other hand, the literature review evaluated the way both types of banks were impacted by the crisis. In view of this, both empirical data and in-depth review of relevant literature were utilized to advance the study's aims.

As regards the objectives, the study sought to evaluate the way IBs and CBs in KSA performed during and after the financial crisis. Its specific objectives include:

1. Evaluating critically the unique characteristics of the Saudi IBs and CBs that contributed or did not contribute to the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry.
2. Comparing and contrasting the way Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the 2008/09 financial crisis.
3. Evaluating the insolvency risk for Saudi CBs in relation to that for Saudi IBs during the crisis.
4. Identifying the forces emanating from the 2008/09 financial crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry
5. Formulating recommendations that could be used to minimize the effects of a probable financial crisis in the future on Saudi banking industry

In the light of the above objectives, the thesis sought to answer the following research questions.

1. *What were the unique banks' characteristics that contributed or did not contribute to the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on the Saudi banking industry?* Answering this question helped to attain the first research objective that sought to identify the unique banks' characteristics that exposed or did not expose the two types of banks to the impact of the crisis. As a result, the second chapter that sought to put things into context before evaluating the studies conducted so far was dedicated to identifying the unique characteristics of the two types of banks and the way they impacted or did not impact Saudi banking industry. This was critical in determining the way those characteristics exposed or did not expose both types of banks to the impact of the crisis.
2. *How did the Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the 2008/09 financial crisis?* Answering this research question was intended to achieve the second objective; as such, it was also important to the study in general.

3. *What was the insolvency risk for the Saudi banking industry during the financial crisis?* Answering this research question was critical to attaining the third objective that sought to determine banks' insolvency risk during the crisis. As a result, it contributed significantly to the attainment of overall objective.
4. *What were the forces emanating from the 2008/09 financial crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry?* In line with the other objectives, this research question sought to determine the forces that emanated from the crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry in general. In so doing, it contributed immensely to the overall objective.
5. *What can be done to protect the Saudi banking industry from impacts of a similar financial crisis that may occur in the future?* This research question was intended to help the study attain the fifth objective. As a result, it evaluated at the additional developments that might be implemented in the Saudi banking industry to improve it and even protect it from probable effects of a similar crisis in the future.

1.7 Significance of the Study

Knowing that the 2008/09 financial crisis was caused and exacerbated by the conventional banking practices that were prone to manipulation before the crisis took place one might form the hypothesis that the IBs were never affected by the crisis. Nevertheless, some authors argue that all banks including the Islamic ones were impacted in one way or the other by the crisis. In view of this, there was the need to evaluate the effects of the crisis on Saudi Arabian banks by comparing the extent to which CBs and IBs were impacted or not impacted by the crisis. This was intended to determine what needed to be done now and in the future to protect banks in KSA from such a crisis, and even make sure that the Saudi banks especially the conventional ones would not contribute to the development of a similar financial crisis in the future. In this respect, the thesis contributes to the existing body of knowledge by identifying what needs to be done in KSA to strengthen the banking practices especially the conventional ones. In addition, it contributes to it by identifying the major developments

that should be developed to enhance the sustainability of the banking industry in the kingdom.

Apart from the above, a review of the current studies identifies IBs as possessing a stronger and effective structure than CBs. However, even if studies claim that IBs were never impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis like their conventional counterparts were impacted by it, very little has been done in KSA to determine the extent to which the structure of the CBs was responsible or not responsible for the effects witnessed by these banks during the crisis. In view of this, the present study was conducted to determine the way Saudi CBs were impacted or not impacted by the crisis in comparison to their Islamic counterparts. This bridged a research gap that has existed for long in KSA thereby contributed immensely to existing body of knowledge.

Alongside the above, the study evaluated the various developments made so far within the Saudi banking industry in response to the effects that the crisis had on the industry in general. Special attention was directed to the way various stakeholders especially the critical ones view the new developments in the light of the crisis. This identified the areas that needed further development to strengthen the industry in general. As a result, it contributed immensely to the formulation of new measures that policy makers in KSA can implement to strengthen the industry.

1.8 Findings' summary

The thesis established that the banks' unique characteristics did not expose the Saudi banking industry to the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis. Instead, the external forces from reduction in oil prices and demand during the crisis exposed the Saudi banking industry to the effects of the crisis.

1.9 Thesis' limitation

Despite its wide-ranging findings, the study was limited in the following manner. Firstly, it restricted its scope to KSA alone; as such, its findings were not generalized to other parts of the Middle East and world in general. However, the findings were utilized to depict the way both IBs and CBs in KSA were affected by the financial crisis. Secondly,

the focus was restricted to the period between 2006 and 2017; as such, the study's findings were restricted to that period alone implying that they were not utilized to depict the way both types of banks performed before the crisis. However, the effects identified from this period were utilized to determine some of the measures that Saudi banking industry had taken to strengthen its business practices. Thirdly, the number of the banks included in the analysis was limited by the availability of the data. As a result, even if its findings were generalized to Saudi banks, the generalization of the findings was made cautiously.

Alongside the above, due to the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, the researcher had limited time to interview research participants included in the study. As such, he did not probe for deeper explanations in certain areas due to the limited time scheduled for the face-to-face interviews. Although this did not impact the study's findings much because pertinent issues were addressed as they emerged, there would be the need for similar studies with larger sample sizes and ample time for interviews to be conducted in the future.

1.10 Thesis' structure

The thesis consists of seven chapters. The first one provides the study's background by identifying the areas that have been evaluated before and the need for the present study. It also provides the study's aim, objectives and research hypotheses together with an overview of the methodology utilized to conduct the study. Additionally, it defines important terms and concepts utilized in the study, highlights some of its limitations and the way the thesis is organized right from the start to the end.

The second chapter goes a step further to provide the context of banking and finance practices among the CBs and IBs throughout the world and in KSA in particular. In contrast to the literature review that provides an overview of the studies conducted so far, it evaluates the way various banking practices are executed in Islamic and conventional banking practices. This provides a deeper understanding of how the banking practices contributed or did not contribute to the 2008/09 financial crisis.

The third chapter reviews previous studies with a view to determine what has been done and not done in the study's area of focus. It starts by reviewing the thesis' theoretical background before looking at some of the factors that led to the crisis. Then it reviews the studies that evaluate the link between banking crisis and financial ratios before evaluating the empirical studies that have been conducted in other parts of the world particularly in the Middle East region and KSA in particular. Upon identifying the gap, it provides an overview of the way the study fills the gap.

The fourth chapter provides the methodology that was utilized to conduct the study in terms of research philosophy and paradigms that were adopted throughout the data collection and analysis processes. It also provides the research approaches and strategies that were adopted throughout the study as well as the population from which the study's sample was obtained from. It concludes by providing the instrument that was utilized to collect the primary data, the ethical procedures observed throughout the data collection and analysis processes as well as the method utilized to analyze the data.

The fifth chapter provides the study's findings in the light of the research objectives and hypotheses. For efficiency purpose, different tables and figures are utilized extensively to present the findings. The sixth chapter discusses the findings in the light of previous studies. It starts by summarizing the findings before discussing them in a non-statistical manner to answer the various research questions. The process entails determining the way the findings agree and disagree with the previous studies and the possible factors that might have contributed to the differences. The seventh chapter concludes the thesis by summarizing the findings and recommending the way forward. It highlights the thesis' contribution to the body of existing literature before elaborating the thesis' limitations and extent to which they affected the thesis' findings and implications.

1.11: Chapter's summary

The chapter has provided the study's background by evaluating what has been done and not done in the area of focus. It has established that although much has been done to evaluate the impact of the financial crisis on banks in different parts of the world, very little has been done to evaluate its impact on the Saudi banking industry. In line with

this, it has identified the thesis' research questions and objectives, provided the motivation behind the study and its significance. Additionally, it has defined key terms used in the study, identified study's limitations and provided an overview of its various chapters.

CHAPTER 2: CONTEXT – BANKING AND FINANCE IN KSA

2.1: Chapter's overview

This part of the thesis provides an overview of the main characteristics of the IBs and CBs with a view to pinpoint the major differences between them. The differences are presumed to have contributed significantly to the way both types of banks were impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 global financial crisis. As a result, there was the need to evaluate them to determine the manner in which they contributed or did not contribute to the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi Arabian banks. The first part of the chapter starts by providing the structure and size of the Saudi banking industry. The evaluation is intended to put the thesis in its context before looking at the banks' unique characteristics and the way they contributed or did not contribute to the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry.

2.2: The Saudi banking industry

2.2.1: Market structure – Major Banks

Currently, there are 26 banks in KSA; 13 locals and the other 13 foreign banks. Nine of the local banks are CBs whereas the other four are IBs. The Saudi major banks include the National Commercial Bank (NCB) with a total asset of \$142.053 billion followed by Al-Rajhi bank with a total asset of \$104.056 billion. The Riyadh bank with a total asset of \$74.264 billion ranks third whereas the Samba Financial Group with a total asset of \$70.915 billion ranks fourth. The Saudi British Bank (SBB) with a total asset of \$70.422 billion ranks fifth whereas the Banque Saudi Fransi with a total asset of \$52.885 billion ranks sixth (ADV Ratings, 2020). The other banks among the top ten major banks in KSA include the Arab National Bank (\$49.086 billion), Alinma bank (\$36.647 billion), Islamic Development Bank (\$32.599 billion) and Saudi Investment Bank (\$26.765 billion).

In terms of market structure, it would be worth noting that three major banks in KSA account for about 45 percent of the sector's assets. In addition, about seven of them

account for about 85 percent of the sector's assets implying that the sector is dominated by major banks (Hassan et al, 2018). Even though the current study is not concerned about bank ownership, it would be worth noting that the national government has substantial shareholding among the three major banks whereas the other four banks that form the seven major banks in the kingdom are owned by families (Hassan et al, 2018). This is an important aspect worth noting because it influences the performance of the major banks.

2.2.2: Islamic versus conventional banking

Hassan et al (2018) argue that the Saudi Islamic banking sector is relatively smaller than the Saudi CBs because it only consists of four registered banks out of the thirteen local banks. However, a closer look at the market share shows that the Saudi Islamic banking sector is relatively influential than the conventional one because it enjoys about 51.3 percent of the market share (Hassan et al, 2018). While the figures may appear controversial mathematically, they suggest that Islamic banking practices are dominant in KSA. As a result, if IBs' unique characteristics protected the Saudi IBs from the 2008/09 financial crisis, then it would be almost difficult to detect the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry.

The four IBs in KSA include Al-Inma, Al-Bilad, Al-Jazira and Al-Rajhi bank. The Al-Rajhi bank, which was established in 1957, is the oldest one followed by the Al-Jazira bank, which was established in 1975. The Al-Bilad bank, which was established in 2004, is the third oldest IB bank in KSA whereas the Al-Inma bank that was established in 2007 is the fourth oldest IB in KSA (Hassan et al., 2018). On the other hand, the Saudi CBs included Saudi Investment Bank (SIB), Riyadh bank, SBB, National Commercial Bank (NCB), Banque Saudi Fransi, Samba Financial Group (SAMBA), Arab National Bank, Alawwal bank and Gulfe International Bank Saudi Arabia (GIB-SA) (SAMA, 2020).

Despite the differences, it would be worth noting that the Saudi IBs and CBs operate hand in hand with each other and that they are both regulated by the Saudi Arabian Monetary Authority (SAMA). Accordingly, despite their differences in banking practices, they adhere to almost similar banking regulations. This, however, does not mean that

they conduct banking businesses in the same manner, but it means that the licensing processes and other important banking aspects are regulated by the same authority. As a result, their differences in performance emanate from other factors other than the regulation processes.

2.2.3: Growth trends

Despite the effects that the 2008/09 financial crisis had on the banking sector in general, the Saudi banking industry has since 2008 managed to grow steadily as Figure 2.1 depicts. The deposits and total assets have grown steadily whereas bank reserves have remained relatively stable.

Figure 2.1: The Saudi banking industry’s growth in terms of deposits, total assets and bank reserves

(Source: Developed by thesis’ author from data obtained from SAMA (2020))

In terms of opening branches and Automatic Teller Machines (ATMs), the exercise has also remained relatively stable as Figure 2.2 depicts. This shows that the banking sector has managed to overcome the economic slowdown that the 2008/09 financial crisis introduced into different parts of the world.

Figure 2.2: The Saudi banking industry’s growth in terms of branch and ATMs opening

(Source: Developed by thesis’ author from data obtained from SAMA (2020))

2.3: The Saudi Islamic banking practices

2.3.1: The IBs’ main characteristics

Prior to looking at the characteristics of IBs, it would be important to start by defining the term IBs so that it can be easier to understand the banking practices allowed under its banking system. This would be critical in differentiating IBs from CBs, and vice versa. Mohamad et al (2013) define IB as a financial institution that operates on the basis of

the Sharia law meaning that it bases its banking practices on Islamic religion and practices. Ali and Sarkar (1995) go a step further to claim that such banks are based on Sharia principles that prohibit payment of interests on borrowed money and banking practices based on uncertainty.

The above arguments and definitions are based on the fact that Islam as a religion forbids the receipt or even payment of any pre-determined rate of return on borrowed money in form of interest. The argument is that interest impoverishes poor people at the expense of the rich who are not involved in investing the money they save in banks (Khan, 2009). From this perspective, Islam considers interest-based transactions as unfair, morally unjustifiable and unjust (El-Gamal, 2000). While this is the case, it is important to note that majority of CBs are profit-driven. As such, they enjoy lending money and charging interests on them because as they do it, they generate revenue and make profit. Additionally, it would be worth noting that other religions such as Christianity and Judaism at one point or the other prohibited the practice of paying interests on borrowed money (Lewis, 2007). However, as time went by, they embraced interests because of capitalism and other money-minded practices.

While it might appear as though Islam is not business-minded because it disallows the payment and receipt of interests on borrowed money, it would be important to note that it allows trade contracts in form of *mudaraba* or *musaharka*, which are investment-oriented. In addition, it allows trade contracts in form of *tawarruq* or *murabaha*, which are debt-based (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). Under the *mudaraba* contract, clients promise to purchase goods from IBs on deferred basis. Then IBs go ahead to purchase those goods from the people who own or supply them and sell them to clients upon adding a markup profit. The markup profit in this case is not considered to be interest. However, the issue of markup profit has for a long time raised contentious issues with some of the people regarding it as a conventional practice. The profit that is generated from this banking practice is shared between banks and people who invest their money in the banking exercise; hence, it is based on profit-sharing basis. In contrast, under the *musharaka* contract, IBs enter into joint ventures with entrepreneurs and agree the terms that would be used to share the possible profits or losses that would emanate

from business practices. Once they agree, they go ahead to purchase products for entrepreneurs (Mohamad et al., 2013). This is quite different from conventional banking practices that do not believe in losses thereby do not share losses with investors in the event business practices do not earn profits.

Under the *murabaha* contract, investors purchase products on credit by simply agreeing to pay mark-up profit on the original cost of the products. Accordingly, it might be regarded as a sale transaction that is conducted on a cost-plus-profit basis. In this case, IBs enable entrepreneurs to acquire goods from clients by financing the process, but allow entrepreneurs to pay for the goods on deferred payment basis. In so doing, entrepreneurs commit to repay the cost of the goods plus agreed profit margins in form of additional installments. Some people regard the mark-up profit as interest rates, but from Islamic perspective, the mark-up profits can never be interest rates because they are determined at the start of the sale processes. This is contrary to conventional banking practices whose interest rates are based on prevailing rates in the international markets or rates that are considered profitable in the eyes of the banks that lend money. For *tawarruq*, the banking concept is almost the same as that of *murabaha* except that the commodity purchased on deferred payment basis is sold to third parties on spot payment basis. As a result, the money owed can be paid as soon as the money is received from third parties or even be paid on deferred basis. Because of this the transaction is sometimes referred to as reverse *murabaha*. One thing to note about the above Islamic banking practices is that they need to be Sharia-complaint no matter the manner in which they are conducted (Mohamad et al., 2013). Otherwise, they might appear to be interest-based like the conventional banking practices.

From the above analysis, it is evident that the investment instruments utilized in IBs allow entrepreneurs and banks to bear the risks involved in investing and share profits or losses incurred in those practices. As such, the trade between both parties becomes partnership as opposed to lender-borrower relationship that is developed in interest-based business practices under conventional banking practices. This practice promotes higher degrees of discipline within financial sector because banks are able to gauge risks carefully before they enter into partnership with entrepreneurs (Mohamad et al.,

2013). In conventional banking, banks do not do that because they focus much of their attention on the profit they make. As a result, they try as much as possible to transfer a large portion of risk to entrepreneurs rather than help them minimize it. To some extent, this is what majority of the CBs did before the financial crisis because they offered mortgages to people who were at high risk of defaulting paying them (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). Consequently, they were hit hard when the people were unable to repay mortgage-based loans.

Besides the above, most of the debt-based contracts allowed under the Islamic banking demand leased assets to be tangible; as such, IBs do not engage in speculative transactions. In addition, they require banks to own assets before they sell them meaning that they cannot sell what they do not own (Mohamad et al., 2013). Furthermore, they require contracts to be genuine to the extent of involving a practice of giving and taking and even prohibit banks from selling debts. From this analysis, it is evident that IBs that acts as financiers bear some level of risk in issuing debts. Accordingly, because they bear some level of risk they are normally motivated to evaluate risks carefully and even take precautionary measures before they transact businesses. This ensures that they do not engage in contracts that may be regarded as toxic. In contrast, majority of the practices involved in conventional banking are largely toxic because they are based on debt-selling and interest taking (Chapra, 2009). This explains why CBs were hit hard by the financial crisis whereas IBs were rarely hit by it especially during the first phase as Warde (2012) claims.

2.3.2: The history of IBs

It would also be important to provide a historical overview of Islamic banking practices and some of the factors that led to its development especially in the 1960s (Mohamad et al., 2013). This would be important in determining why the Islamic banking practices have spread widely in different parts of the world especially after the 2008/09 financial crisis. In addition, it would be important in determining the possible impact it might have on international banking practices in the future. In the light of this, it would be important to acknowledge the fact that before the emergence of Islam, Arab countries had banking practices that were similar to the conventional ones (Alharbi, 2015). This is in

relation to the fact that some of the highest Islam personalities such as Al-Zubair bin Al-Awam acted as a conventional bank by accepting deposits from Muslims in form of loans and invested it by lending it to other people to earn interests on them. In addition, it is in relation to the fact that some of the banks that existed within Islamic empires back then operated as CBs (Cerović, Nikolaj, & Maradin, 2017). However, after the rise of Islam, the IBs practices emerged slowly especially with Prophet Muhammad who because of his personal characters of integrity and honesty acted as a wealth keeper for other Muslims (Mohamad et al., 2013). This led to the emergence of Bayt al Mal bank, which acted as the central bank for Islamic states, and whose focus was to help the poor people from the alms that Muslims provided and properties that did not have owners or direct heirs.

In the light of the above, it would be important to note that from the time that the Roman kingdom fell till the time that Islam religion emerged, the history of man was full of unsettled and corrupt period (Chachi, 2005). However, as soon as Islam emerged, it was able to transform life politically, socially and economically. This was largely because all the practices whether social or banking were based on Sharia law and submission to Allah. Beside the above, even though the emergence of Islamic banking practices was influenced by what was going on in other parts of the world, it was largely influenced by long distance trade practices that developed among Muslims. These practices led Muslims into borrowing, guaranteeing, transferring, lending and safeguarding the currencies used to exchange goods (Cerović, Nikolaj, & Maradin, 2017). The banking practices during this period were dominated by bankers who were referred to as *jahabidhah*, *sayarifah* or *sarraffeen* and banks that were referred to as *dawawinal-jahabidhah* (Chachi, 2005).

The term *jahabidhah* was utilized largely in the 8th century to refer to financial clerks or skilled people who were able to examine and even exchange money. Following this, most of states established *dawawinal-jahabidhah* as banks with branches all over major cities. The banking institutions offered most of services offered by modern banks even though they did not charge interests on borrowed money. In so doing, the Muslims were able to mobilize financial resources without necessarily charging interests (Chachi,

2005). Some of the most experienced people in those banking institutions rose to become governors and they were required by their states to prepare accounting reports on monthly and yearly basis. This system of banking was based on profit and loss sharing under the *mudarabah* system of partnership, which was passive, and *musharakah* that was active partnership. During this period, bankers were tasked with evaluating the fineness and authenticity of coins and transferring them from one place to the other to facilitate trade.

In spite of the above, during the 13th century, most of IBs lost significant control of banking practices because of the decline of Islamic empires; hence, most of Islamic banking institutions were replaced by the western ones. With the rise of European banking practices that were conventional in nature, the Islamic banking practices decreased significantly (Alharbi, 2015). This led to the opening of foreign banks within Islamic countries and states, but as soon as Islamic states gained independence from European colonizers, the trend for Islamic banking practices gained momentum once again.

The most notable recent developments in IB can be traced back in 1940s and 1950s when Islamic banking systems were initiated in Malaysia and Pakistan respectively (Shahar et al., 2017). The Malaysian IBs sought to invest savings from prospective pilgrims in plantations and real estates in accordance to Sharia law, but it was unsuccessful. The Pakistan one, on the other hand, developed IBs at local level. Both banking systems failed because of technical challenges. The second of such attempt occurred in Egypt between 1963 and 1967 under the Mit Ghamr Savings Bank. This was largely based on a saving-investment model, but it could not meet the banking needs of the people it targeted. As such, its existence was short-lived and its banking operations were taken over by the Egyptian national bank in conjunction with the central bank and converted over to *riba* system (Alharbi, 2015). In spite of this, the Mit Ghamr saving bank served as a milestone in IB system because it was considered to be the most effective interest-free bank from the time that conventional banking practices were introduced among Islamic states by Europeans.

Similar banks were developed in Egypt and elsewhere after the Mit Ghamr saving bank was taken over by Egyptian government. For instance, in 1974 the finance ministers from 22 Islamic states met and developed the Islamic Development Bank that served as the first international IB (Shahar et al., 2017). The bank's head offices were located in KSA, but it had regional offices in Malaysia and Morocco. This paved way for other similar banks in other parts of Islamic states. The influence of those banks on banking practices forced some of CBs in those states to develop separate segments within their banking practices for Islamic banking. Others converted fully to IBs; hence, since then, several Islamic bodies have been developed to promote and regulate IB practices whereas certain countries such as Sudan and Iran have Islamized their banking practices (Alharbi, 2015).

In spite of the above, it would be important to acknowledge that Islamic banking is in its early stages of development following the collapse of Islamic empires that affected its development. As a result, most of the IBs were relatively small in size just before the 2008/09 financial crisis occurred. Accordingly, some of the authors have demonstrated and argued that this minimized the effects of the financial crisis on IBs in comparison to CBs that were relatively big (Cerović, Nikolaj, & Maradin, 2017). Others have linked the reduced effect to the moral practices promoted by Islamic business practices (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017).

To provide a balanced overview of the IBs and CBs, the next part of the chapter evaluates the main characteristics of CBs. Besides, it provides a historical overview of the banking practices to depict some of the factors that have led to its widespread in different parts of the world.

2.4: The conventional banking practices

2.4.1: The major characteristics of CBs

Having identified some of major aspects that define IBs, it would now be necessary to look at similar aspects within conventional banking practices to depict the way they affect both types of banks. Before then, it would be important to appreciate the fact that

the differences affect the way both types of banks operate and conduct businesses. Even though it would not be possible to justify the most ethical banking practices because both practices have their own backgrounds, it would be important to appreciate the fact that the conventional ones are riskier than the Islamic ones (Alharbi, 2015). One thing to note is that CBs engage in less tangible financial practices whereas Islamic ones engage in practices that are more tangible. This is in relation to the fact that IBs do not encourage banking practices that trade gold on deferred basis (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). In addition, they discourage investments made on pork related products, tobacco, alcohol, weapon and gambling among other uncertain practices (Hanif, 2011). While this practice is good on ethical basis, it trims down the range of investments that can be made in Islamic banking.

In contrast to the above, CBs engage in term deposits with precise maturity dates at the end of which depositors are expected to earn interests from the people who borrow that money from banks. For this reason, CBs charge interest rates on loans that they issue to customers and the money acquired from that practice is shared between them and depositors though at rates determined by bank's management teams (Onakoya & Onakoya, 2013). IBs do not encourage this practice because they consider it immoral and unethical. Instead, they expect banks to engage in partnership with customers so that they can share profits and losses (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). This discourages IBs from engaging in risky banking practices contrary to what CBs do in their effort of making huge profits.

Besides the above, CBs offer loans and mortgage products to clients: the borrowed money is then repaid back within a specified time with some interests determined at the time of issuance. One unique thing about this money is that the property that one secures out of the practice acts as the security for the borrowed money. As a result, in the event of default, the property can be sold by banks to recover the amount of outstanding loan balances (Onakoya & Onakoya, 2013). This means that CBs do not expect to lose or even make loss out of the money they lend to customers. The same principle was applied before the crisis, but it did not work because the housing market

had literally collapsed; hence, the houses could do not be sold at market rate to recover the mortgage loans.

The banks also offer saving accounts that are devised to pool medium and long-term capital from customers. Even though the money is easily accessible to customers meaning that they can deposit more or even withdraw it at any given time, they earn interest from it if they abide by terms and conditions determined by banks(Onakoya & Onakoya, 2013). Once again, the banking instrument is aimed at attracting money from customers so that it can be offered as loan to other customers who need it. One unique difference between CBs and Islamic ones is that whereas IBs share profit made from business practices that customer engage in; conventional ones expect customers to pay pre-determined interests on loans (Hanif, 2011). As such, it does not matter whether customers make profit or loss, the fact remains that they have to repay the money and interests on top of that money.

One unique aspect about conventional banking is that it largely engages in debit transactions meaning that transactions are conducted against business deals that will be conducted in the future. For this reason, most of the transactions are normally speculative in nature. Even though such transactions are seen as the rightful ones because people have conducted them for a long time, they in most cases act as sources of instabilities in banking sector. As a result, they might endanger the world economy in a contagious manner as witnessed during the 2008/09 financial crisis. In Islamic banking, debt can never be traded even if tangible goods and services can be sold on credit. The value of debt in such instances is determined by equilibrium mark-up rates derived from the supply and demand of such goods and services (Onakoya & Onakoya, 2013). Therefore, the possibility of instability within banking sector is restricted to certain limits. More importantly, banks do not engage in speculative activities; hence, there are minimal risks within the Islamic banking practices.

Largely, the main difference between the two types of banks is in the manner they invest the money they acquire from customers. Under the Islamic banking, banks supply money to entrepreneurs for transactional purposes as opposed to earning interests. As a result, the profits or losses that are generated during the transaction period are shared

by banks and their customers based on agreement developed between them. In this respect, IBs do not use money to increase wealth, but to help customers to conduct businesses and share profits with banks. In contrast, conventional banking engages in buying and selling money to generate wealth in form of profit; hence, they charge interests on borrowed money. With regard to evaluating the soundness of business proposals, CBs put more emphasis on capacity, capital and collaterals whereas IBs put more emphasis on the character and capacity of people who borrow money (Onakoya & Onakoya, 2013). In so doing, IBs concentrate on advancing the well-being of customers rather than their financial growth as Islamic religious practices advocate. Additionally, they involve themselves in procuring and managing capital assets as opposed to CBs that acquire such products for own use.

2.4.2: The history of CBs

While the above is the case, it would be important to note that some of the differences between IBs and CBs emanated from historical developments within the two types of banks. As such, it would be important to look at the history of CBs to understand the manner in which some of the historical developments influenced the conventional banking practices especially those related to interest rates. To begin with, Cerović, Nikolaj and Maradin (2017) link the development of CBs to trade practices in Rome, Greece and Middle East regions that were rich in natural resources. In addition, they link them to the emergence of money especially in Italy. This implies that conventional banking practices emerged out of trade necessity as opposed to emergence of any religious group. However, one thing that is evident in the Middle East is that religion played an important role in its development. This was in spite of the fact that banking practices were separated from religious practices especially after the development of Hammurabi's banking codes. Contrary to IB practices that were largely influenced by Islamic practices, the conventional banking practices were influenced largely by, economic and political conditions that prevailed in different parts of the world. These conditions continue to influence interest rates charged on borrowed money and banking practices even today. Even though both factors – political and economic – have to some extent influenced Islamic banking practices, their influence is not much as the Islam

religion. Thus, Islamic banking practices are considerably different from the conventional ones even though both of them might be regarded to be similar in one way or the other (Hanif, 2011).

In relation to IB, Chachi (2005) claims that after the fall of the Roman Empire, Western Europe, which was largely influential economically and politically, went through a period of Dark Age. During this period, Western Europe, with exception of Italy and Spain, resulted to agricultural practices; thus, its trading practices were largely depressed. This does not mean that there were no trade practices in Western Europe, but it means that they were overshadowed by agricultural practices because of high transport costs, piracy, political instability and high level of uncertainty in the area (Chachi, 2005). Even though this was the case, money continued to circulate within the region, but at a lower rate, thereby banking practices were not widespread prior to the 10th century. During this period, most of banking practices within Western Europe were in the hands of money changer (Chachi, 2005). However, towards the end of 10th century crusaders from the region were able to weaken Islamic Empire that was on verge of collapsing following attacks from neighboring regions. Because of this, some of trade practices including banking ones were transferred to Western Europe particularly Italy that had maintained close links with Islamic Empires prior to the Dark Age. The money changers managed to embrace some of Islamic banking practices, but transferred them slightly to suit their business needs and practices. This marked the growth of conventional banking practices in Europe before spreading to other parts of the world.

2.5: Chapter's summary

The chapter has evaluated the Saudi banking industry with a view to determining the differences between Saudi IBs and CBs. It established that even if both types of banks operate hand in hand and that they are regulated by SAMA, their banking practices are quite different from each other. In addition, it established that even if there are only four registered IBs in KSA, their market share is about 51.3 percent implying that Islamic banking practices are dominant in KSA. The next chapter critically reviews what has been done in the past to place the thesis in its rightful position within the body of existing literature.

CHAPTER 3: LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1: Chapter's overview

This part of the thesis provides an overview of the previous studies that relate to the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on IBs and CBs with a view to determining the way the crisis impacted or did not impact the Saudi banks. It starts by providing an overview of the way the crisis impacted the global economy and KSA in particular before looking at some of the factors that led to the crisis. Then it reviews the studies that evaluate the link between banking crisis and financial ratios before evaluating the empirical studies that have been conducted in Middle East in general and KSA in particular. Upon identifying the gap, it provides an overview of the study fills the gap.

3.2: Theoretical framework

Research into the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry could take a decoupling effect theory (Dullien et al., 2010) or a contagion effect theory (Rigobon, 2016) or even a spillover effect theory (Rigobon, 2016). The decoupling theory is concerned about the way different countries in the world separate themselves from others whereas the spillover effect theory is concerned about the way effects in one part of the world spread to other parts of the world. The contagion effect theory, on the other hand, is concerned about the way movements in financial assets co-move in different parts of the world simultaneously. The purpose of this part of the chapter is to identify theories about financial crisis that could explain the way Saudi CBs were impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis.

The fundamental ontological assumption behind this study is that most of the effects that occur in different types of banks do not occur by chance, but they are methodical. And because they are methodical, research on a group of Saudi banks could be used to depict the manner in which the Saudi banking industry was impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis. Identifying such impacts could be the first step to

determining what should be done to protect the Saudi banking industry from similar impacts in the future if a comparable financial crisis could occur in the future.

But why is that the financial crisis that occurred in USA was able to spread to KSA, which was far away from the USA? In other words, why is that it is not sufficient to presume that a financial crisis that occurs in a given country could be restricted to that country so that it could not spread to other countries? The precise answer to this question is still a matter of debate (Rigobon, 2016), but there seems to be a general consensus that countries throughout the world are intertwined. As such, an effect in one country is able to spread to other countries and parts of the world once it occurs in that country.

3.2.1 The contagion and spillover effects Theories

In the view of the above, the contagion and spillover effects theories could be the best theories for evaluating the manner in which the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis spread to Saudi CBs and KSA in general. The spillover effect theory presumes that events that occur in one part of the world are able to spread to other parts of the world because world systems are intertwined. In contrast, the contagion effect theory presumes that movements in financial assets co-move in different parts of the world simultaneously without necessarily relying on interrelation between world systems (Rigobon, 2016). For better evaluation of the theories, their theoretical literature could be classified into three different classes namely; coordination, financial and fundamental studies. Each of these classes attempts to explain the way the 2008/09 financial crisis spread to KSA and other parts of the world.

3.2.1.1 Coordination view

The studies that evaluate the two theories from coordination viewpoint base their arguments on the way investors and those in powers coordinate business practices. They argue that spillover effects result from political contagion, learning, multiple equilibrium and herding problems (Rigobon, 2016). They go ahead to argue that market shocks transfer from one country or part of the world to the other due to informational problems that cause market participants to withdraw their resources from the market

jointly across nations (Ahrend & Goujard, 2015; Claessens, 2017). The information in one country in this case is able to influence investors in another country to take actions that align with information obtained from the other country.

The informational problem does not only affect investors, but it also affects policy makers to the extent that they abandon particular macroeconomic policies across nations (Rigobon, 2016). When this happens, market shocks are transmitted across nations not because of interconnectedness, but due to movement of equilibrium from one point to the other due to policy shift in two or more countries simultaneously. The contagion effects in this case occur because a change in policy in one country causes another country to change its actions altogether. With regard to political spillover, different countries with political affiliation may decide to move in one direction, and in so doing, influence each other into taking actions related to political issues. The political decision may in turn influence financial systems in the two countries thereby result into co-movement.

3.2.1.2 Fundamental view

The studies that base their arguments on fundamental view of the two theories appeal to real channels in their processes of explaining the propagation of shocks across nations. They argue that macro similarities, bilateral trades, and similar monetary policy coordination are able to transfer shocks to different parts of the world (Agénor & Pereira da Silva, 2018). With regard to bilateral trades, they argue that crises in one country that decline consumption are able to decline imports from countries that do business with that country, and in so doing, cause trading partners to suffer demand for their exports either in terms of price drop or deterioration of bilateral trade (Rigobon, 2016). The impact may extend to unrelated countries, which do business with one of these countries due to inter-link in trade channels. A similar trend is also seen in macro policies and coordination of monetary policies such as increases and decreases in interest rates. Both theories have been utilized to explain the way great depression spread to other parts of the world. As such, the current study has utilized them to depict the manner in which the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis spread to KSA and other parts of the world.

3.2.1.3 Financial view

In contrast to the above, the studies that base their arguments on financial viewpoints focus much of their attention on international equity markets and banking sectors. They argue that imperfections that occur in financial systems worsen during financial crisis. By arguing so, they limit their scope to the way financial services are offered in different parts of the world even though financial systems in those parts of the world might be considered independent of each other. While such studies provide reasonable basis of the way the effects of financial crisis are transferred from one country to the other, they disregard the shutdown of trade channels and other important channels (Rigobon, 2016). In other words, they ignore the existence of real linkages that fundamental viewpoint provides; hence, presume imperfections in financial markets to be the only forces responsible for propagation of shocks from one country to the other. Even though this might be a good presumption, it is an extreme one; thus, may not necessarily be true in real world.

From a contagion viewpoint, the studies argue that the propagation of the shocks of financial crisis transfer from one country to the other due to interrelation of the financial systems especially in the case of a common lender. Such studies argue that even if different countries could be independent from each other from a real linkage perspective, effects of the financial and even banking crisis could be identified in different countries due to co-movement (Agénor & Pereira da Silva, 2018). The Japanese banks provide a good case study of what happened during the 1997 Asian crisis because they were affected by it even though they were not part of that system (Rigobon, 2016). The spillover theory on its part highlights the issue of network across financial institutions in different parts of the world. As such, it links the effects of the financial crisis on different parts of the world and financial system in particular to system interconnectedness. From this perspective, it presumes that the Saudi CBs were impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis because of interconnectedness of CBs throughout the world.

Agénor and Pereira da Silva (2018) define cross-border financial spillovers as occurrences that result to fluctuations in asset prices in certain countries because of

similar changes in other countries. They argue that the fluctuations in this case could either result to desirable effects, which might be in form of news that result to forward-looking asset prices or undesirable effects in form of transmission of excess volatility resulting from financial frictions with accelerator effect. The impact of cross-border financial spillover could thereby depend on the type of shock, the channel through which shock transmits through internationally or mitigation mechanisms in place in different countries. In addition, it might depend on the nature of macro-prudential and macroeconomic policies in different countries as well as the scope of policymakers in recipient countries.

Agénor and Pereira da Silva (2018) argue that global banks in form of foreign banks and cross-border banking practices may be some of the major vehicles of spreading the effects of financial crisis. They classify cross-border banking practices into two different categories with the first category consisting of inter-banking funding, which occurs between unrelated banks. The second category consists of intra-group funding, which occurs among related banks; for instance, between a parent bank with its foreign affiliates. To date, the literature review shows that global banks played major roles in propagating the financial shocks of the 2008/09 financial crisis (Ahrend & Goujard, 2015; Claessens, 2017). In spite of this, global banks can only transfer financial risks if domestic lending standards could be relaxed whereas cross-border lending could be increased. Alternatively, they could transfer those risks through credit spillover channels that increase financial vulnerability in host countries. This was not the case in KSA during the crisis; hence, it is unlikely that global banks contributed to the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry.

With regard to macro-prudential policy leakages, it is possible for global banks to increase lending abroad if macro-prudential restrictions could be tightened in home countries and not tightened in host countries. The credit spillover may not necessarily occur via direct lending alone, but it may also occur via loan re-booking to parent banks and local lending to foreign branches. This may also extend to shadow banks located in different geographic regions (Claessens, 2015). Irrespective of the method through which macro-prudential policy leakages takes place, it is possible for foreign banks and

other financial institutions, which are not subject to regulation by host countries to undermine local macro-prudential policies. Accordingly, it is possible for these policies to influence international capital flow either positively by increasing them or negatively by decreasing them.

Despite the appeal of both contagion and spillover effects theories in evaluating the extent to which the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis spread to Saudi banking sector, it would be important to note that some crises are never contagious (Rigobon, 2016). As a result, the level of spreading the effects of the crisis to Saudi banking sector and subsequently the application of both theories to the current study could depend on the level of business ties between the American and Saudi Arabian economies. If the level of such ties could be high then the effects of the crisis could be high on the Saudi banking sector. Conversely, if the level of business ties between the two economies could be low, then the impact of the crisis could be minimal or even unnoticeable.

Apart from the above, it would be important to note that contagion and spillover events tend to be short-lived. As a result, the frequency of such events requires high frequency data, which may not necessarily be available to the current study. In spite of this, the effects of contagion and spillover events take long to resolve. As a result, it would be important to note that even if the 2008/09 financial crisis occurred between September 2008 and mid-2009, it has taken the US government and other governments in the world long to resolve its effects. The unfortunate thing is that by mid-2010 most of the emerging economies had recovered from the effects of the crisis (Rigobon, 2016). As such, the current study may not necessarily manage to determine the effects of the crisis on the Saudi banking sector due to low frequency of the data utilized to measure its effects on the Saudi CBs. In spite of this, the crisis period will be restricted to between 2006 and 2010 so that its effects can be detected from the secondary data collected online.

3.2.2 Decoupling theory

In spite of the above, it is also possible that the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis did not spread to Saudi CBs or KSA in general. Under such a case, then the decoupling

theory could be the best theory for evaluating the manner in which the Saudi CBs were not impacted by the crisis despite their similarities with CBs in other parts of the world and USA in particular. The theory claims that the expansion of intra-regional trade over the years has decoupled certain emerging market economies from developed economies (Dullien et al., 2010). As a result, most of them including KSA were not impacted by the recent financial crisis like developed countries were impacted by it.

While the above is the case, the theory has several limitations, some of which might inhibit its application to the current study. Firstly, in the midst of what the theory argues, it is evident that certain emerging economies such as India and China were impacted significantly by the recent financial crisis (Dullien et al., 2010). As a result, it is possible that Saudi banking industry was also impacted by the crisis given that Ghassan, Alhajhoj and Alaoui (2013) were able to demonstrate the way Saudi economy was impacted negatively by the crisis. This simply means that while the theory presumes the existence of absolute cases, they may not necessarily exist in reality. Secondly, because the crisis lasted for a relatively short time; between September 2008 and mid-2009, then it might be that its impact may not necessarily be possible to determine within KSA, which was not the epicenter of the crisis.

3.3 The factors that led to the crisis

A preliminary literature review shows that before the 2008/09 financial crisis occurred in USA and elsewhere, the conventional banking practices had changed significantly. Alqahtani and Mayes (2017) claim that the commission that was developed to evaluate the factors that led to the financial crisis established that before the crisis occurred risky mortgages that did not care much about borrowers' ability to repay them were packaged, repackaged and sold to investors in different parts of the world especially in USA. The authors claim that most of these mortgages were highly discriminative and exploitative because they targeted low-income earners who did not qualify for bank loans. The authors claim that prior to this period a red lining practice that distinguished between high risk borrowers from low ones was practiced widely in conventional banking practices. However, slightly before the crisis occurred the red line was ignored by majority of those banks because of the urge to reach more investors and make profit

from them through interest rates charged on mortgages (Boyes, 2009). While the lending practice was risky, it was largely facilitated by high-tech information tools and innovative risk-shifting tools that saw a number of low-income earners qualify for loans whereas the number of middle income and well-up people who qualified for such loans declined significantly (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). While it was a good practice from conventional banking practices, it was a moral failure that led to the financial crisis.

A similar conclusion was also reached by a commission that was developed soon after the crisis ended to determine the factors that led to the crisis. The commission established that before the crisis occurred there was significant governance breakdown within conventional banking practices. With the help of special instances, it established that the top management team for AIG ignored the risks and terms of the \$79 billion derivative that was linked to mortgage-related assets (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). Similarly, it established that most of the banks in USA and elsewhere offered highly leveraged bank loans without examining their qualities.

Apart from the above, most of CBs had taken too much risk to earn huge profits. However, the risks were dependent on short-term funding borrowed from overnight market thereby they needed to be renewed on daily basis. A further review of the literature shows that by the time that the crisis occurred some of CBs in USA and elsewhere had capital leverages as high as 20 or even 30 times of their tangible capitals (Thakor, 2015). Unfortunately, most of them underpriced their complex products because there was inadequate market discipline within the financial sector. In addition, there was a presumption that central banks would rescue those banks so they would not collapse (Chapra, 2009). Nevertheless, the crisis struck before the central banks and supervisory bodies intervened.

A further analysis showed that even if moral failures were the main factors that exposed banks throughout the world to the financial crisis, others factors also exposed banks to the crisis. According to Abdelbaki (2010), the decrease in demand for oil and its related products that resulted to decrease in oil prices was among the major factors that exposed banks in Middle East to the effects of the crisis. In addition, the high inflation rates that resulted from the crisis decreased the incentives for savings due to low

interest rates. Thakor (2015) identifies political factors, misaligned incentives, diversification fallacy, success-driven skills inferences, financial innovations, economic developments at global level and growth of securitization as some of the factors that led to the crisis. He claims that the factors led to the rise in house prices in USA that in turn enticed banks to offer highly leveraged loans to unqualified borrowers. The practice became widespread to the extent that screening standards in conventional banking practices were rarely applied due to political factors. The bubble soon burst resulting to liquidity crisis within shadow banking that was widespread.

Siddiqi (2009) believed that the financial crisis was caused by moral failures that emanated from conflicts of interests. According to Alqahtani and Mayes (2017), the moral failures emanated from banks' governance structures utilized in banking practices. On one hand, the Islamic governance structure was thought to have protected Saudi IBs from the crisis and its subsequent effects; hence, it was deemed necessary to look at it to depict the manner in which it protected those banks from the crisis. The general structure is provided in Figure 3.1. However, prior to looking at the way it influenced the management of IBs before, during and after the crisis, it would be important to start by acknowledging the fact that Muslim self-discipline played a major role at personal level. The discipline prohibited Muslims from engaging in fraudulent banking practices that were exploitative in nature. While similar religions such as Judaism and Christianity prohibit such practices, they do not prohibit CBs from charging interests on bank loans.

Figure 3.1: The Islamic bank governance structure

As Figure 3.1 depicts, the Sharia supervisory board, which is the top-ranking body supervises Islamic banking practices. Unlike CBs that do not have such boards, each of the IBs has an Islamic board, which consists of bank experts with vast knowledge on Islamic business practices. Alongside the boards, the banks also have well-developed internal mechanisms that ensure that Islamic banking practices are followed all the times. As a result, unless various supervisory bodies cooperate in engaging in unethical banking practices; the likelihood of such occurrences is rare.

The Sharia boards are generally tasked with providing advices related to acceptable Sharia banking practices and ensuring that the guidelines are implemented in the right way. In line with this, the board, which is appointed by shareholders at the start of every financial year, has the responsibility of issuing reports at the end of the years relating to the way IBs follow or do not follow Islamic business practices. The general practice is

that IBs that violate Islamic business practices lose trust and credibility among the Muslims, which trigger their failure and systematic risks as well (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). In fear of such eventualities, IBs do not violate Islamic business practices; as such, it is highly unlikely that they altered their banking practices before, during and after the 2008/09 crisis to match the US banking practices. Alongside the above, it would be important to stress the importance of sound governance in IBs because their failures are likely to affect many people and institutions including insurance companies, which do not take deposits from Muslims. In addition, the failure of IBs is also likely to affect investment account holders because they do not have direct right of monitoring the management of IBs.

In view of the above, the external supervisory boards ensure that banks observe high levels of transparency as they engage in Islamic banking practices and even offer services to their respective customers. More importantly, they ensure that IBs adhere to standards relating to liquidity risks, capital adequacy and other important banking practices. In view of this, Siddiqi (2009) opines that it is almost impossible for IBs to engage in unethical business practices because of two main reasons. Firstly, the Islamic business practices require banks to provide clear business contracts that are easily understood by banks and their respective customers. While one might be persuaded to think that the business contracts that CBs provide to their respective customers are always clear, it is rather obvious that CBs are more business-minded than IBs. As a result, they normally leave out certain issues unclear so that they can exploit them whenever need arises. This partly explains why some of them engaged in exploitative business practices to earn more profits charged on mortgages (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). While this is the case, there is high level of transparency and risk disclosure among IBs. Secondly, IBs offer products and services, which are permissible under Islamic business practices. While the same might be said about CBs, the practices that transpired before the crisis negate this presumption.

Similarly, it would be important to provide of a general supervisory mechanisms utilized to govern CBs throughout the world. The mechanism is largely thought to have exposed CBs to the crisis and its subsequent effects; as such, it deemed appropriate to provide it

before providing the conceptual framework. The governance mechanism is provided in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: The CBs' governance structure

From an ethical viewpoint, it is quite clear that there lacks an overall body that ensures that CBs engage in ethical business practices as Figure 3.2 depicts. This is in spite of the fact that one might contend that central banks and other supervisory bodies do that job; hence, no need of such a body. While arguing this way, it would be important to note that IBs like their conventional counterparts are equally subject to rules and regulations issued by central banks in their respective countries. However, beyond central banks they have several Islamic-based bodies such as the Sharia board that ensure that they conduct their banking practices within the confines of Sharia law. In contrast, CBs do not have such bodies and the ones in existence only make sure that they follow laid out procedures. As a result, the ethical issues are left out to individual banks to determine how to deal them. While this practice is good businesswise, it exposes banks to considerable risks as the 2008/09 financial crisis depicts.

3.4 Relationship between banking crisis and various financial ratios

A preliminary literature review depicts a close relationship between banks' financial ratios and the way banks perform at any given time (Boyes, 2009). It shows that banks with high financial ratios are unlikely to experience financial challenges whereas their counterparts with low financial ratios are likely to experience financial challenges (Alshammari, 2017). The working capital ratio, which measures the banks' abilities to meet their short-term obligations, is an important liquidity ratio. Given that it determines the ability of a bank to meet its short-term obligations, then it is an important ratio especially in determining the effects of financial crisis on Saudi banks (Alshammari, 2017). A higher ratio would indicate that the banks were able to meet their short-term obligations during the crisis whereas a lower ratio would indicate that they were unable to meet those obligations during the crisis.

With regard to profitability ratios, banks like other institutions should make profits so that they can provide shareholders with appropriate returns to expand their capital bases and build confidence among depositors. In spite of this, it would be important to note that higher earnings act as first lines of defence against liquidity risks, credit risks and currency risks among other types of risks (Zehri, Abdelbaki, & Bouabdellah, 2012). The most important profitability ratios in banking include the ROA, interest spread, and ROE. The ROE measures the amount of return generated from shareholders' equity; hence, a higher ratio is better than a lower one. The ROA on its part measures the efficiency of management teams; hence, a higher ratio is also better than a lower one. The best thing about ROA and ROE is that they both evaluate banks' profitability from two different perspectives. Alshammari (2017) argues that ROE depicts the management teams' efficiencies in utilizing shareholders' equity whereas ROA, on the other hand, depicts the management teams' ability to utilize assets to generate profits. The two different perspectives were relevant to the current study; hence, they were included in the analysis to evaluate banks efficiency and profitability during and after the crisis.

In the light of the above, the profitability ratios could also identify the way Saudi banks fared before, during and after the crisis with a possibility of determining the ones that were affected significantly by the crisis than others. Nevertheless, in line with

Almanaseer (2014) it may be possible that both types of banks were impacted by the crisis negatively because investors did not have money to invest during the crisis. In such a case, then the difference between the performances of IBs could not be statistically different from that of the conventional one (Alshammari, 2017). Accordingly, it would be important to evaluate the nature of the effect to determine whether it was positive or negative. If it was positive, then the profitability ratios would be expected to increase slightly, but if the nature of the effect was negative, then the profitability ratios would be expected to decrease slightly.

According to Zehri, Abdelbaki and Bouabdellah (2012), the profitability ratios depict IBs as more profitable than CBs even though the difference does not tend to be significant statistically. In spite of this, during the crisis the profitability ratios for the two types of banks were statistically different from each implying that CBs operating in Islamic states were impacted negatively by the crisis whereas the IBs were impacted by it positively. Erfani and Vasigh (2018) identify the Altman's z-score, which was developed in 1968, as an effective model for determining the financial health of various institutions. They claim that institutions with high financial ratios are able to withstand financial challenges whereas those with low financial ratios are likely to collapse sometimes in the future. In spite of this, it would be important to note that the accuracy of the model depends on the accuracy of the data that institutions provide implying that if they provide inaccurate data, then the model is likely to be faulty. In contrast, if they provide accurate data, the model is likely to provide accurate estimates of institutional financial health (Alshammari, 2017). An institution with a model score above 3 is regarded to be safe whereas that with a score between 2.7 and 2.99 is regarded to be in grey region and that with values below 1.8 is regarded to be in distress region.

The first discriminate factor (working capital/total assets) included in Altman's analysis depicts the net liquid assets within a firm in relation to firms' total capitalization. As a result, in contrast to working capital that evaluates the liquidity of a firm devoid of total capitalization, the discriminate factor evaluates the liquidity of a firm in the presence of its total capitalization. In so doing, it shows the way a firm performs in relation to its total assets (Altman, 1968). A review of the literature shows that firms that experience

operating losses tend to have shrinking current assets that affect their performances and even their risks of bankruptcy during financial crises (Erfani & Vasigh, 2018). In view of this, the discriminate factor was included in the analysis to depict the extent to which banks included in the analysis experienced liquidity challenges throughout the financial crisis.

In contrast to the above, the second discriminate factors; retained earnings/total assets, depicts the extent to which firms accumulate profits over time. The unfortunate thing with this factor is that it includes age of a firm in its analysis (Altman, 1968). As a result, relatively new firms may have relatively lower retained earnings/total assets ratios because of the shorter time they have to accumulate profits in comparison to well-established firms. In spite of this, it would be worth noting that the likelihood of such a scenario is more theoretical than practical because the incidences of failure extend beyond the age of firms (Erfani & Vasigh, 2018). In the light of this, the factor was also included in the analysis to depict the extent to which Saudi banks included in the analysis were at the risk of failing or even filing for bankruptcy.

The third discriminate factor, earnings before interest and taxes/total assets, on the other hand, depicts the actual productivity of firms' assets (Altman, 1968). Because the existence of Saudi banks included in the analysis was dependent on the earning ability of their assets then the factor was critical in the determination of the effects of the crisis on Saudi banks. Accordingly, it was also included in the analysis. Furthermore, because the banks included in the analysis were publicly listed on national stock exchange markets, the fourth discriminate factor; equity market value/total debt book value was also included in the analysis to measure banks' equity. The intention was to determine the extent to which banks' asset prices declined in value as measured by equity and market value (Erfani & Vasigh, 2018). The factor was instrumental in the analysis because it incorporated market value in the analysis. Similarly, the fifth discriminate factor; sales/total assets, was also included in the analysis because it depicted the ability of the banks to generate income from their assets (Altman, 1968). In addition, it depicted the extent to which banks' management teams were effective at dealing with competitive conditions in the Saudi banking industry.

3.5: Empirical studies on the impact of the 2008 global financial crisis on CBs and IBs

Prior to looking at the empirical studies that relate to the 2008/09 financial crisis, it would be important to note that a number of them have established that the principles of Islamic finance played a significant role in protecting IBs from the negative effects of the financial crisis. One unique thing about these principles is that they do not allow banks to carry out some of the practices such as Credit Default Swaps (CDSs), Collateralized Debt Obligation (CDO) and Mortgage-Based Securities (MBS), which led to the financial crisis (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). Although some of the studies claim that IBs did not succumb to the effects of the crisis because their banking practices were protective in nature, Warde (2012) claims that IBs only endured the first phase of the crisis because most of practices that contributed to its development could not pass the Sharia boards of IBs. While this might be considered a far-fetched argument by the researchers who maintain that IBs were not impacted by the crisis, it has significant implications to the current study. It simply means that if the Islamic banking practices did not protect the Saudi IBs from the negative effects of the crisis, then notable changes need to be taken in Saudi banking practices to protect the banking industry from such effects of a similar crisis.

Hasan and Dridi (2010) were among the first people to evaluate the performance of both types of banks in GCC countries during the crisis by evaluating their external rating, asset and credit growth as well as profitability. They argued that the region had witnessed a significant growth in IBs thereby it was an important areas of research. Upon conducting their study, they established that the two types of banks had been affected by the crisis differently. They argued that the business model that was utilized by IBs limited the adverse effects of the crisis on the banks whereas the loopholes in the risk management of CBs exposed them to high risks in their profitability (Hasan & Dridi, 2010). In addition, they established that the asset and credit growth for IBs performed better than that for their conventional counterparts. For this reason, IBs were rated as better on risk management than their counterparts demonstrating the extent to

which Islamic banking practices minimized the effects of the 2008/09 crisis on IBs in GCC.

Parashar and Venkatesh (2010) evaluated the effects of the crisis on GCC region-based banks by comparing and contrasting the performance of IBs with the performance of CBs during the crisis. With the help of 12 IBs and 12 CBs, the authors established that the leverages, Return on Average Equity (ROAE) and capital ratios for IBs were affected more than their counterparts for CBs. In contrast, the liquidity and Return on Average Assets (ROAA) for CBs were affected more than their counterparts for IBs during the crisis (Parashar & Venkatesh, 2010). Despite the differences, the authors concluded that IBs performed better than their conventional counterparts between 2006 and 2009.

Kassim and Abd Majid (2010) evaluated the impact of the 1997 and 2007 financial crisis on Malaysia IBs using data collected between 1997 and 2009. With reference to the periods that both crisis occurred, the authors defined the period between July 1997 and September 1999 as the time that the Asian financial crisis occurred whereas that between July 2007 and September 2009 as the period that the 2008/09 financial crisis occurred. They then defined the period between the two crises as the non-crisis period. With the help of vector auto-regressive method, the authors established that the Malaysian IBs were impacted by both crises (Kassim & Abd Majid, 2010). Even though the study was conducted in Malaysia as opposed to KSA, its findings were of great importance to the current study because they suggested that if both types of banks were impacted by the crisis, then effective measures should be put in place in KSA to protect both types of banks from financial crisis.

Jaffar and Manarvi (2011) compared the performance of IBs with that of CBs in Pakistan for the period between 2005 and 2009. This was partly before and during the financial crisis; as such, it was a critical period to the current study. They utilized CAMEL factors, which included liquidity position, earning ability, management quality, asset quality and capital adequacy to measure banks' performance. The data that was utilized to conduct the study was obtained from banks' financial statements and the study's sample included 5 banks from each category. The authors established that IBs

had better liquidity positions and adequate capital whereas CBs outperformed them in earnings and management (Jaffar & Manarvi, 2011). In terms of assets, they did not establish significant difference between both types of banks even though CBs had slight losses on loans.

The one notable finding from Jaffar and Manarvi's (2011) study was that the slight differences in both types of banks had slight impact on their performances. Accordingly, it could not be concluded that IBs outperformed the conventional ones in all aspects. In spite of this, an important take-away from this study was that the debt-to-equity ratio, which evaluated the extent to which both types of banks financed their banking practices using debts, showed significant difference between both types of banks. The authors identified IBs as minimizing their dependence on debts to finance their banking practices during the financial crisis whereas their conventional counterparts were shown to depend more on debts to finance their banking practices (Jaffar & Manarvi, 2011). In the light of this, the current study evaluated this aspect to determine the way both types of banks exposed themselves to risks during the financial crisis.

Ganic (2012) evaluated the impact of the crisis on the Western Balkans' banking sector by focusing much of his attention on cross-country analysis. He established that even though the depth of the crisis in the region was not yet developed, the impact had affected the profitability, asset quality and credit growth of the banks that participated in the study. He also established that even though the banks considered in the analysis performed differently, their results showed that the crisis had a substantial effect on the banking sector in the region (Ganic, 2012). Even though KSA is somewhat different from western Balkan region, its findings suggest that CBs in KSA could have been impacted in one way or the other by the crisis. This effect could have permeated to their credit growth, asset quality and profitability among other areas. However, very few studies if any have sought to evaluate this area. As a result, it was necessary to evaluate the extent to which the crisis affected the Saudi Arabian banks.

In the light of the above, Zehri, Abdelbaki and Bouabdellah (2012) evaluated the effects of the crisis on the performance of IBs by comparing them with the conventional ones. In contrast to the other studies, the authors utilized logit model using stepwise method.

They established that the accounting ratios that were utilized in the study were good discriminators between CBs and IBs within the international context. In addition, they established that IBs were relatively stable than their counterparts during the financial crisis. Zehri, Abdelbaki and Bouabdellah (2012) linked the better performance of the IBs to the Sharia law that dictated the banking practices of those banks implying that bank characteristics could have contributed to the impact that was identified between CBs and IBs. In spite of this finding, very few studies have been conducted in KSA to evaluate the manner in which both types of banks were impacted by the recent financial crisis. To fill this gap, the current study was conducted to determine the possible differences between both types of banks and the extent to which banks' characteristics protected or did not protect both types of banks from the effects of the crisis.

In contrast to the above studies, Abdulle and Kassim (2012) evaluated the impact of the crisis on Malaysian banks by comparing the performance of CBs with that of the IBs. The three main variables that were compared in the analysis included credit risk, liquidity and profitability and the period of study was between 2006 and 2010. A ratio analysis method was adopted to compare 9 CBs with 6 IBs. The study established that there was no significant difference in credit worth and profitability of the banks during the crisis and that they were both on an upward trend (Abdulle & Kassim, 2012). In addition, it established that IBs held more liquidity assets than conventional ones; as such, they were less exposed to liquidity risks than their counterparts. While the study did not establish any significant difference between the two sets of banks, it provided a method that could be utilized to minimize the conflict between liquidity and profitability within banking sector. In addition, it demonstrated that banks could hold more liquidity assets to protect themselves from liquidity risks.

Shafique, Faheem and Abdullah (2012) evaluated the impact of the crisis on IBs after the crisis took place. They established that even though Islamic banking was also vulnerable to the crisis, it was not affected significantly by it because its system was interest-free. They suggested that the demand for Islamic banking was increasing considerably in the western world finance system especially after the financial crisis (Shafique, Faheem, & Abdullah, 2012). This area could be an emerging area of

research, but the current study does not evaluate it; hence, other studies may evaluate it.

Merchant (2012) evaluated the effects of the crisis by comparing and contrasting the performance of IBs and CBs in GCC region between 2008 and 2011. With a sample of 10 CBs and 17 IBs, the author established that CBs were able to increase their Equity to Total Asset (EQTA) and Loan Loss Reserve (LLR) whereas IBs increased their LLR only after the crisis (Merchant, 2012). In spite of this, IBs were identified as possessing adequate capital structures even though their management efficiency were poor whereas their Return on Average Equity (ROAE) were lower than ROAE for CBs.

Al-Smadi, Hamdan and Almsafir (2013) compared and contrasted the performance of IBs with that of conventional ones in Malaysia during the 2007 global crisis and the 1997 Asian financial crisis. They utilized business growth, liquidity, operational efficiency and profitability to measure the performance. They established that IBs performed better than the conventional ones because their systems were competent. During the same period, Onakoya and Onakoya (2013) compared the performance of CBs with that of Islamic ones in the United Kingdom for the period between 2007 and 2011. They included the top five CBs and four Islamic ones in the analysis and collected secondary data from banks' financial statements. In addition, they focused much of their attention on banks' risk, profitability, efficiency, solvency and liquidity. They established that both types of banks were almost similar in terms of business orientation and performance indicators such as efficiency, solvency, risk, liquidity and profitability (Onakoya & Onakoya, 2013). In spite of this, CBs were relatively more profitable and able to meet their financial obligations on time and more effectively even if they depended largely on external sources to fund their projects. Nonetheless, IBs were not exposed to liquidity risks than their counterparts and they were more cost effective.

Ouerghi (2014) evaluated the resilience of IBs to financial crisis in comparison to CBs using z-score and equity mean test. The analysis was carried out by evaluating the way both types of banks performed before, during and after the financial crisis on the basis of banks' efficiency, leverage, capital adequacy, liquidity and profitability. The study established that IBs were less profitable, less efficient and more prone to credit risks

than their counterparts (Ouerghi, 2014). In addition, the study established that smaller banks tended to do better than the larger ones. Furthermore, it established that IBs were financially unstable in comparison to conventional ones even though they performed relatively better than large CBs.

Waemustafa and Sukri (2015) evaluated the specific macroeconomics dynamics that determined the credit risk for CBs and IBs in Malaysia for the period between 2000 and 2010. They collected secondary data from banks' financial statements and utilized multiple regression analysis to analyze the data they collected from 13 IBs and 15 CBs. They established that credit risk determinants for both types of banks were influenced largely by the availability of credit risk information. In addition, they established that Islamic contracts and regulatory capital were the main determinants for credit risk among IBs whereas liquidity, earning management, size, regulatory capital, debt-to-total asset ratios and loan loss provision were the main determinants for credit risk among CBs (Waemustafa & Sukri, 2015). Furthermore, they established that M3 and inflation were the significant macroeconomic factors for both types of banks.

Tanim-UI-Islam and Ashrafuzzaman (2015) compared and contrasted the performance of CBs with that of Islamic ones in Bangladesh using CAMEL analysis for the period between 2009 and 2013. This was immediately after the crisis ended; hence, it was significant to the current study. Ten banks; five from each category was selected to participate in the study. The data was collected from the banks' financial statements and independent t test was utilized to evaluate the possible differences between the performances of both types of banks. The study did not establish any significant difference between the banks' capital adequacy, earnings and management capability (Tanim-UI-Islam & Ashrafuzzaman, 2015). However, it established significant difference in asset quality with Islamic ones holding higher amounts of loans than their conventional counterparts.

Derbali (2015) appraised the performance of IBs from seven different Islamic states between 2006 and 2012. Using a multivariate regression model, he established that IBs from the countries included in the analysis were not impacted by the crisis. Ibrahim (2015) compared the performance of IBs and CBs in UAE before the financial crisis

occurred in 2007 and 2008. His analysis focused much of the attention on share performance, capital structure, management capacity, profitability and liquidity. He utilized descriptive statistical tools to rank these performance indicators. In contrast to studies conducted before, he went a step further to measure the financial stability of the banks included in the study. He established that both types of banks performed reasonably well between 2002 and 2006. In spite of this fact, IBs appeared to be relatively stable and perform better in shares even if their conventional counterparts had higher degrees of liquidity, capital structure and profitability (Ibrahim, 2015). This demonstrated that even if IBs might be relatively stable because they do not expose themselves to excessive risks, they do not make higher profits than their counterparts.

Al-Deehani, El-Sadi and Al-Deehani (2015) compared and contrasted the performance of IB from GCC countries with the performance of their conventional counterparts from the same countries. They utilized the multivariate general linear model to estimate the differences both types of banks before and during the crisis. With the help of a sample of twenty-five banks from the region, the authors established that there was statistically significant difference between the performances of both types of banks (Al-Deehani, El-Sadi & Al-Deehani, 2015). The notable difference was identified between the banks' loan/asset ratio with the IBs' ratio increasing significantly whereas that for CBs remained relatively the same.

Alongside the above, Al-Deehani, El-Sadi and Al-Deehani (2015) established that even if the deposits/asset ratio for CBs was relatively higher than that for IBs before the crisis, it reduced significantly during the crisis implying that most of the customers for CBs did not deposit money as they deposited before the crisis. Although many factors might have contributed to the decline in deposits, the fact remained that the crisis was responsible for part of the decline in deposits. Furthermore, the study established that even IBs managed to attract more deposits than their conventional counterparts during the crisis; most of them experienced dramatic decreases in ROE than their conventional counterparts experienced (Al-Deehani, El-Sadi & Al-Deehani, 2015).

Sukmana and Febriyati (2016) conducted a similar study in Indonesia using the financing deposit ratio, loan deposit ratio, non-performing loans and financing,

operational costs and revenues as well as return on assets. They covered the period between 2004 and 2014 meaning that the impact of the global crisis was also included in the analysis. They utilized the paired t test was to evaluate whether there was significant difference on the performance of the two types of banks. They established that the operational costs and revenues, non-performing loans, return on assets and capital adequacy ratios for CBs were significantly higher than those for the IBs (Sukmana & Febriyati, 2016). The capital adequacy results highlighted the need for IBs to acquire more capital so that they would be able to face inherent risks.

Aziz, Husin and Hashmi (2016) compared and contrasted the performance of CBs with that of IBs in Pakistan between 2006 and 2014. Although they did not focus much of their attention on the effects of the crisis on the two types of banks, they covered the period that the crisis occurred; hence, their study was relevant to the current study. Upon comparing and contrasting the two types of banks, they established that Pakistan IBs has higher levels of efficiency, asset quality and returns than their conventional counterparts (Aziz, Husin & Hashmi, 2016). In spite of this, the authors established that IBs were struggling in areas related to liquidity, capital, deposits, investment and advances whereas their conventional counterparts performed better in these areas. In contrast to other studies, the study established that Pakistan IBs needed to enhance their profit sharing processes to boost their credibility among depositors. In addition, they recommended that they needed to develop new products and solutions that meet customers' needs.

Saddique et al (2016) evaluated the effects of the crisis on both types of banks by comparing and contrasting the performance of Pakistan banks. With the help of regression analysis, the authors established that the crisis had notable negative effects on the performance of both types of banks before and after the crisis (Saddique et al, 2016). In spite of this, the authors claimed that the effects were relatively less on IBs than they were on CBs implying that the effects were heavy on CBs.

Dalaien (2016) evaluated the impact of the crisis on Indian and Jordanian banking sector, but in contrast to the former study, he collected data from fourteen banks; seven from each country. The variables evaluated in this study included non-performing

assets, interest rates, banks' deposit-lending ratio, banks' capital adequacy and their share prices. He established that the crisis affected Jordanian banks negatively whereas it provided Indian banks with growth opportunity. In particular, he established that the share prices for Jordanian banks declined immediately after the crisis thereby affected non-performing assets, capital adequacy and deposit-lending ratio negatively. In contrast, the share prices for Indian banks went up after the crisis thereby affected positively all the variables that were evaluated in the study (Dalaien, 2016). This suggested that while financial crisis was expected to have affected CBs negatively, it was possible that it affected them positively. This was an important finding because the effects of the financial crisis could be expected to be either positive or negative.

A similar study was carried out by Latif et al (2016) in Pakistan, but with a special attention on the nature of IBs in the country between 2006 and 2010. Once again, this was an important period for the current study because it covered the period before and after the crisis. In contrast to other studies, banks' performance was measured using trend analysis and twelve financial ratios, which addressed themselves to banks' efficiency, liquidity, risk and profitability. The study established that IBs were relatively less risky, more efficient and solvent than the conventional ones. In spite of this, CBs were found to be relatively profitable than their Islamic counterparts (Latif et al, 2016). The trend analysis established that IBs had relatively better income and balance sheet statements in comparison to the conventional ones. The study concluded that the findings were of great importance to IBs because they identified the need for those banks to improve their performance.

In line with the above, Prastawa and Zen (2016) compared the performance of Islamic and non-Islamic banks in Indonesia between 2004 and 2014. They established that IBs in the country had outperformed the non-Islamic ones in terms of liquidity and asset-liquidity ratios. Accordingly, they concluded that IBs were growing at a relatively higher rate than the non-Islamic ones in Indonesia (Prastawa & Zen, 2016). Although the current study did not evaluate the growth of IBs in KSA, it would be an interesting field of study for further studies.

A similar study was also conducted among GCC countries by Miah and Uddin (2017), but with a special attention to banks' stability and efficiency. The study's data was obtained from 28 IBs and 48 CBs for the period between 2005 and 2015. The accounting ratios, ordinary least square regression and stochastic frontier analysis techniques were utilized to analyze the data. The study established that CBs managed costs more effectively than their Islamic counterparts. In spite of this, IBs were more stable to short-term solvency even though this stability was not long-term. The study also established that the operations of both types of banks were significantly different from each other even after controlling banks' specific variables (Miah & Uddin, 2017). Furthermore, it established that highly capitalized banks tended to be more stable and cost ineffective suggesting that such banks had failed to capitalize on leverage effect.

During the same period, Wahab, Rosman and Zainol (2017) evaluated the efficiency of IBs during the financial crisis using empirical data from Asian banks. They covered the period between 2007 and 2011 meaning that they did not cover the period before the crisis occurred. They established that banks' management structures were the main sources of efficiency and inefficiency for the Asian banks that were included in the study.

Alshammari (2017) evaluated the effects of the crisis on banks by comparing and contrasting the performance of GCC region-based IBs with the performance of their conventional counterparts between 2003 and 2015. Although there were notable differences between countries, performance measures and period included in the analysis, the author established that CBs included in the analysis outperformed their Islamic counterparts (Alshammari, 2017). In spite of this, the author did not establish any significant effects of the crisis on the banks; hence, concluded that they were not impacted by the crisis. This was in spite of the fact that there was notable decline in their profitability due to economic downturn.

Cerovic, Nikolaj and Maradin (2017) evaluated the effects of the crisis on IBs and CBs by evaluating their efficiency and stability before, during and after the crisis using a literature review approach. The authors established that IBs were more efficient and stable than their conventional counterparts before, during and after the crisis (Cerovic,

Nikolaj, & Maradin, 2017). Accordingly, they contended that regulation of the financial market was important in enhancing the efficiency and stability of the banking system.

Wiryo and Effendi (2018) conducted a similar study, but focused much of their attention on IBs. In contrast to the above studies, they utilized panel data and regression model to analyze the secondary data they collected from Indonesian banks' financial statements for the period between 2010 and 2016. They established that banks' sizes had positive influence on credit risks. Other variables such as inflation, GDP, financing quality and expansion were found to affect credit risk negatively. Qureshi (2018) conducted a similar study in Pakistan between 2010 and 2017. This was immediately after the crisis ended; as such, it was important to the current study. He utilized the CAMELS approach to measure the performance of the banks that participated in the study. He established that IBs were effective at managing capital, liquidity and enhancing earnings.

Dodoev (2018) conducted a similar study in Malaysia without necessarily focusing his attention on the impact of the crisis on the banking sector. However, he covered the period between 2006 and 2016 meaning that he literally covered the period that the crisis occurred. He utilized the CAMEL ratio analysis to evaluate the financial performance of the eight banks; four from each category. In addition, he applied a two tailed t-test to examine the possible difference between the performances of various factors namely; net interest margin, loans, assets and profits that were included in the analysis. He established that there was no significant difference in the performance of CBs and IBs (Dodoev, 2018). Nevertheless, IBs outperformed their conventional counterparts in all aspects of CAMEL model. This suggested that IBs could have performed better than conventional ones even during the crisis.

Ulussever (2018) compared and contrasted the performance and corporate governance of CBs and IBs from different parts of the world for the period between 2005 and 2011. A total of 154 banks; 77 from each category was selected to participate in the study. The two-step generalized methods of moment and random effect GLM method were utilized to analyze the data that was collected using questionnaires. The study established that corporate governance was stronger in IBs than in CBs because CEOs

and boards were powerful in IBs. Also, it established that whereas return variables for IBs were correlated positively to board structure variables and financial disclosure index, they were negatively correlated to CEO related variables and risk closure index (Ulussever, 2018). Accordingly, financial disclosure indices and corporate governance had negative effects on the performance of IBs. This meant that they decreased IBs' profitability. In addition, the study established that corporate governance for CBs were more effective and better than those for the IBs.

Alqahtani and Mayes (2018) evaluated the financial stability of IBs from GCC region during the 2008/09 financial crisis by comparing their performance with the performance of their conventional counterparts between 2000 and 2013. With the help of market-based and accounting-based measures, the authors established that there was no statistically significant difference between the two types of banks during the crisis. Nonetheless, as soon as the effects of the crisis spread to other parts of economies during the later phases of the crisis, the IBs suffered higher levels of financial instability than their conventional counterparts suggesting that IBs were also affected negatively by the crisis. In spite of this, the effects were largely true for large IBs and not the small ones implying that large banks were impacted more by the crisis than the small ones (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2018). The authors argued that their findings supported the idea that IBs were more stable financially when they operated as small banks as opposed to when they operated as large banks. As a consequence, it might be concluded that IBs may not be substitute to CBs especially during financial crisis.

Khartabiel, Ahmad and Bakar (2019) compared the performance of IBs with that of CBs in Malaysia for the period between 2005 and 2016. They utilized eight financial ratios that included lending intensity, liquidity, skills utilization, customer deposits, return on average equity, bank size, return on average asset and leverage to measure banks' performance. A t test was utilized to evaluate the difference in the performance of the two types of banks for the period before and after the financial crisis. The authors established that the performance of the two types of banks was significantly different for the period that was considered in the analysis (Khartabiel, Ahmad, & Bakar, 2019). In particular, they established that CBs were relatively larger and profitable, but riskier than

IBs. Nonetheless, IBs were able to utilize their skills more effectively and tended to be more liquid than their counterparts.

Table 3.1 summarizes the empirical studies with a view to provide an overview of what has been done and possible gaps that the current study attempts to fill.

Table 3.1: A summary of the empirical studies

Author(s)	Sample	Methodology	Country/Region of study	Findings
Hasan & Dridi (2010)	30 IBs and 90 CBs, which in total was 120 banks	Descriptive statistics	GCC region	<p>The business model utilized by IBs limited the adverse effects of the crisis on IBs whereas the loopholes in the risk management of CBs exposed them to high risks in their profitability.</p> <p>The asset and credit growth for IBs performed better than the credit growth for their conventional counterparts.</p> <p>As a consequence, IBs were rated as performing better on risk management than their conventional counterparts</p>
Parashar & Venkatesh (2010)	12 IBs and 12 CBs	Comparative analysis	GCC countries	<p>The leverages, Return on Average Equity (ROAE) and capital ratios for IBs were affected by the crisis more than their counterparts for CBs.</p> <p>The liquidity and Return on Average Assets (ROAA) for CBs were affected by the crisis</p>

				<p>more than their counterparts for IBs.</p> <p>Despite the differences, the study concluded that IBs performed better than their conventional counterparts between 2006 and 2009</p>
Kassim & Abd Majid (2010)	Not specified	Vector auto-regressive	Malaysia	Malaysian IBs were impacted by the 1997 Asian and 2007 global financial crises
Jaffar & Manarvi (2011)	5 IBs and 5 CBs	CAMEL analysis factors	Pakistan	<p>IBs had better liquidity positions and adequate capital whereas CBs outperformed them in earnings and management</p> <p>In terms of assets, the study did not establish significant difference between both types of banks even though CBs had slight loan losses</p>
Ganic (2012)	Unspecified	A cross-country comparison of banks in the region	Western Balkan region	The crisis affected the profitability, asset quality and credit growth of the banks that participated in the study

Zehri, Abdelbaki & Bouabdellah (2012)	110 samples (59 CBs 51 IBs)	Logit model	International context	<p>The accounting ratios that were utilized in the study were good discriminators between CBs and IBs within the international context.</p> <p>IBs were relatively stable than their counterparts during the financial crisis</p> <p>The study linked the better performance of the IBs to the Sharia law that dictated the banking practices of the IBs</p>
Abdulle & Kassim (2012)	9 CBs with 6 IBs	A ratio analysis method	Malaysia	<p>There was no significant difference in credit worth and profitability of the banks during the crisis</p> <p>Nonetheless, IBs held more liquidity assets than conventional ones; hence, they were less exposed to liquidity risks than their counterparts</p>
Merchant (2012)	10 CBs and 17 IBs	Quantitative study that utilized the CAMEL framework	GCC countries	<p>The study established that CBs were able to increase their Equity to Total Asset (EQTA) and Loan Loss Reserve (LLR) whereas IBs increased their LLR only after the crisis.</p> <p>In spite of the above, IBs were identified as</p>

				possessing adequate capital structures even though their management efficiency were poor whereas their Return on Average Equity (ROAE) were lower than ROAE for CBs.
Shafique, Faheem & Abdullah (2012)	Unspecified	Literature review	Unspecified	The study established that even though Islamic banking was also vulnerable to the crisis, it was not affected significantly by it because its system was interest-free
Al-Smadi, Hamdan & Almsafir (2013)	Unspecified	Unspecified	Malaysia	The study established that IBs performed better than CBs because their systems were competent.
Onakoya & Onakoya (2013)	5 CBs and 4 IBs	Comparative study	UK	The study established that both types of banks were almost similar in terms of business orientation and performance indicators such as efficiency, solvency, risk, liquidity and profitability. However, CBs were relatively more profitable and able to meet their financial obligations on time and more effectively even if they depended largely on external sources to fund their projects. Nonetheless, IBs were not exposed to liquidity risks than their counterparts

				and they were more cost effective
Ouerghi (2014)	30 IBs and 64 CBs	z-score and equity mean test	GCC region	<p>The study established that IBs were less profitable, less efficient and more prone to credit risks than their conventional counterparts.</p> <p>The study also established that smaller banks tended to do better than the larger ones.</p> <p>Furthermore, it established that IBs were financially unstable in comparison to conventional ones even though they performed relatively better than large CBs.</p>
Waemustafa & Sukri (2015)	13 IBs and 15 CBs	Multiple regression analysis	Malaysia	<p>The study established that credit risk determinants for both types of banks were influenced largely by the availability of credit risk information. The study also established that Islamic contracts and regulatory capital were the main determinants for credit risk among IBs whereas liquidity, earning management, size, regulatory capital, debt-to-total asset ratios and loan loss provision were the main determinants</p>

				for credit risk among CBs. Furthermore, the study established that M3 and inflation were the significant macroeconomic factors for both types of banks.
Tanim-UI-Islam & Ashrafuzzaman (2015)	5 IBs and 5 CBs	CAMEL analysis using t test	Bangladesh	The study did not establish any significant difference between the banks' capital adequacy, earnings and management capability. However, it established significant difference in asset quality with Islamic ones holding higher amounts of loans than their conventional counterparts
Al-Deehani, El-Sadi & Al-Deehani (2015)	25 banks	Multivariate general linear model	GCC countries	The study established that there was statistically significant difference between the performances of both types of banks In addition, it established that even if the deposits/asset ratio for CBs was relatively higher than that for IBs before the crisis, it reduced significantly during the crisis
Ibrahim (2015)	Unspecified	descriptive statistical	UAE	The study established that both types of banks performed reasonably well between 2002 and

		tools		2006. In spite of this, IBs appeared to be relatively stable and perform better in shares even if their counterparts had higher degrees of liquidity, capital structure and profitability
Saddique et al. (2016)	Unspecified	Regression analysis	Pakistan	The study established that the crisis had notable negative effects on the performance of both types of banks before and after the crisis. In spite of this, the authors claimed that the effects were relatively less on IBs than they were on CBs implying that the effects were heavy on CBs.
Sukmana & Febriyati (2016)	Unspecified	Paired t test	Indonesia	The study established that the operational costs and revenues, non-performing loans, return on assets and capital adequacy ratios for CBs were significantly higher than those for the IBs.
Aziz, Husin & Hashmi (2016)	5 IBs and 5 CBs	Comparative study	Pakistan	The study established that Pakistan IBs had higher levels of efficiency, asset quality and returns than their conventional counterparts during the crisis. In spite of this, the authors established that IBs were struggling in areas related to liquidity, capital, deposits, investment

				and advances whereas their conventional counterparts performed better in these areas
Dalaien (2016)	Fourteen banks; seven from each country	Comparative method	India and Jordan	The study established that the crisis affected Jordanian banks negatively whereas it provided Indian banks with growth opportunity. This was in relation to the fact that the share prices for Jordanian banks declined immediately after the crisis thereby affected non-performing assets, capital adequacy and deposit-lending ratio negatively. In contrast, the share prices for Indian banks went up after the crisis thereby affected positively all the variables that were evaluated in the study
Latif et al. (2016)	5 IBs and 5 CBs	Trend analysis	Pakistan	The study established that IBs were relatively less risky, more efficient and solvent than the conventional ones. In spite of this, CBs were found to be relatively profitable than their Islamic counterparts.
Prastawa & Zen (2016)	1221 CBs and 77 IBs	Financial ratios	Indonesia	The study established that IBs in the country had outperformed the non-Islamic ones in terms

				of liquidity and asset-liquidity ratios.
Miah & Uddin (2017)	28 IBs and 48 CBs	accounting ratios, ordinary least square regression and stochastic frontier analysis techniques	GCC region	The study established that CBs managed costs more effectively than their Islamic counterparts. However, IBs were more stable to short-term solvency even though this stability was not long-term. The study also established that the operations of both types of banks were significantly different from each other even after controlling banks' specific variables. Furthermore, it established that highly capitalized banks tended to be more stable and cost ineffective suggesting that such banks had failed to capitalize on leverage effect.
Cerovic, Nikolaj & Maradin (2017)	Unspecified	Literature review	Unspecified	The authors established that IBs were more efficient and stable than their conventional counterparts before, during and after the crisis.
Alshammari (2017)	Unspecified	Comparative analysis	GCC countries	The study established that CBs included in the analysis outperformed their Islamic counterparts. However, the study did not establish any significant effects of the crisis on the banks; hence, concluded that they were not

				impacted by the crisis. In spite of this, there was notable decline in their profitability due to economic downturn.
Alqahtani & Mayes (2018)	76 banks	market-based and accounting-based measures	GCC countries	The study established that there was no statistically significant difference between the two types of banks during the crisis. Nonetheless, as soon as the effects of the crisis spread to other parts of economies during the later phases of the crisis, the IBs suffered higher levels of financial instability than their conventional counterparts suggesting that IBs were also affected negatively by the crisis. In spite of this, the effects were largely true for large IBs and not the small IBs.
Khartabiel, Ahmad & Bakar (2019)	6 IBs and 6 CBs	T test	Malaysia	The study established that the performance of the two types of banks was significantly different for the period that was considered in the analysis. In particular, they established that CBs were relatively larger and profitable, but riskier than IBs. Nonetheless, IBs were able to utilize their skills more effectively and tended to

				be more liquid than their conventional counterparts
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(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

3.6 Study's Hypotheses

The review of the literature provides mixed results with some of the studies showing that IBs and CBs were impacted differently by the 2008/09 financial crisis whereas others do not find any statistically significant difference between both types of banks. To determine the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry, the study hypothesized that banks' unique characteristics contributed to the way both types of banks were impacted or not impacted by the crisis. It presumed that if Saudi CBs implemented banking practices as implemented in other parts of the world, then they engaged in risky banking practices during the crisis. This could mean that Saudi CBs managed to make more profits before the crisis and probably make losses after the crisis. It could also mean that IBs in KSA did not record any significant profits/losses before, during and after the crisis because they did not alter their banking practices in any way. As a result, the study started by hypothesizing as follows;

H0₁: the performance of IBs in KSA was consistent during and after the 2008/09 financial crisis

In the event that Saudi CBs altered their banking practices prior to the 2008/09 financial crisis, then their performance before the crisis was significantly different from their performances after the crisis; thus, the study's second hypothesis was as follows;

H0₂: the performance of CBs in KSA was inconsistent during and after the financial crisis

From the above hypotheses, the study attempted to evaluate whether there was significant differences between the performances of the two types of banks. It was presumed that if the banking characteristics had any effect on the banks, then their performances would differ from each other. Accordingly, the third null hypothesis hypothesized as follows;

H0₃: There was no statistically significant difference between the performance of IBs and CBs in KSA between 2006 and 2010.

3.7: Research gap

In KSA, Ghassan, Alhajhoj and Alaoui (2013) evaluated the impact of the crisis on Saudi economy. They used both non-linear SVAR and linear methodologies to determine the interdependence between economic growth, net-exports and international liquidity. They established that the crisis dropped the net-exports by a big margin and as a result hampered economic growth in the kingdom for a period of about three years. Tabash and Dhankar (2014) evaluated the stability of Saudi Arabian IBs during the financial crisis using financial data collected between 2005 and 2010. They utilized trend analysis method to determine the banks' capital adequacy ratios and liquidity ratios. They also utilized the one-way ANOVA to evaluate the difference between the banks that were included in the analysis. They established that IBs in KSA were relatively stable because they had adequate capital and high levels of liquidity (Tabash & Dhankar, 2014). They concluded that their findings were in agreements with studies that identify IBs as strong and safe means of finance. In spite of this, they did not compare the performance of CBs in KSA with that of IBs to determine whether there was significant difference between their performances. To bridge the gap, the current study compared the performance of CBs and IBs in KSA during and after the financial crisis.

Akhtar (2010) evaluated whether Saudi banks were productive between 2000 and 2006 using the data envelopment analysis. Although the study did not evaluate the effects of the crisis on Saudi banks, it established that the improvements in the banks' productivity emanated from technological developments implying that the banks were less efficient. Miyajima (2017), on the other hand, evaluated the factors that influenced bank lending in KSA using the data collected between 2000 and 2015. Although this period was relatively similar to the one that the current study evaluated, the study did not evaluate the effects of the crisis on Saudi banks. However, it established that oil prices, economic activities and strong bank balance sheets were among the factors that influenced bank lending in KSA (Miyajima, 2017).

While the above studies have evaluated important areas of study, they do not compare and contrast the way Saudi IBs and CBs were impacted or not impacted by the crisis. In

addition, they do not evaluate the measures developed to protect the Saudi banking industry from financial crisis. As a result, in the midst of conflicting results that provide differing results on the impact of crisis on world's banking sector and the fact that majority of the studies conducted in KSA did not evaluate the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry, there was the need for the current study to be conducted. The current study sought to fill the research gap from two different perspectives. Firstly, it sought to contribute to the body of existing literature by depicting the way the industry was impacted or not impacted by the crisis. Secondly, it sought to update the studies that evaluate the effects of the crisis on Saudi economy by looking at the way Saudi banking industry was impacted by the crisis and measures put in place to protect the industry from a similar crisis that may occur in the future.

3.8: Conceptual framework

Figure 3.3 provides the study's conceptual framework. The framework provides the link between variables included in the study.

Figure 3.3: The study's conceptual framework

(Adapted from Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017)

Based on the literature review, the thesis presumed that the 2008/09 financial crisis was caused mainly by moral failure, imprudent lending, excessive leverages and supervision failure as well as excessive debts as Figure 4.3 depicts. The moral failure was defined as the inability of CBs in the world particularly in USA and developed countries to self-regulate themselves as it was expected of them. The presumption was that due to conflicts of interests the various parties involved in conventional banking practices were tempted by the lucrative housing business and other businesses to offer unethical banking products and services. This led to imprudent lending, which was defined as irresponsible lending that did not care about the capability of the low-income earners to repay their mortgages so long as they secured their mortgages with the houses they purchased (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017). In so doing, CBs did not evaluate the capability of low-income earners to repay their mortgages in the event that the house business was unsustainable.

As the above took place, the bodies mandated with the responsibility of supervising CBs and other financial institutions did not execute their mandates effectively because of market liberalization. In view of this, supervision failure was defined as the inability of the bodies mandated with supervising CBs failing to act and stop the unethical banking practices among CBs in good time. This was in line with FCIC (2011) that argued that the US Federal Reserve failed to prevent the toxic mortgages because it did not act in time to set the requisite standards. In addition, it was in line with Kayed and Hassan (2011) who argued that the governments' agencies mandated with supervising financial institutions were slow to act. The above resulted to highly leveraged debts, which the low-income earners could not service once the bubble in the housing market burst. As a consequence, the excessive debts were defined as the high number of loans and huge amounts of loans that CBs offered to their customers in effort to maximize profits from interests they charged on those loans especially the mortgage ones (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017).

The presumption was that the above factors resulted to development of toxic assets in forms of CDSs, CDO and MBS that impacted the way CBs offered their services and

even contributed to development of the crisis. The CDSs were the derivative instruments that CBs developed prior to the crisis to redistribute credit risks. They were literally privately negotiated mutual contracts promising buyers to compensate them in the event that loans and mortgages were defaulted (Terzi & Ulucay, 2011). The CDO was asset-backed securities that were backed either by bank loans, mortgages or corporate bonds. The funds used to purchase underlying assets were obtained from debt obligations. Although they were special purpose vehicles for investing in different pools of assets, they were common among CBs because they engaged in uncertain businesses. The MBS, on the other hand, were the mortgages that are pooled together and then sold to investors as diversified portfolios. Since they were diversified, they were considered less risky than mortgage contracts; hence, they were common prior to the crisis (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2017).

In contrast to the above, the thesis presumed that the Saudi IBs were not impacted by the financial crisis because contrary to CBs, they did not charge interests on loans. In addition, they prohibited uncertain banking practices derived from financial derivatives, which CBs allowed. Because of this, the moral failures, imprudent lending, excessive debts and leverages as well as supervision failure witnessed among CBs were not witnessed among them. As a result, the CDSs, CDO and MBS contributing to development of crisis in USA and elsewhere were not developed among Saudi IBs. In this respect, the crisis did not impact these banks directly. In contrast, the thesis presumed that it was highly likely that the Saudi CBs were influenced in one way or the other by banking practices in USA and other parts of the world at the time to outsmart the Saudi banking regulations. Accordingly, some of the toxic practices that contributed to development of the crisis were imported to KSA without the knowledge of the Saudi central bank and other relevant supervisory bodies. Based on this presumption, the thesis argued that the Saudi CBs were impacted by the crisis indirectly without the knowledge of relevant supervisory bodies because of external influence from CBs.

Apart from the above, the non-exposure of Saudi IBs to the crisis was also attributed to the various supervisory bodies that supervise the Islamic banking practices. The argument was that the bodies could not allow most of the banking practices that CBs

allowed to be practiced within Saudi IBs. The various supervisory bodies included in the conceptual framework included Islamic financial boards, which acted as external supervisory board, the internal Sharia supervisory board, which supervised IBs internally and the existing supervisory system. This was supported by Muslim self-discipline instilled by the Sharia business practices. While the thesis acknowledged the fact that it was possible for some laxity within the supervisory system, it appreciated the fact that the system was multifaceted; hence, unlikely to compromise it within the short time that the crisis lasted. In so doing, the thesis presumed that Saudi IBs were largely protected from exposure to the crisis; thus, ruled out the likelihood of crisis impacting the Saudi IBs. This was consistent with Warde (2012) who argued that IBs were able to survive the first phase of the crisis. In addition, it was consistent with researchers who argued that IBs were not affected in any way by the crisis.

In the midst of the above, the thesis appreciated the fact that even though Saudi IBs and to some extent Saudi CBs were not impacted by the crisis directly because they did not embrace the toxic banking practices, it was possible that they were impacted by the crisis indirectly. Accordingly, other factors were included in the conceptual framework to depict the indirect effect of the crisis on Saudi banking industry as a whole. Because the effect spread to all banks irrespective of their nature, some of its effects were thereby directed to IBs whereas another part of it was directed towards CBs. The presumption was that both types of banks were impacted by global recession and other factors that resulted from the crisis. In so doing, the thesis appreciated the fact that it was possible that both types of banks were impacted by the crisis irrespective of their banking practices. The presumption was that the effects of the crisis spilt over to other parts of the world including KSA regardless of the banking practices. Nevertheless, in making this presumption, the researcher was aware of the fact that the study may not detect the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry given the short time that the crisis lasted and the fact that by mid-2010 most of the emerging economies had recovered from the effects of the crisis (Rigobon, 2016).

Both ROA and ROE were utilized to measure the way Saudi banks performed during and after the crisis. The ROA measured banks' profitability in terms of the money

invested in assets whereas the ROE measured the profitability in terms of equity capital. While the above is the case, it would be important to note that the conceptual framework was aimed at understanding the manner in which the Saudi CBs were impacted or not impacted by the crisis rather than predict the occurrence of a similar crisis. As a result, the framework can be re-conceptualized and even modified based on the emergence of new data and even the evolution of the issue under investigation.

3.9 Chapter's summary

The chapter provides both theoretical and conceptual framework utilized to conduct the study. It identifies both contagion and spillover effect theories as the two main theories that can explain the way the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis spread to KSA and other parts of the world. In addition, it identifies the decoupling theory as the counter theory that could be utilized to depict the way the effects of the crisis did not spread to Saudi banking industry in the event they did not spread to it. Also, it has critically reviewed the body of existing studies with a view to placing the thesis in its rightful position in the light of what has been done. In so doing, it has established the link between the financial crisis and the banking sector by reviewing the factors that led to the crisis. Furthermore, it has identified the research gap and research questions emanating from the literature review and concluded by providing the study's hypotheses. The next chapter provides the methodology that was followed to conduct the thesis.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Chapter's Overview

Before providing the method that was utilized to conduct the study, it would be imperative to remember that the study had several interrelated objectives set within the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on the Saudi banking industry. The specific objectives included;

1. Evaluating critically the unique characteristics of the Saudi IBs and CBs that contributed or did not contribute to the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry.
2. Comparing and contrasting the way Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the 2008/09 financial crisis.
3. Evaluating the insolvency risk for Saudi CBs in relation to that for Saudi IBs during the crisis.
4. Identifying the forces emanating from the 2008/09 financial crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry
5. Formulating recommendations that could be used to minimize the effects of a probable financial crisis in the future on Saudi banking industry

The previous chapters particularly the second one devoted much of its focus on the first objective whereas the seventh chapter was devoted to the fifth objective. Accordingly, the empirical part of the study was devoted largely to the other objectives; second, third and fourth objectives. The second objective sought to compare and contrast the performance of the Saudi CBs with the performance of the Saudi IBs during and after the crisis. The third one sought to evaluate the insolvency of both types of banks during the crisis as part of determining the way both of them were impacted by the crisis. The fourth one sought to evaluate forces emanating from the crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry.

The third chapter identified a research gap in KSA that needed to be filled by conducting an empirical study in the kingdom. In the light of the gap, the current study was conducted to contribute to existing body of knowledge by identifying measures taken in the kingdom to strengthen the banking industry from the time the crisis ended. In view of the above, this part of the thesis provides the details of the research strategy utilized to collect both secondary and primary data utilized throughout the study.

4.2 Methodological review of research

4.2.1 Research philosophy

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) claim that the research philosophies that researchers adopt in studies have significant influence on the vital assumptions they hold towards the world. They add that the assumptions, on the other hand, have significant influence on the research methods and strategies that they adopt in the other parts of their studies (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). In view of this, the first part of the chapter starts by looking at the various research philosophies that could have been adopted in the current study before identifying and justifying the one that was adopted.

4.2.1.1 Positivism

This philosophy is normally adopted by natural scientists because it deals with observable realities. However, over the years, social scientists have slowly adopted it especially on issues related to observable social realities. By adopting it, researchers view reality as objective; hence, independent of people observing it (Aliyu et al., 2014). In so doing, they consider the quantifiable data they utilize in their studies as not influenced by impulsive human behaviors; hence, regard it as reliable to provide accurate results. While this is the case, it would be imperative to appreciate the fact that the philosophy deals with observable realities; hence, leaves out the unobservable ones. As a consequence, Leong (2008) believes that it treats symptoms without addressing the real problems.

While the above is the case, it would be worth noting that positivism had considerable influence on scientific practices especially in social science for a long time during the

early 20th century. This was partly because of its high level of accuracy in predicting social issues accurately, but because of human volition, most of its predictions became less reliable towards the end of the century (Leong, 2008). As a result, the philosophy was abandoned in favor of critical multiplism that argued that no single research approach was sufficient to explain different phenomena adequately.

In view of the above, researchers who hold positivist worldview perceive reality as predictable and measureable; hence, start by developing theories, which they test and even go ahead to draw inferences from the information they obtain from samples. In the light of this, the current study might be perceived as adopting a positivist worldview because it starts by developing theories, which are then tested based on data obtained from banks' sample (Biggam, 2008). Similarly, because it uses secondary data to evaluate the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry, it considers the effect of the crisis to be independent of the people who work in the industry; hence, might be considered to hold a positivist worldview. In spite of this, it would be important to note that the current study does not test such theories only; instead, it goes a step further to collect qualitative data utilized to answer the research questions not answered by the secondary data. In so doing, it goes beyond what the positivist worldview propagates; hence, does not adopt the positivist worldview to evaluate the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry.

4.2.1.2 Realism

Like positivism philosophy, this research philosophy is also related to scientific inquiries. Nonetheless, it presumes that people perceive reality through senses; thus, considers everything that senses provide as truthful and independent of human mind (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). By presuming so, it opposes the idealism theory that believes in the existence of mind and its context only thereby supports the idea behind collecting and analyzing data to understand it. In spite of this, there are two types of realism namely; critical and direct realism. The direct one asserts that things experienced in life through senses portray realities in life whereas the critical realism argues that such things are experienced through sensation; hence, tend to be unrealistic. In response,

direct realists argue that people see illusions because they lack sufficient information about realities.

The critical realists perceive realities in two different steps with the first one starting by seeing things and sensations they convey whereas the second step considers the mental process involved in understanding realities. The direct realists consider the first step to be sufficient in perceiving reality; hence, excludes mental processes in perceiving realities. Because researches in management and businesses are concerned about the social world that people live in, they often identify with critical realists more than they identify with direct realists (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). Accordingly, they emphasize on social structures that give rise to issues of interest they attempt to understand because they believe that perceived things provide bigger pictures only.

Inasmuch as the current study concurs with critical realists that things perceived in life and business practices keep on changing; hence, should be looked at from different levels, it does not base its arguments on senses. In addition, it does not approach the issue under investigation from a scientific approach like realism does even though it tests theories. In the light of this, it does not adopt realism philosophy in evaluating the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry.

4.2.1.3 Interpretivism

An interpretivism research philosophy on its part considers reality to exist in different forms, but goes ahead to consider those forms equally valid. It appreciates the fact that reality is able to change based on time and context meaning that it depends on time and context. In view of this, researchers who hold this research philosophical worldview conduct qualitative studies to understand the constructs that people hold in different contexts and at different time (Biggam, 2008). Such researchers believe that part of information from complex issues of life is lost when issues are reduced to simple laws like positivists reduce it.

While the current study attempts to capture the different views that people working in Saudi banking industry hold towards the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on the

industry, it also combines the qualitative data with quantitative one collected from banks' financial statements. In addition, while the study concurs with an interpretivism philosophical stand that part of information is lost in the analysis process when complex issues such as effects of the 2008/09 financial on Saudi banking industry are reduced to simple laws, it appreciates the fact the issue can be understood partly from law-like perspective. As a result, it does not adopt an interpretivism research philosophy because of the two reasons to evaluate the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry.

Before proceeding further, it would be important to define the terms epistemology and ontology because they will be critical in defining the other aspects included in the research onion as part of research philosophies. The ontology relates to the way researchers view realities in life; hence, determines whether they view them as either ever changing or constant meaning that, they do not change with time (Kumar, 2011). On the other hand, epistemology relates to the assumptions that researchers holds towards the best ways of studying realities in life. It determines whether a subjective approach or an objectivism approach should be utilized to study realities in life (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). An objectivism approach considers social entities independent of social actors that evaluate their existence whereas a subjectivism approach treats social phenomena as emanating from the actions and perceptions of social actors.

In the light of the above, researchers who view realities in life as consisting of social orders that keep on changing and who believe that such issues should be studied from objective perspectives adopt functionalist approach in their studies. The current study does not adopt a functionalism approach because inasmuch as it appreciates the fact that the world consists of social orders that keep on changing, it does not adopt an objectivism perspective. In other words, it does not believe the changes should be studied independent of people involved in changing them. Accordingly, it collects qualitative data to determine the way people working in Saudi banking industry perceive the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on the industry. On the other hand, researchers who believe that social orders in life should be studied from subjective

perspectives that attempt to reconcile differences among responses obtained from research participants adopt interpretivism approach in their studies. While the current study appreciates the fact that social studies should be studied from a subjective perspective thereby goes ahead to collect qualitative data, it also collects quantitative data from secondary sources to complement the subjective perspective. In so doing, it does not adopt an interpretivism perspective.

Researchers who believe that the world consists of radical changes that keep on changing and who believe that such changes should be studied from objectivism perspectives adopt radical structuralism approaches in their studies. Once again, while the current study appreciates the fact that social orders in life keep on changing, it does not adopt an objectivism perspective; hence, it does not utilize a radical structuralism approach to evaluate the effects of the 2008/09 crisis on Saudi banking industry. Lastly, researchers who evaluate radical changes in life from subjective perspective adopt radical humanism approaches in their studies. Once again, the current study does not adopt a pure subjective perspective in evaluating the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry; hence, does not utilize the radical humanism approach to evaluate the issue under investigation.

4.2.1.4 Pragmatism

In contrast to the above, the pragmatism research philosophy identifies research questions as the important elements for determining the epistemological and ontological perspective that one adopts in a study (Kaushik & Walsh, 2019). It argues that no single approach can be sufficient to explain phenomena in life; hence, appreciates the fact that different approaches can be combined in a study (Leong, 2008).

In line with pragmatism research philosophy, the current study appreciates the fact that no single approach can be utilized to evaluate the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry on its own. It appreciates the fact that different research approaches should be combined to understand the issue under investigation. Accordingly, it goes ahead to collect quantitative data from secondary sources and combine it with qualitative data obtained from people working in the Saudi banking

industry to understand the effects that the crisis had on Saudi banking industry. In so doing, it combines a subjective approach, which appreciates the fact that reality depends on social actors, with an objectivism approach that views reality as independent of social actors (Kumar, 2011). In line with this, a pragmatism research philosophy is adopted to conduct the current study.

4.2.2 Research approach

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) claim that a research may either be deductive meaning that it may be interested in testing theories or inductive meaning that it may be interested in building theories. This part of the thesis attempts to distinguish the two approaches with a view to justifying the research approach that was utilized to conduct the study.

4.2.2.1 Deductive approach

As indicated earlier on, this approach is concerned about testing theories meaning that it relies on existing theories to determine the way they apply to areas of interest (Kumar, 2011). Accordingly, it starts by identifying a theory that defines the way various variables in an area of interest relate with each other. Then it develops the operational hypotheses that indicate the way variables relate or do not relate with each other using deductive reasoning. The operational hypotheses are then tested to examine their specific outcomes, which are utilized to make the final decision. Based on the findings, the theory may either be verified or modified altogether. If modified, the process would be repeated to revise the new theory (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). The approach attempts to search and explicate causal link between variables; as such, researchers should be independent of issues under investigation. In so doing, existing concepts are normally operationalized to allow researchers measure them quantitatively. The results are then generalized to determine the extent to which they apply or do not apply to target population.

4.2.2.2 Inductive approach

In contrast to the above, this approach focuses its attention on building theory based on data obtained from target population. The process starts by collecting data or observing an area of interest before using inductive reasoning to derive a theory out of the data or what a researcher observes. The theory developed out of this process attempts to make sense of the data or what a researcher observes from it by determining the extent to which it fits or does not fit into a pattern.

To a large extent, it would be important to note that while the current study combines qualitative research methods with quantitative ones; hence, might be regarded as both deductive and inductive, the fact remains that the qualitative method is not aimed at building theory. Instead, it attempts to identify some of the measures that have been put in place in KSA to minimize the effects of a probable financial crisis in the future. In addition, it would be important to note that existing theories about the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis are being tested in KSA, which is an area of interest. Furthermore, the existing concepts have been operationalized and measured quantitatively to test the existing theories. More importantly, it would be worth noting that a theory is not developed from both qualitative and quantitative data obtained from the study to determine the way it fits or does not fit into the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis. Accordingly, a deductive research approach was utilized to conduct the current study with a view to deducing the impact of the crisis and various measures that had been developed to mitigate possible effects in the future.

4.2.3 Research strategy

The research onion identifies seven research strategies, which relate to the way studies are conducted. The first of these strategies is the experiment, which seeks to determine the causal link between variables by manipulating independent variables. A simple experiment involves determining the link between variables whereas a more complex experiment involves determining the size of change on the variables. In view of this, experiments are normally utilized in explanatory and exploratory researches to answer research questions related to 'why' and 'how' (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). More

importantly, experiments tend to have two separate groups namely; experimental and control groups. Research participants are then allocated to the two groups randomly and those in the experimental group subjected to some form of planned intervention/manipulation whereas those in the control group are not subjected to any form of intervention (Kumar, 2011). The dependent variables in both groups are then evaluated to determine any possible difference between them. The differences identified in them are attributed to manipulation done on the independent variables.

Even though the current study consisted of two separate groups namely IBs and CBs, no form of intervention/manipulation was applied on any of them. As a result, there were no experimental and control groups in the study even though the differences between the two types of banks were evaluated to determine the way they impacted or did not impact the performance of both types of banks. More importantly, the study did not evaluate the causal link between the independent and dependent variables. Instead, it sought to evaluate whether the differences between the two types of banks had any influence on the way both Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the crisis as a way of evaluating the impact of the crisis on them. In this respect, the experimental research strategy was inappropriate for the current study; hence, it was not utilized to conduct it.

The second strategy in the research onion is the case study, which Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) define as empirical examination of a contemporary phenomenon in its real life context using various sources of evidence. The basic difference between an experimental strategy and a case study is that the boundaries of a case study are normally not clearly defined whereas those of an experimental strategy are normally defined clearly. Case studies are normally conducted to gain richer understanding of issues under evaluation; hence, like experiments they are also applied mainly to exploratory and explanatory researches (Kumar, 2011). The best thing about case study is that multiple data sources may be utilized to triangulate studies' findings. While the current study limited its scope to KSA, it did not confine the issue under investigation to a particular bank institution. As a result, the study was not a case study.

The third strategy identified in the research onion is the action research, which Biggam (2008) considers to be iterative in nature. Action research starts by diagnosing a problem that needs to be resolved, then goes ahead to plan what needs to be done before taking the right actions. Once the right actions are taken, the relevant data is collected and analyzed to determine whether a problem is solved or not. If the problem is not solved, the process is repeated until the problem is resolved. The unique aspect about this strategy is that researchers and different practitioners are involved in the process of resolving research problem. Another unique aspect about it is that it tends to be research in action as opposed to research about action (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). The current study is not largely research in action because researchers and different practitioners are not involved directly in resolving the research problem. In addition, the study is not iterative because even though a research problem is identified, logical process is not developed to resolve the problem. More importantly, the study is not interested in resolving the research problem; instead, it evaluates the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry and the different measures that followed the crisis. In view of this, action research was not utilized to conduct the current study.

The fourth strategy relate to grounded theory, which is largely helpful in predicting and explaining behaviors by way of developing theories rather than testing them. As a result, theoretical frameworks are never developed at the start of the study, but they are developed once the data is collected. The process of developing theoretical frameworks involves generating predictions from the data and keeping on referring to it constantly to develop more theoretical frameworks (Biggam, 2008). In spite of this, it would be imperative to note that grounded theory does not involve presenting raw data without referring to existing theories identified from existing literature. Instead, it involves generating such frameworks from existing ones through interpretative processes (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). While the current study attempts to identify the measures that have been incorporated into the Saudi banking industry to safeguard it from the time that the 2008/09 financial crisis ended, it does not attempt to build new theories. In addition, it is largely deductive rather than inductive; hence, grounded theory is not utilized to conduct it.

Ethnography, which is the fifth research strategy identified in the research onion, is largely qualitative in nature and it involves studying people and their respective cultures. In contrast to other research strategies, researchers observe cultures the way their people view them, and in some instances interacting with research participants in real-life environments. The best thing about this research strategy is that it enables researchers to account for complex behaviors among people by explaining the way they interact with each other at personal levels. In addition, it allows researchers to express certain issues beyond what other research methods do. This may be critical in determining follow-up researches and the type of questions to be asked to different people (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). More importantly, it enables researchers to understand the way certain behaviors occur in different cultures as opposed to simply noting their occurrences. In spite of this, the research strategy requires a lot of time to conduct especially when researchers are involved in real-life environment. In addition, researchers' biases may affect studies' findings particularly in data collection and interpretation. The current study does not evaluate the Saudi cultural phenomena. In addition, it is not purely qualitative in nature because it combines both qualitative and quantitative mechanisms to evaluate the way Saudi banking industry was impacted by the crisis. More importantly, the researcher does not interact with research participants in real-life environment as researchers do in ethnography research strategy. As a result, the research strategy is not utilized to evaluate the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry.

The archival research is the sixth research strategy identified in the research onion. In contrast to other strategies, it utilizes administrative documents and records as its main sources of data. While the term archival is largely linked to historical issues, it is also linked to recent historical documents and records (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). Apart from this, it would be importantly to acknowledge the fact that while archival research strategy may be classified among secondary data analysis, the data utilized to conduct it tends to be a product of daily activities of a source it is collected from. As a result, when it is conducted, it evaluates a reality for which the data was collected for contrary to secondary data analysis, which evaluates other issues that the data was not collected for. In view of this, the secondary data analysis process utilized to conduct the

current study did not relate in any way to archival research strategy because the data utilized to evaluate the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banks was not collected originally for that purpose. Instead, it was collected for other purposes other than the one it was utilized for in the current study; hence, archival research strategy was not utilized to conduct the current study.

The survey design is the seventh research strategy in the research onion, which is utilized to justify the method used to conduct the current study. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) define it as a flexible research strategy that utilizes questionnaires to evaluate a variety of topics. They claim that it is largely deductive in nature in the sense that it focuses much of its attention on testing theories as opposed to building theories. The authors also claim that because it is normally utilized to answer research questions relating to how many, how much, where, what and who then it is largely utilized in descriptive and exploratory researches.

Creswell and Creswell (2018) claim that survey research strategy provides quantitative accounts of opinions, attitudes and trends from populations by testing association among variables obtained from samples. In addition, they claim that the strategy helps researchers to answer descriptive questions, determine link between variables and questions about predictive links between variables. The current study does not describe the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry by having the respondents complete a survey. Instead, it utilizes secondary data obtained from Saudi banks' financial statements and in-depth interviews conducted on critical people from Saudi banking industry. More importantly, even if it tests the link between various variables, it does not base its findings on quantitative accounts of opinions obtained from research participants. As a result, a survey design was not utilized to conduct the current study.

The preceding part of the thesis has determined that the seven research strategies identified by the research onion could not be utilized to conduct the current study. Accordingly, this part of the thesis discusses the causal-comparative design that was utilized to conduct the study as a way of justifying why the design was utilized whereas the others were deemed as unfit to evaluate the issue under investigation. To begin

with, the current study is interested at evaluating the impact of the 2008/09 financial crisis on the Saudi banking industry by comparing and contrasting the way both Saudi IBs and CBs performed before, during and after the crisis using secondary data obtained from banks' financial statements and primary data collected from critical stakeholders in the industry. In the light of this, a causal-comparative design was utilized to conduct the current study. But what is a causal-comparative design, and why was it the best strategy for the current study?

Salkind (2010) defines it as a design that attempts to ascertain the link between dependent and independent variables when an event has already occurred. He claims that it is normally conducted to determine whether an independent variable has any effect on a dependent variable by comparing different groups. Since the design is non-experimental in nature, then the variables are never manipulated. While the design might be considered to be almost similar to correlational research design, it would be important to note that it compares the effects of independent variables on dependent ones by comparing results from two separate groups. In contrast, correlational research design evaluates the effect of independent variables on dependent ones on a single group.

The banks' performance measured in terms of profitability, credit worth and liquidity was the dependent variable whereas banks' type defined in two levels namely; Islamic and conventional were the independent variables. However, because it was not possible to manipulate both types of banks, which were the independent variables given that the financial crisis had already occurred; then a causal-comparative research design was utilized to conduct the study (Salkind, 2010). The design entailed finding the relationship between the two types of banks based on the way they performed during the 2008/09 financial crisis. In this respect, secondary data from their respective financial statements were obtained to determine the way they performed before, during and after the financial crisis. In addition, two groups of people from both types of banks were identified and interviewed to provide their views on the new changes that have been implemented within the industry from the time the crisis ended.

The design was preferred over others because the crisis had already occurred; as such, it was not possible to manipulate the independent variables to determine the way the crises impacted both types of banks. Similarly, it was preferred because it was not possible to conduct an experimental study to determine the way the crisis impacted or did not impact both types of banks. In view of this design, the process of conducting the study entailed starting by determining the study's focus and the exact research questions that needed to be evaluated and answered. Then determining both dependent and independent variables as well as identifying and matching appropriately the banks that were included in the study. The matching of the banks was intended to strengthen the study's internal validity (Salkind, 2010). A similar process was replicated in selecting the research participants who provided the primary data. The data collected was then analyzed to provide an overview of the way both Saudi IBs and CBs were impacted or not impacted by the crisis.

4.3 Research approaches applied in thesis

4.3.1 Target population

At the time of the study, 26 banks were licensed to operate in KSA. Thirteen of them were local banks whereas the others (13) were foreign banks licensed to operate in KSA. It would be worth noting that other five foreign banks were in the process of obtaining licenses or had already been licensed, but they had not started operating officially at the time of the study. One of them, the state bank of India, had stopped operating and even requested for cancelation of its license (SAMA, 2020). The best thing about these banks was that they were not in operation between 2006 and 2010, except the state bank of India, which had requested for cancellation of its license. In addition, they were not in operation at the time of the study; hence, together with the state bank of India they were excluded from the target population and study at large because they were not in operation between 2006 and 2010 and at the time of the study.

It would be worth noting that because the thirteen foreign banks were subsidiaries for their mother banks based in other countries, then they did not have financial reports of

their own that could be included in the analysis. As a result, they were excluded from the target population (Al-Maghzom, Hussainey & Aly, 2016). In this respect, out of 26 banks operating in KSA, only 13 local banks were included in the target population. Four of these banks were IBs whereas the other nine were CBs. The IBs included Al-Inma, Al-Bilad, Al-Jazira and Al-Rajhi bank whereas the CBs included SIB, Riyad bank, SBB, National Commercial Bank (NCB), Banque Saudi Fransi, Samba Financial Group (SAMBA), Arab National Bank, Alawwal bank, and Gulfe International Bank Saudi Arabia (GIB-SA) (SAMA, 2020).

In terms of background information, the Al-Rajhi bank, which was established in 1957, was the oldest Islamic bank in KSA followed by the Al-Jazira bank, which was established in 1975. The Al-Bilad, which was established in 2004, was the third oldest IB bank in KSA whereas the Al-Inma bank that was established in 2007 was the fourth oldest IB in KSA (Hassan et al., 2018). Even though the Saudi IBs are only four, it would be worth noting that they capture about 51.3 percent of the total assets in the Saudi banking industry. The Al-Rajhi bank is the largest followed by Al-Jazira bank whereas Al-Bilad bank is the smallest.

Based on the number of IBs in the target population, the researcher decided to include 3 Islamic and 3 CBs in the sample to balance the number of banks in each sample. Accordingly, 6 CBs were excluded from the analysis whereas one of the IBs was excluded from the analysis. Largely, the decision to include three banks from each bank category was informed by availability of annual reports online and from other relevant sources that the researcher was able to access. In addition, it was informed by the year each bank started operating in KSA. For instance, the decision to exclude Al-Inma bank from the analysis was informed by the fact that it started operating in KSA in 2007. As a result, the financial reports that were available for analysis from Al-Inma bank were for 2009 and 2017.

The best thing about the banks that were selected to take part in the study was that a level of matching that involved selecting banks with equal levels of assets and market shares was applied in selecting them. For instance, both Al Rajhi and Riyad banks were included in the analysis because they were considered major IBs and CBs respectively.

This was critical to the causal-comparative research design that was utilized to conduct the study.

The study covered the period between 2006 and 2017. The period between 2006 and 2010 was considered the time that the crisis lasted whereas that the one between 2011 and 2017 was considered to be after the crisis. Although the timeframe was relatively short in terms of the number of years included in the analysis, it was considered appropriate given the short time that the financial crisis lasted. In addition, it was considered appropriate because it covered the period during and after the crisis. The effects not captured between 2006 and 2017 from the quantitative data were captured by the qualitative data obtained from research participants to complement the secondary quantitative data that was collected from online sources.

4.3.2 Sampling

Different sampling methods could have been utilized to select the Saudi banks included in the study. As a result, as a way of justifying the sampling method that was utilized to select the banks and research participants who were included in the study, it would be important to identify a number of sampling methods and pinpoint the basis upon which they were excluded from the study. According to Kumar (2011), the simple random sampling selects research participants purely on chances; hence, every element in the target population has equal chances of selection into the sample. The advantage of giving elements in the target population equal chances of selection into the sample is that the study's findings are normally generalized to the target population. In spite of this, it would be worth noting that it is not always possible to select research participants on random basis because of prevailing conditions; hence, simple random sampling does not apply in all incidences (Levy & Lemeshow, 2013). In view of this, the sampling method was not utilized in the current study because of the diversity of Saudi banks included in the target population given that most of them offered both Islamic and conventional products and services. As a result, their financial reports could not be considered purely Islamic or conventional; hence, critical evaluation was applied in selecting the types of banks included in the study.

In order to overcome the heterogeneity challenge that limits the application of simple random sampling method in certain cases, the stratified sampling method organizes elements in target population in sequences. Then it proceeds to select the first element included into the sample on random basis either using random tables or other random methods (Levy & Lemeshow, 2013). Once the first element is selected, the others are selected on a fixed sampling interval until the last element to be included in the sample is selected. The stratified sampling method could not be applied to the current study because the banks were few and they were not organized in a sequence manner.

Both simple random sampling and stratified sampling methods depend on researchers' abilities to identify elements in target populations, but it is not always possible to identify all elements in target populations especially when populations are large. To overcome this challenge, the cluster sampling method divides target populations into small groups with relatively similar characteristics from which sample elements are then selected from them on random basis (Kumar, 2011). While this sampling method was good, the target population consisted of only twenty-six banks that operated in KSA; as such, the population was not large to warrant for the use of cluster sampling method. This was in spite of the fact that the banks were grouped into two separate categories namely; Islamic and conventional. While one might be tempted to consider the two groups as clusters, it would be important to note that the sampling method did not amount to cluster sampling method. Accordingly, it would be wrong to presume that cluster sampling method was utilized to select the banks included in the study.

The accidental sampling entails selecting research participants based on ease and convenience of accessing them without considering their unique characteristics. The selection process stops once the desired number of research participants is attained. While the sampling method is good, it normally includes sample elements with undesired characteristics because its selection process does not consider desired characteristics (Kumar, 2011). In view of this, the sampling method was not utilized to select the research participants and banks that were included in the study.

The purposive sampling method overcomes the above challenge by giving researchers freedom to select people they think might provide them with useful information way

before they collect data. Once this is determined, then the selection process is conducted among those people or elements. The sampling method is relatively useful in historical realities and qualitative studies (Kumar, 2011). While the current study is historical in nature, it is not qualitative in nature. In addition, while the researcher had a greater responsibility in determining the people and banks to include in the study, he did not base his decision solely on that responsibility. Instead, other determining factors such as the manner in which banks offered services were considered in selecting research participants and banks included in the analysis; hence, the sampling method was not utilized in the current study.

In contrast to the purposive sampling method that gives researchers freedom to select research participants based on their ability to provide relevant information/data, the expert sampling method includes only experts in its data collection process. As a result, everybody who is not considered an expert in an area of interest is excluded from the study (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Largely, the people who were included in the current study were experts in their various banks because they understood several aspects about those banks. Nevertheless, the banks included in the study may not be regarded as experts in their areas of specialization. Accordingly, even though people with vast experiences in banking were included in the study, the expert sampling method was not utilized to conduct the current study because the study was not entirely qualitative in nature.

The snowball sampling method selects research participants using networks, which start with few individuals in groups or organizations who are then asked to recruit others from groups or organizations once data is collected from them. The recruitment and data collection process continues until the desired number of respondents is attained. The sampling method is useful when little is known about groups and organizations, but the fact that research participants recruit one another then findings tend to be biased (Kumar, 2011). The current study did not ask research participants to recruit one another; hence, the sampling method was not utilized to conduct it.

In contrast to the above, the quota sampling method selects sample elements based on their visible characteristics and ease of accessing the sample population. In line with

this, the selection process is conducted based on convenience of location to the people collecting the data and it starts by specifying the elements' visible characteristics that should be included in the sample. Then it proceeds to select sample elements based on those characteristics. Accordingly, whenever an element with visible characteristics is identified from the target population, it is selected to be part of the sample. The process is repeated until the desired sample size is attained. The best thing about this sampling method is that it ensures that the elements with desired characteristics are included in the sample (Kumar, 2011). Nevertheless, the fact that sample elements are selected on non-random basis, then it might not be possible to generalize the study's findings.

Despite the above shortcoming, the quota sampling method was applied in the current study because of the services and products that Saudi banks offered. In general, most of the Saudi banks especially the foreign ones offered both conventional and Islamic banking services even though they separated them from each other. In addition, it was slightly impossible to obtain the financial statements for each of the banks for the period between 2006 and 2017 over the internet. As a result, it proved practically impossible to select the banks that were included in the study on a random basis (Levy & Lemeshow, 2013). Because of this challenge, the quota sampling method was utilized to select the banks that were included in the study. The sampling method entailed evaluating the type of banking services and products that Saudi banks offered, determining whether they were either conventional or Islamic in nature and making the final decision based on the services and products they offered. The banks that offered both types of banking services were excluded from the study whereas those that were either Islamic or conventional were included in the study. The process was repeated until a sample of three IBs and three CBs was attained.

4.3.3 Research choice

Before justifying the research choice adopted in the current study, it would be important to differentiate quantitative research from qualitative research. On one hand, quantitative researches are concerned about measurements and quantities of items of interest in a study whereas the qualitative ones, on the other hand, are concerned about making senses of things in their natural settings. Because the two researches approach

issues of interest from two different perspectives, they are normally combined to provide better explanations of issues of interest (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). This partly explains the reasoning behind the pragmatic research philosophy adopted to conduct the current study. Nevertheless, it would be worth noting that both researches collect data differently; hence, it would be worth looking at the different choices provided on research onion.

The mono method applies when a single method is utilized to collect data whereas multiple methods apply when many methods are utilized to collect data. Under the multiple methods, it is possible to use mixed methods or multi-methods. Mixed methods apply when qualitative and quantitative methods of collecting data are combined whereas multi-methods apply when different quantitative methods of collecting data or qualitative ones are combined in data collection processes. The distinction is that under multi-method, the focus is normally on either qualitative methods of collecting data or quantitative ones whereas in mixed method both types of methods are combined in the processes of collecting data (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). In view of this, a semi-structured interview was utilized to collect the qualitative data whereas online sources were utilized to provide the secondary data that formed part of the quantitative data. From this perspective, then mixed method was utilized to collect and even analyze the data sequentially.

4.3.4 Time horizons

Upon providing and justifying the research choice utilized in the current study, it would be imperative also to justify the nature of the study based on time horizons, which relate to the manner the data was collected. As far as this issue is concerned, it is possible for a study be cross-sectional in nature meaning that data would be collected at a single point in time. Alternatively, it is possible for a study to be longitudinal in nature meaning that research participants would be followed for a particular time and data collected from them over that period. The advantage of collecting data from research participants over time is that it provides an overview of issue of concern over time; hence, depicts the way it changes over time (Kumar, 2011). Nevertheless, research participants might

respond to research questions in one particular manner; thus, limit the chances of determining the way issues of concern change over time.

The current study evaluated the manner in which the Saudi banks were impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis between 2006 and 2017. As a result, secondary data covering this period was collected to determine the effects of the crisis on the banks. In addition, qualitative data collected from research participants at a single point was utilized to complement its findings. While the data collected from research participants was obtained once meaning that the respondents were not followed to provide additional data, the study focused much of its attention on changes that occurred within Saudi banking industry from the time that the crisis ended to the time the study was conducted. In the light of this, the study was relatively longitudinal because it evaluated the effects of the crisis over time.

4.3.5 Data collection

This part of the thesis provides an overview of the process that was followed in collecting the data. It starts by providing the process that was followed to collect the primary data before presenting the one that was utilized to collect the secondary one.

4.3.5.1 Primary data

The introductory letter attached at the appendix was utilized to introduce the study to IBs and CBs that were included in the study. The letter was intended to obtain permission from those banks to collect data from them; hence, it was presented to relevant banks' authorities before the data collection process started. Upon obtaining permission to collect data from those banks, the researcher identified the people to be included in the study and went ahead to interview them. It would be worth noting that because the study sought expert opinions about the issue under consideration, then not everybody working in the banks was interviewed. Instead, the interview was narrowed to forty of these people who were deemed to possess the information that the researcher was looking for.

The semi-structured interviews were utilized to interview the people who were selected purposively to take part in the study. The process entailed starting by introducing the study to them by informing them about it and its possible benefits to them, establishing rapport with them and interviewing them. Because the process was largely semi-structured, then the research questions included in the interview guide were not asked in a structured manner. Instead, they were asked based on the rapport that the researcher developed with research participants from the start of the study. Even though the process was a bit hectic, it offered the researcher the opportunity to probe for deeper responses where necessary. In addition, it offered him the chance to clarify them where necessary to ensure that the data collect was specific and accurate (Smith & Osborn, 2007). This enriched the study's findings by making sure that the data that was collected was both informative and specific to research problem.

4.3.5.2 Secondary data

The secondary data was collected from online sources. This involved looking for official websites for the IBs and CBs that were selected to take part in the study and searching for their financial statements from their respective websites. The financial statements were then scrutinized further to ensure that they had the relevant data and that they were the official ones. This involved determining the exact data that needed to be collected from each financial statement, collecting that data and transferring it to an Excel program that was utilized to calculate the relevant financial ratios. The data collected from both process was assembled ready for analysis, which was conducted separately even though the findings were combined to complement each other.

4.3.6 Instrument

The interview schedule attached at the appendix was utilized to collect primary data from research participants. The interview schedule consisted of seven open-ended research questions that were intended to collect data relating to the way the Saudi banks were impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis including the new developments within the banking industry that resulted from the crisis. In line with this purpose, the research questions addressed themselves to the measures implemented

so far within the Saudi banking sector to protect it from possible effects of a probable financial crisis in the future.

4.3.7 Pilot testing

According to Kumar (2011), pilot testing is an important element of research. It does not only help researchers to test the viability of their research instruments by clarifying unclear questions, but it also help them to coordinate their research processes effectively. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009), pilot testing helps researchers to modify research processes and plan research processes effectively. In line with this, prior to the actual data collection process, the interview schedule used to collect qualitative data from research participants was piloted to ensure that it collected valid data. The pilot testing process involved selecting 10 people (5 working in IBs and 5 in CBs), reading the questions from the interview schedule to them and asking them to pinpoint what they thought the questions asked them to do. The different points obtained from the respondents were noted and used to improve the unclear questions including making the questions more focused. The pilot testing was conducted in two separate Saudi banks (one Islamic and the other one conventional) that were not included in the final data collection process.

4.3.8 Data analysis

4.3.8.1 Qualitative data analysis

A thematic analysis procedure was utilized to analyze the qualitative data. The procedure entailed starting by reading through the data as a way familiarizing with it before summarizing it. This involved reading the responses that the respondents provided repeatedly to understand and probably get some patterns from them. After reading it several times, the initial codes were generated by way of coding the ones that related directly to research questions and leaving out the irrelevant ones. The next step then proceeded to searching for themes from the initial codes by way of collating them, which involved sorting codes into potential themes by way of combining them where necessary (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Visual representations in form of tables and maps

were utilized to collate various codes. This produced long lists that were too broad to be included into the final report. As a result, the themes were reviewed further to refine them by way of determining the themes with supporting data and those without supporting data. The themes with supporting data were retained whereas those without supporting data were dropped at this stage. Similarly, the closely related ones were merged whereas the separate ones were separated or even broken further based on supporting data.

Two methods were utilized to refine and review the main themes; the first method entailed reading and collating themes' extracts, and then determining whether they formed coherent patterns or not. The ones that did not form coherent patterns were evaluated further to determine whether they were problematic or not. The problematic ones were re-worked or even converted into new themes that were supported by the data. Upon conviction that resultant themes captured contours of coded data, the second method, which involved looking at the data wholesomely and evaluating the validity of individual themes, was applied to analyze the data. The last process entailed defining and naming themes by way of identifying the essence of each theme and the aspects they captured (Braun & Clarke, 2006). As a result, a detailed analysis of each theme was conducted in the light of research problem. The data was then presented in a narrative form that provided emerging issues from the responses that research participants provided.

4.3.8.2 Quantitative data analysis

To provide an overview of the way the data analysis was conducted, this part of the analysis highlights the research questions together with presumptions made and the way each of them was answered. It starts by highlighting what each of the research question sought to achieve before outlining the data analysis method used to answer each one of them. Doing this, justifies the method utilized in each case.

In this respect, the first research question sought to evaluate the unique bank characteristics that exposed the Saudi banking industry to the crisis. Given that the crisis emanated from conventional banking practices, the thesis presumed that the

Saudi CBs were impacted by the crisis whereas the Islamic ones were not impacted by it. To evaluate the correctness or incorrectness of this presumption, line graphs were utilized to plot the banks' ROE and ROA for the period between 2006 and 2017. A decline in the ROE and ROA during the study period was identified as signaling the effect of the crisis on banks' performances whereas an upward trend was taken to imply otherwise.

The second research question sought to evaluate the way both types of banks performed during and after the crisis. Once again, the line graphs were utilized to depict the way different banks performed during and after the crisis. The third research question, on the other hand, evaluated the insolvency risk for the Saudi banking industry during the crisis. It was presumed that CBs were at higher insolvency risk than the Islamic ones. To evaluate this presumption, the Altman Z-score model, which was developed by Edward Altman in 1968, was utilized to evaluate the solvency risk of each type of bank during the crisis. Since its development, the model has been utilized in different studies and demonstrated to be efficient at predicting the likelihood of institutions going bankrupt with high level of accuracy (Erfani & Vasigh, 2018). In this respect, it was utilized to determine the extent to which both types of banks were at the risk of filing for bankruptcy during the crisis for failure to meet financial obligations. The following 5-factor model was utilized to compare and contrast the impact of the crisis on both types of banks.

$$\text{Z-Score} = 1.2A + 1.4B + 3.3C + 0.6D + 1.0E$$

Where:

A = working capital / total assets

B = retained earnings / total assets

C = earnings before interest and tax / total assets

D = market value of equity / total liabilities

E = sales / total assets

The variables were also calculated from banks' financial reports and plotting them using bar charts. The process entailed calculating the five variables for each bank and calculating their weighted means individually. The independent sample t test was also utilized to determine whether the differences were statistically different from each other.

The fourth research question sought to evaluate the forces emanating from the crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry. To answer this research question, a qualitative data analysis method was utilized to analyze the qualitative data obtained from 40 key stakeholders in the industry. The results are provided in the next chapter. The tenth research question was a general question; hence, it was answered from study's findings.

The Excel program was utilized to analyze the quantitative secondary data obtained from banks' financial reports. The financial ratios were then converted into line graphs to depict the way banks performed between 2006 and 2017. The banks' ROE, which were calculated from banks' financial statements were utilized to measure the banks' levels of efficiency during and after the crisis. The liquidity ratios were utilized to measure the extent to which banks' were able to liquidate their current assets to offset their current liabilities whereas the profitability ratios were utilized to measure the performance of the banks. The banks with higher profitability ratios were considered to perform better than their counterparts with lower profitability ratios.

4.3.9 Validity

Kumar (2011) claims that the data and instrument utilized in research studies ought to be both valid and reliable. The validity ensures that the instrument measures what it is supposed to measure (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). In line with this, three levels of validity namely construct, face and content validities were evaluated to ensure that the instrument measured what it was supposed to measure. The content validity evaluated individual research questions to ensure that they were both specific and clear. Accordingly, the unclear ones were clarified whereas the unspecific ones were revised to ensure that they address specific issues of concern. The construct validity on its part evaluated the research questions to ensure that they included relevant concepts

and ideas that were critical in determining the way Saudi banking practices had changed over time since the 2008/09 financial crisis occurred in different parts of the world. The face value validity evaluated the manner in which research questions were organized and ordered to ensure that they appeared in the right manner.

4.3.10 Reliability

The instrument was also evaluated to ensure that it provided consistent findings with a view to making sure that it would yield similar results if the study would be conducted a second or even a third time. This entailed conducting a pilot study before the actual one was conducted, collecting data from same research participants twice and evaluating the extent to which their responses differed from the first ones (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The underlying constructs were evaluated to make sure that they did not mislead research participants to providing inconsistent responses. By so doing, threats to reliability were minimized by making sure that participants' biases did not influence the way they responded to research questions (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). Accordingly, it was evident that if the interview guide would be utilized to collect data a second or even a third time, then it would provide consistent findings.

4.3.11 Ethical consideration

Finally, because the study collected data from human beings who could be harmed in one way or the other if the study was conducted inappropriately, then this part of the thesis provides an overview of the measures that the researcher put in place to protect research participants from possible harms. Similarly, it highlights some of the measures that the researcher put in place during data collection and analysis processes to ensure that the secondary data was not manipulated in any way to align to researcher's expectations.

To begin with, it would be worth noting that a consent form attached at the appendix was prepared and provided to research participants before they took part in the study. The form informed research participants about possible risks and benefits of taking part in the study. It informed them that necessary measures had been put in place to mitigate possible harms and that they were free to withdraw from the study at any time

without giving reasons or prior notice. In so doing, it assured them that their participation in the study was voluntary, and that it would not cost them anything taking part in the study. Additionally, it informed them that the responses they provided would not be used in other studies other than the one it was collected for. Furthermore, it informed them that there would be no direct benefit for taking part in the study, but they would be required to spare some of their time to answer research questions (Kumar, 2011). As a way of confirming that, they read and understood the process that was utilized to collect the data; the last part of the form asked them to sign the consent form. Among other things, the signature indicated that they took part in the study on voluntary basis.

As a way of minimizing the risk of inappropriate disclosure, the participants were not asked to provide their names, contact details or anything else that could be used to identify them because their participation was anonymous. They were assured that the data they provided would not be shared with unauthorized people including their employers. Additionally, the data they provided was stored in padlocked cabinets to ensure that it was not accessed by unauthorized persons. Similarly, a laptop secured with strong password was used to enter the data into the computer program used to analyze it. More importantly, nothing that the research participants provided during the data collection that could identify them was provided in the findings. In this case, the names of the banks the participants worked for were not included in the findings. Instead, general terms such as the types of banks (Islamic or conventional) and where necessarily the positions that some of them held were included in the findings. Doing so minimized the risk of disclosing the identities of the participants.

Alongside the above, the researcher collected the secondary data that was utilized in the study from official sources or credible sources with official seals. In addition, the financial ratios that were utilized to determine the way various banks were affected by the financial crisis were calculated from the data collected from those sources. More importantly, the data was not altered in any way to reflect researcher's expectations meaning that it was reported the way it was even when it went against what the researcher expected to get from it (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). By so doing, the data

reflected the way various banks in KSA were affected or not affected by the financial crisis.

4.3.12 Chapter's summary

The chapter has provided the methodology used to conduct the thesis. Special attention has been directed towards the research philosophy, research approach and research strategy used to conduct the thesis. In line with thesis' focus, the pragmatism research philosophy was identified as the best research philosophy for achieving the thesis' research objectives. The mixed method, on the other hand, was identified as the most suitable research method for answering research questions adequately. Accordingly, both quantitative and qualitative research approaches were used to conduct the thesis. On one hand, both inferential and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the quantitative data whereas thematic data analysis method, on the other hand, was used to analyze the qualitative data. The next chapter provides the study's findings; it starts by providing the findings from secondary data before presenting findings from qualitative data that was collected from 40 key research participants from Saudi banking industry.

CHAPTER 5: FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Chapter's Overview

This chapter presents the thesis' findings based on its research questions. It starts by providing the descriptive statistics for both types of banks, which summarizes the means and standard variables for the variables included in the study before providing the inferential statistics. It concludes by providing the qualitative findings from the 40 research participants included in the analysis to depict the extent to which the Saudi bank industry was impacted or not impacted by the crisis.

5.2 Descriptive statistics

Six (6) Saudi banks (3 conventional and 3 Islamic) were included in the analysis. The three IBs included Al-Bilad bank, Al-Jazira bank and Al-Rajhi bank whereas the CBs included SIB, Riyadh bank and SBB. The Al-Rajhi bank and Riyadh bank, which were both established in 1957, were the oldest banks in the sample. In terms of total assets, the Al-Rajhi bank with a total asset of \$104.056 billion was the largest bank among the six banks included in the analysis followed by the Riyadh bank with a total asset of \$74.264 billion. The Saudi British bank with a total asset of \$70.422 billion was third among the six banks whereas the Saudi Investment Bank with a total asset of \$26.765 billion ranked fourth. The Al-Jazira bank with a total asset of \$24 billion ranked fifth whereas the Al-Bilad bank ranked six.

The crisis period was considered to be between 2006 and 2010 whereas the period after the crisis was considered to be between 2011 and 2017. Table 5.1 provides a summary of the descriptive statistics for both types of banks during and after the crisis. The minimum weighted average ROA for CBs that were included in the analysis during the crisis was 1.32 percent whereas the maximum value for that period was 3.98 percent. Their respective mean ROA for that period was 2.13 percent with a standard deviation of 1.10 percent. In contrast, the minimum weighted average ROA for IBs that were included in the analysis during the crisis was 0.88 percent whereas the maximum

value for that period was 7.03 percent. Their respective mean ROA for that period was 2.85 percent with a standard deviation of 2.48 percent suggesting that they varied more than the ROA for CBs.

The minimum ROE for IBs during the crisis was 5.29 percent whereas the maximum ROE for that period was 29.71 percent. Their mean ROE for that period was 14 percent with a standard deviation of 9.53 percent. In contrast, the minimum ROE for CBs was 9.12 percent whereas the maximum value for that period was 30 percent (Table 5.1). Their respective mean ROE for that period was 16.92 percent with a standard deviation of 8.39 percent.

Table 5.1: The variables' descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
ROA (IBs during crisis)	5	2.85	2.476	1.676	.913	2.801	2.000
ROA (CBs during crisis)	5	2.13	1.100	1.666	.913	2.576	2.000
ROE (IBs during crisis)	5	14.00	9.530	1.461	.913	2.244	2.000
ROE (CBs during crisis)	5	16.92	8.390	1.115	.913	.639	2.000
ROA (IBs After Crisis)	7	1.88	.232	1.717	.794	3.418	1.587
ROA (CBs After Crisis)	7	1.80	.116	-.942	.794	1.308	1.587
ROE (IBs After Crisis)	7	14.16	1.833	1.226	.794	1.065	1.587

ROE (CBs After Crisis)	7	12.03	1.415	-.504	.794	-.740	1.587
Valid N (list wise)	5						

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

In contrast to the above, the minimum weighted average ROA for CBs after the crisis was 1.59 percent whereas the maximum value for that period was 1.95 percent. Their respective mean ROA for that period was 1.80 percent with a standard deviation of 0.116 percent. In contrast, the minimum weighted average ROA for IBs after the crisis was 1.66 percent whereas the maximum value for that period was 2.36 percent. Their respective mean ROA for that period was 1.88 percent with a standard deviation of 0.232 percent. The minimum ROE for IBs after the crisis was 12.57 percent whereas the maximum ROE for that period was 17.61 percent (Table 5.1). Their mean ROE for that period was 14.16 percent with a standard deviation of 1.833 percent. In contrast, the minimum ROE for CBs after the crisis was 9.80 percent whereas the maximum value for that period was 13.58 percent. Their respective mean ROE for that period was 12.03 percent with a standard deviation of 1.415 percent.

5.3 The banks' unique characteristics that exposed or did not expose Saudi banks to the crisis

The first research question sought to critically evaluate the unique characteristics of the Saudi IBs and CBs to determine whether they exposed the Saudi banking industry to the crisis or not. It presumed that because most of the conventional banking practices were responsible for the crisis in USA and other parts of the world, then they were responsible for the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry. The results showed that both types of banks were significantly different from each other because while the Saudi CBs charged interests on loans, the Saudi IBs did not charge interests on loans. In addition, the results showed that while CBs entered into business relationships with customers on the basis of lender-borrower relationship, the Islamic ones entered into partnerships with their customers. In so doing, the CBs did not expect to make losses because they expected to get their money back and interests at the end of investment

period. In contrast, the IBs appreciated the fact that it was possible for customers to make losses in their businesses; hence, they shared profits and losses with them as opposed to charging them interests on bank loans. Furthermore, the study established that the Saudi IBs did not engage in speculative banking practices that did not provide real assets whereas the CBs engaged in such practices. In view of this, it was evident that the Saudi Islamic banking practices were significantly different from the conventional ones. In spite of this, the study did not identify Saudi conventional banking practices as responsible for the effects of the crisis on the Saudi banking industry.

5.4 The performance of Saudi IBs versus Saudi CBs

The study presumed that the unique characteristics of the Saudi IBs protected Saudi IBs from the crisis whereas the characteristics of the Saudi CBs exposed Saudi CBs to the crisis and its subsequent effects. To evaluate the validity of this presumption, the second research question sought to determine the way Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the crisis. However, because it would not be possible to evaluate the validity of this hypothesis without developing a null hypothesis that would presume that the performance of the two banks would not be statistically different from each other, then the thesis hypothesized further that both types of banks were not impacted by the crisis in any way. By presuming so, the thesis implied that the performance of both types of banks was consistent between 2006 and 2017 and that it was not statistically significant from each other.

5.4.1 Performance during the crisis

5.4.1.1 Impact of the crisis on the performance of Saudi IBs

In contrast to the above hypotheses, the study established that the profitability of IBs as measured in terms of ROA and ROE was inconsistent between 2006 and 2010 as Figure 5.1 depicts.

Figure 5.1: The impact of the crisis on IBs' ROA between 2006 and 2010

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

As Figure 5.1 depicts, the ROA for Al-Jazira bank was the most inconsistent one because it dropped from a high of 12.56 percent to a low of 0.09 percent between 2006 and 2010. Accordingly, the Al-Jazira bank was impacted more than the other two IBs by the crisis. The impact of the crisis on the other two IBs was relatively less because their ROAs did not change significantly, as it did for the Al-Jazira bank.

A similar trend was also evident from the bank's ROE as Figure 6.2 depicts. Indeed, like in the above case, the ROE for Al-Jazira bank was the most affected one because it dropped from a high of 47.07 percent to a low of 0.59 percent between 2006 and 2010. While the same might be said about Al-Bilad bank, it would be worth noting that Al-Bilad bank was not impacted significantly like the Al-Jazira was impacted by it because even if Al-Bilad bank's ROE was negative in 2009, it remained relatively low as it was before the crisis occurred. In contrast, the Al-Rajhi bank was not impacted significantly by the crisis like the other two banks were impacted by it because even if the ROE dropped from a high of 36.18 percent to a low of 22.33 percent, the impact was not that much as Figure 5.2 depicts.

Figure 5.2: The impact of the crisis on IB's ROE between 2006 and 2010

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

5.4.1.2 Impact of the crisis on the performance of Saudi CBs

A similar trend of inconsistency was also evident among the three Saudi CBs that were included in the analysis as Figure 5.3 depicts. As the trend shows, it would be worth noting that SIB was impacted more by the crisis than the other two CBs that took part in the study. This is in relation to the fact that its ROA dropped from a high of 4.91 percent to a low of 0.83 percent between 2006 and 2010 as Figure 5.3 depicts. While the same might be said about the other two CBs, it would be worth noting that their impacts were not as notable as SIB's.

Figure 5.3: The impact of the crisis on CBs' ROA between 2006 and 2010
 (Source: Developed by thesis' author)

A similar trend was also evident from their ROE with SIB still experiencing the largest part of the effect because its ROE dropped from a high of 33.43 percent to a low of 5.27 percent between 2006 and 2010 as Figure 5.4 depicts. The SBB was least impacted by the crisis because its ROE did not change significantly as it changed for the other two banks.

Figure 5.4: The impact of the crisis on CBs' ROE between 2006 and 2010

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

5.4.2 Banks' performance after the crisis

Alongside the above, the third research question sought to determine the way both types of banks performed after the crisis. Since the crisis had already ended despite the persistence of its consequences on various sectors of the world and Saudi economy, the thesis presumed that both types of banks performed relatively the same meaning that their performances were relatively consistent.

5.4.2.1 Saudi IBs' performance after the crisis

In contrast to the above presumption, the study established that the performance for Saudi IBs was not consistent between 2011 and 2017, which was the period after the crisis. Figure 5.5 depicts the way Saudi IBs performed between 2011 and 2017.

Figure 5.5: The IBs' ROA for between 2011 and 2017

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

As Figure 5.5 depicts, the performance of the Saudi IBs that were included in the analysis rose and fell between 2011 and 2017 suggesting that it was not consistent. A similar trend was also evident from the banks' ROE as Figure 5.6 depicts.

Figure 5.6: The IBs' ROE for between 2011 and 2017

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

Figure 5.6 shows that from the time that the crisis ended up to 2017; the performance of Saudi IBs' in terms of ROE rose and fell among the three IBs included in the study.

5.4.2.2 Saudi CBs' performance after the crisis

A similar trend though relatively stable was also evident among the Saudi CBs that were included in the analysis. In terms of ROA, the trend was relatively stable even though it dropped slightly in 2016 as Figure 5.7 depicts.

Figure 5.7: The CBs' ROA for between 2011 and 2017

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

A similar trend was also evident among the banks' ROE as Figure 5.8 depicts. However, the decline in the trend was relatively higher than the one witnessed in the banks' ROA suggesting that the banks' ROE had declined more than ROA had declined.

Figure 5.8: The CBs' ROE for between 2011 and 2017

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

5.5 Inferential statistics

5.5.1 The impact of the crisis on Saudi IBs and CBs

To determine the manner in which both types of banks were impacted by the crisis, the thesis evaluated whether both types of banks were impacted by the crisis the same way or differently. It presumed that banks' characteristics exposed Saudi CBs to financial crisis whereas they protected Saudi IBs from the crisis. To determine the validity of this presumption, a t test (two-sided) with a p-value of 0.05 was conducted to assess whether there was a statistically significant difference in the performance of both types of banks during the crisis. The banks' type with two levels: IBs and CBs was the independent variable whereas banks' performance was the dependent variable. The study's null hypothesis presumed that there was no statistically significant difference between the performances of both types of banks during the crisis. By presuming so, it expected that banks' performances in terms of ROA would not be statistically different from each other.

The results indicated that the mean ROA ($M = 2.85$, $SD = 2.48$) for IBs were not statistically different from the mean ROA ($M = 2.13$, $SD = 1.10$) for CBs during the crisis. This was in relation to the fact that the study's p-value (0.575) for a two-tailed t test was greater than 0.05, which was the study's significance level. Accordingly, the null hypothesis presuming that the difference between their ROA was not statistically different from each other was not rejected. Table 5.2 summarizes the results.

Table 5.2: t test's summary for banks' ROA during the crisis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>CB's ROA</i>	<i>IB's ROA</i>
Mean	2.13	2.85
Variance	0.0121	0.0613
Observations	5	5
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	-0.592	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.288	
t Critical one-tail	1.943	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.575	
t Critical two-tail	2.447	

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

Similarly, a t test presuming unequal variance between the two types of banks was conducted on banks ROE to determine whether they were statistically different from each other. Like in the above case, the study presumed that the ROE for both types of banks for the period between 2006 and 2010 were not statistically different from each other.

The results indicated that the mean ROE ($M = 14.00$, $SD = 9.53$) for IBs were not statistically different from the mean ROE ($M = 16.92$, $SD = 8.39$) for CBs during the crisis. This was in relation to the fact that the study's p-value (0.621) for a two-tailed t

test was greater than 0.05, which was the study's significance level. Accordingly, like in the above case, the null hypothesis presuming that the difference between them was not statistically different from each other was not rejected. Table 5.3 summarizes the results.

Table 5.3: t test's summary for banks' ROE during the crisis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	14.00	16.92
Variance	0.90847	0.7044
Observations	5	5
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	8	
t Stat	-0.514	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.311	
t Critical one-tail	1.860	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.621	
t Critical two-tail	2.306	

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

Based on the above findings, the study concluded that the effect of the crisis on the two types of banks was not statistically different from each other in terms of banks' ROA and ROE. The implication was that the two types of banks performed relatively the same throughout the crisis. Because the trend analysis showed that the performances for the two types of banks declined between 2006 and 2010, then the main take away from this finding was that the performances for both types of banks were impacted in the same way suggesting that the Islamic banking practices did not protect Saudi banks from the effects of the crisis.

5.5.2 Effects after the crisis

To determine whether the performances of both types of banks has been statistically different from each other from the time that the crisis ended, a t test presuming unequal variances was also conducted for the period between 2011 and 2017. The test's null hypothesis presumed that the mean differences between the banks' ROA was not statistically different from each other whereas the alternative hypothesis presumed that the mean difference between then was statistically different from each other.

The results indicated that the mean ROA ($M = 1.88$, $SD = 0.232$) for IBs was not been statistically different from the mean ROA ($M = 1.80$, $SD = 0.116$) for CBs from the time that the crisis ended. This was in relation to the fact that the study's p-value (0.42) for a two-tailed test was greater than 0.05, which was the study's significance level; hence, the null hypothesis presuming that the difference between the banks' ROA was not statistically different from each other was not rejected. Table 5.4 summarizes the banks' performance as measured in terms of ROA for the period between 2011 and 2017.

Table 5.4: t test's output for banks' ROA between 2011 and 2017

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Weighted averages (CBs)</i>	<i>Weighted averages (IBs)</i>
Mean	1.80%	1.88%
Variance	1.3489E-06	5.43E-06
Observations	7	7
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	9	
t Stat	-0.842	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.211	
t Critical one-tail	1.833	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.422	
t Critical two-tail	2.262	

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

A further analysis was conducted using banks' ROE to determine whether banks' performance in terms of ROE was statistically different from each other or not from the time that the crisis ended. Like in the above case, a t test presuming unequal variances was conducted to determine whether both types of banks had performed differently from the time that the crisis ended or not. The test's null hypothesis presumed that the banks' mean ROE were not statistically different from each other whereas the alternative hypothesis presumed that the mean difference between them was statistically different from each other.

The results indicated that the mean ROE ($M = 14.16$, $SD = 1.833$) for IBs was statistically different from the mean ROE ($M = 12.03$, $SD = 1.415$) for CBs between 2011 and 2017. This was in relation to the fact that the study's p-value (0.03) for a two-tailed test was less than 0.05, which was the study's significance level. Accordingly, the test's null hypothesis presuming that the mean differences were not statistically different from each other was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis that presumed that the mean differences were statistically different from each other. Since the IBs' ROE (14.16%) was relatively higher than the CBs' ROE (12.02%), then the Saudi IBs' were identified as performing relatively better than the Saudi CBs from the time that the crisis ended. Table 5.5 summarizes the banks' performance as measured in terms of ROE from the time that the crisis ended.

Table 5.5: t test's output for banks' ROE after the crisis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Weighted averages (CBs)</i>	<i>Weighted averages (IBs)</i>
Mean	12.02%	14.16%
Variance	0.0002	0.000335
Observations	7	7
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	11	
t Stat	-2.444	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.016	

t Critical one-tail	1.796
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.033
t Critical two-tail	2.201

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

5.6 Effect on banks' efficiency

Alongside the above, the t test analysis was also utilized to evaluate the banks' levels of efficiency using ROE. To determine whether the level of efficiency between both types of banks was statistically different from each other or not, the null hypothesis presumed that the level of efficiency between both types of banks was not statistically different from each other during and after the crisis. In contrast, the alternative hypothesis presumed that the difference between their levels of efficiency was statistically different from each other during and after the crisis.

5.6.1 Effects of the crisis on banks' efficiency

The analysis established that the level of efficiency between both types of banks was not statistically different from each other during the crisis as Table 5.6 depicts. This was in relation to the fact that the study's p-value (0.621) for a two-tailed test was greater than 0.05, which was the study's significance level (Table 5.6). Accordingly, the test's null hypothesis was not rejected showing that the level of efficiency for both types of banks was not statistically different from each other during the crisis.

Table 5.6: t test's output for banks' performance after the crisis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>IB's ROE</i>	<i>CB's ROE</i>
Mean	14.00%	16.92%
Variance	0.9085%	0.7044%
Observations	5	5
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	

df	8
t Stat	-0.514
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.31
t Critical one-tail	1.860
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.621
t Critical two-tail	2.306

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

5.6.2 Effect on banks' efficiency after the crisis

In contrast to the above, the analysis established that the level of efficiency between both types of banks has been relatively different from each other from the time that the crisis ended. This was in relation to the fact that the study's p-value (0.033) for a two-tailed test was less than 0.05, which was the study's significance level (Table 5.7). Accordingly, the test's null hypothesis presuming that the levels of efficiency between both types of banks were not statistically different from each other was rejected in favor of the alternative one that presumed that the level of efficiency between both types of banks was statistically different from each other from the time that the crisis ended. Since the IBs' ROE (14.16%) was relatively higher than the CBs' ROE (12.02%), then the level of efficiency among the Saudi IBs' were said to be relatively higher than the level of efficiency among Saudi CBs as Table 5.7 depicts.

Table 5.7: t test's output for banks' performance after the crisis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Weighted averages (CBs)</i>	<i>Weighted averages (IBs)</i>
Mean	12.02%	14.16%
Variance	0.000200182	0.000335
Observations	7	7
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	11	

t Stat	-2.444
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.016
t Critical one-tail	1.796
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.033
t Critical two-tail	2.201

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

5.7 Banks' insolvency risk

5.7.1 The insolvency risk during the crisis

Having determined that both types of banks were impacted by the crisis, there was the need to determine the insolvency risk of the Saudi banking industry during the crisis. This was aimed at determining the extent to which banks in the industry were likely to file for bankruptcy during the crisis for failure to meet their financial obligations. Given that banks' unique characteristics were presumed throughout the study to protect Saudi IBs from the crisis whereas they exposed Saudi CBs to it, then the presumption was that CBs were at higher insolvency risks than the Islamic ones. The implication was that Saudi CBs were in distress zones during the crisis whereas the Saudi IBs were not in distress zones. To evaluate the validity of this presumption, the Altman's z-score analysis, which involved computing the z-scores for the banks on annual basis and computing the weighted averages, was utilized.

In contrast to the presumption that only Saudi CBs were in distress zones during the crisis because they were impacted by the crisis, the analysis showed that both types of banks were in distress zones. This was in relation to the fact that their weighted average scores were below 1.80 throughout the period under investigation as Figure 5.9 depicts.

Figure 5.9: The bank’s Altman weighted z-score for between 2006 and 2010

(Source: Developed by thesis’ author)

As Figure 5.9 depicts, it was quite evident that even though the z-scores for both types of banks were relatively low even before the crisis started in 2006, they were almost equal in 2006. In spite of this, a closer look at the data showed that the weighted average z-score for CBs was slightly higher than that for IBs in 2006. Even though it declined slightly in 2007, a similar trend was repeated in 2007 with the Islamic z-score declining more than the conventional one. However, in 2008, the z-score for IBs rose significantly whereas the conventional one declined slightly. Between 2008 and 2010, the z-score for CBs remained relatively stable whereas the Islamic one changed significantly. Even though none of the banks included in the analysis filed for bankruptcy like some of the US-based banks did during the crisis, this was an indication that most of them had high chances of filing for bankruptcy based on Altman’s z-score analysis.

To determine whether the differences in the z-scores for both types of banks were statistically different from each other, a t test presuming unequal variances was

conducted. The analysis showed that the differences between the banks' z-scores were not statistically different from each other as Table 6.8 depicts. This was in relation to the fact that the study's p-value (0.591) for a two-tailed test was greater than 0.05, which was the study's significance level. As a result, the null hypothesis presuming that the difference between them was not statistically different from each other was not rejected. Table 5.8 summarizes the findings from the t test.

Table 5.8: The t test for Saudi banks' z-score

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	<i>Weighted averages (IB)</i>	<i>Weighted averages (CBs)</i>
Mean	0.749	0.822
Variance	0.0659	0.0163
Observations	5	5
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	-0.568	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.295	
t Critical one-tail	1.943	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.591	
t Critical two-tail	2.447	

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

The study conclude that both types of banks were at high risks of insolvency between 2006 and 2010 implying that they were impacted by the crisis. As a result, the IBs' unique characteristics did not play major roles protecting Saudi IBs from the effects of the crisis.

5.8 Forces emanating from the crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry

To understand the impact of the crisis on Saudi banking industry and measures taken to protect it from the effects of a similar financial crisis in the future, the first qualitative research question started by asking research participants to indicate whether they were working in the banking industry or not at the time of the crisis. This research question was meant to make sure that research participants worked in the industry at the time of the crisis. Accordingly, it was asked in collaboration with the second research question that sought to determine the number of years the respondents had worked in the bank industry at the time that the crisis occurred, their specific duties at that time and the banks they worked for at that time.

In line with this, the forty people who were included in the study were already working in the Saudi banking industry between 2006 and 2010. About 20 of them representing 50% of the respondents had already worked for approximately 10 years in the industry, 15 of them representing 37.5% of the respondents had worked in it for between five and nine years whereas the rest of them representing the other 12.5% of the respondents had been in the industry for between two and four years. About 75% of them were male whereas 25% of them were female. Their levels of education and ages were as Table 5.9 summarizes them.

Table 5.9: The respondents' demographic characteristics

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	30	75%
Female	10	25%
Total	40	100%
Education level		
Bachelor's	20	50%
Master's	15	37.5%
PHD	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%
Age		

31 - 40	3	7.5%
41 – 50	17	42.5%
51 – 60	15	37.5%
61 and above	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%
Years in bank industry at the time of crisis		
2 – 4 years	5	12.5%
5 – 9 years	15	37.5%
Over 10 years	20	50%
Total	40	100%

(Source: Developed by thesis' author)

Majority of the respondents worked for the banks they worked for during the financial crisis; hence, they had vast knowledge about the impact of the crisis on their respective banks and the industry in general.

The third research question moved a step higher by asking the respondents to describe the history of the crisis from a Saudi Arabian perspective. This was meant to depict the manifestation of the crisis in KSA from a research participants' perspective. Of the 40 respondents, 30 of them claimed that the effects of the crisis were evident in KSA when oil prices declined significantly in the international market.

As an illustration of the way the effects manifested themselves in KSA, one of the respondents from CBs claimed that;

' . . . As soon as oil prices declined in the international market, I knew that the Saudi economy would be impacted negatively by the crisis. However, because the crisis did not start in the country, I expected the effects to be minimal in the economy . . . '

Another respondent from an Islamic bank claimed that;

‘ . . . I expected the worst to happen to our economy because we exported most of oil products to international market . . . However, apart from reduction in oil prices in the international market, nothing much was notable in the Saudi economy.’

Generally, there was an impression that the oil industry, which was critical to the success of most of the sectors in the kingdom, was the major determinant of the impact of the crisis on Saudi economy.

Since the third research question was so general, the fourth research question asked research participants direct question relating to the way their respective banks were impacted by the crisis. About 25 of the respondents claimed that even though the crisis did not start in KSA, its impacts were evident in the oil industry, which impacted banking practices in the kingdom in one way or the other. Most of them claimed that as soon as oil prices declined, some of the notable customers who relied heavily on oil industry stopped honoring their banking obligations as they honored them before. About five of these people attributed the impact of the crisis to the inability of Al Gosaibi group and Saad group to repay their debts on time. One of them from IBs claimed that;

‘ . . . The inability of the Saad group to repay its huge debts on time impacted the bank that I was working for even though the bank was not deterred from offering its services. . . Despite the challenge, effort was made to recover the money and even allow the group to continue with its operations.’

Another respondent from CBs claimed that;

‘ . . . During the crisis, I was a bank manager; hence, I was able to detect the difficulties with which some of the customers especially the major ones faced as they repaid their loans or even submitted their dues to the bank. . . . Despite the challenges, I would not say that the bank was impacted significantly by the crisis, but because customers working especially in the oil industry were impacted by reduced oil prices, then they affected banks’ operations indirectly. . . . The impact, though, was short-lived; hence, we continued with banking operations as soon as things returned to normal’

Without necessarily referring directly to specific institutions or groups of people, other respondents claimed that they noted significant changes in the way people deposited and withdrew their money from banks. One respondent from IBs who was an institutional banker claimed that;

‘ . . . I noted a huge drop from the people and institutions that the bank relied heavily for huge deposits. . . I do not know what happened to that customer because he was not doing business in the oil industry.’

Another respondent from CBs claimed;

‘ . . . There was a huge decline in deposits and even banking activities because the long queues of customers in the bank either depositing or withdrawing money from the banks were not there anymore. At that point, I knew that something needed to be done to improve the banking activities in the bank. . . At first, I thought that the ATM machines that had been installed were responsible for decline in the number of people queuing in banks, but later I changed my mind when I realized that the queues had also reduced even at ATM machines.’

The respondents also claimed that their respective banks opted to disengage in conventional banking practices that were deemed as risky to their banks. In line with this, one of the respondents from CBs claimed that;

‘ . . . As soon as the crisis struck, we were instructed by bank’s management team to desist from engaging in banking practices that exposed CBs to financial crisis. As far as I now, the bank that I worked for did not engage in banking practices that were exploitative in nature. However, from the news going round the media . . . interest-based banking practices were said to be exploitative . . . Though this was the case, I could not substantiate it, but we opted to change our banking practices . . . ’

Another respondent from CBs claimed;

‘ . . . The bank opted to reduce the amount of loans issued on interest for some time . . . However; the exercise was continued as soon as the crisis ended. . . In

spite of this, I do not think that the loans we offered to various customers exposed us to the crisis . . . As a result, I did not support the idea of stopping the loan issuance process even though the decision came from high ranking people in the bank . . .'

In terms of investment, the respondents claimed that some of major banks' customers did not invest their money in their respective banks as they did before. One of the respondents from IBs who worked as a bank manager claimed that;

' . . . There was notable decline in the number of institutional investors who I served at that time. . . Even though I did not understand the cause of the decline, I suspected that the effects of the crisis, which cut across countries, contributed to the decline . . . I say this because as soon as the crisis ended, I started serving many of such customers as I served them before.'

Another respondent from IBs claimed that;

' . . . There was a general feeling that banks were at the risk of collapsing following the number of banks that had filed for bankruptcy in USA and other parts of the world. As a result, some of the customers opted to invest elsewhere or withhold investing in banks. . . To some extent, there was also a general feeling that most of the investors especially the upcoming ones were impacted negatively by declines in oil prices in the international market. For me, I do not have a precise explanation to the cause of decline in investment in banks, but I think most of these factors impacted the way investors made decisions at the time of the crisis.'

Another respondent from CBs claimed that;

' . . . As far as I am concerned, majority of the people opted to forego investing their money in financial products during the crisis. As a result, the bank was unable to raise sufficient capital to invest in its various banking practices.'

In terms of performance, the respondents claimed that the profitability for their various banks was impacted during the crisis. The majority of the respondents who linked the

crisis' effects to their banks' profitability referred to annual reports released at the end of the years during the crisis. One of the respondents from CBs claimed that;

' . . . I realized that our bank had been impacted by the crisis as soon as the financial reports were released at the end of the year. Before then, I thought that the bank had been safe because the crisis did not occur in KSA . . . But I was surprised when it was reported that the bank's revenue had reduced substantially that year.'

Another respondent from IBs claimed that;

' . . . At first, I thought that the bank was not impacted by the crisis because things were running normally, but when the annual report was released later in 2008 and 2009, I realized that the bank's activities had been impacted slightly. I did not see the huge figures that I was used to at the end of the year even though nothing notable could be pinpointed from the report . . .'

Moreover, the respondents especially those who were in high ranks at the time of the crisis claimed that their banks opted to reduce the amounts of loans that they offered to private investors. They claimed that the measure was aimed at protecting their banks from further effects of the crisis from the ones that were already in existence.

Despite the above, some of the respondents were somewhat unsure of the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking practices. One of them claimed that he did not think that the crisis impacted the Saudi banking industry in any way because there were no direct links between Saudi banks and international banks especially the US ones. In spite of this, the respondent indicated that it was possible that foreign banks operating in KSA were impacted by the crisis. Another respondent claimed that effective measures to protect the banking industry from the crisis were already in place; hence, there was no way the industry could be impacted by a US-based crisis.

To probe for deeper explanations, the fifth research questions asked research participants to explain the way banks' processes in terms of policies, structures and the way banks offered services to customers contributed to the effects of the crisis on

individual banks. Although the results were mixed with some of the respondents feeling that IBs were more secure than the conventional ones, there was a feeling that the effects did not emanate from banks' policies, structures and processes. One of the respondents from IBs claimed that;

' . . . Inasmuch as certain people believed that banking processes exposed CBs to the crisis, I did not think that those processes were the ones that exposed our banks to the crisis. To me, the effects of the crisis in KSA emanated from oil prices; hence, no way banking processes exposed Saudi banks to the crisis.'

Another respondent from CBs claimed that;

' . . . All along I have never linked the effects of the crisis on our banks to banking processes and policies because the crisis did not start here in KSA . . . Nevertheless, I have always believed that they exposed the US banks to the crisis because that's where the crisis started.'

On the same note, another respondent claimed that the effects emanated from other sectors of economy; hence, no way banking processes and policies were responsible for the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry. The few respondents who linked the crisis to banking processes and policies claimed that conventional banking practices were highly speculative rather than definite as Islamic ones; hence, they exposed CBs to the crisis and its subsequent effects.

To understand the way the respondents who were representative of the key stakeholders in the Saudi bank industry felt about the way both types of banks handled the financial crisis, the sixth research question asked the respondents to indicate whether IBs dealt with the crisis better or worse than CBs. In contrast to the expectation that IBs would be identified as dealing with the crisis better than CBs, most of the respondents felt that none of the banks dealt with the crisis better than the other because both of them were caught unaware. In spite of this, there was a general feeling that IBs were far much safer than CBs because of the nature of their banking practices. One of the respondents from IBs claimed that;

'Even if both types of banks were impacted by the crisis, I strongly believe that Islamic banking practices are far much better than the conventional ones because IBs do not engage in speculative banking practices. As a result, there is no way Islamic banking practices can expose IBs to financial crisis even though the banks experienced slowed banking activities during the crisis.'

Another respondent from IBs claimed that;

'Actually, I am certain that even if both types of banks were impacted by the crisis, IBs remain to be the favorite banks in the country and else. As such, no way I can support conventional banking practices because they do not align with my religious and national practices, which align to what majority of the people in the country believe in.'

5.9 The subsequent effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry

To understand the measures that the Saudi government with help of relevant bodies had taken to protect the Saudi banking industry from the impact of a similar crisis in the future, the seventh research question asked research participants to pinpoint some of those measures. Of the 40 research participants who took part in the study, 30 of them claimed that SAMA had made it mandatory for Saudi banks to maintain 8 percent of their capital as minimum capital adequacy ratio. As a way of showing that their banks were complying with this measure, one of the respondents from IBs observed that:

' . . . As part of observing this measure, the bank has even gone ahead to maintain higher capital ratios to protect its business practices from any crisis that may emerge in the future.'

Another research participant from CBs claimed;

' . . . The bank being a tier I bank maintains capital ratios as high as 17.17 percent to safeguard its interests and the interests of its customers'.

The respondents also claimed that the SAMA in line with Basel III regulation required Saudi banks to maintain 8.5 percent capital adequacy ratio, which was slightly higher

than the Basel II measure. One of the respondents claimed that the measure was intended to protect banks from the financial distress; hence, it was a good move to him as a bank manager. Another respondent claimed that the measure was intended to ensure that banks had sufficient financial resources to protect them from unforeseen circumstances. As they responded to this question, most of the respondents appreciated the critical role that SAMA was playing in its effort to streamline Saudi banking practices. The respondents claimed that the body was always promulgating rules and guidelines aimed at strengthening banking practices in the kingdom. One of the respondents from IBs claimed that:

‘ . . . The measures implemented by SAMA were for the benefits of individuals banks; as such, I do not see anything wrong with them as some of the people see them . . . I strongly believe that they have so far strengthened the financial position of this bank; hence, do not intend to deviate from them despite the challenge that the bank goes through raising such huge capitals.’

Alongside the above, another respondent from CBs claimed that;

‘ . . . The SAMA always takes corrective measures to make sure that banks follow its guidelines without undermining them. As a result, it is my strong belief that the Saudi banking industry is safe unlike what transpired in 2008.’

The respondents further claimed that SAMA had resulted to utilizing other monetary measures to limit the level of inflation in KSA. They claimed that the high inflation rates witnessed during the crisis contributed to the effects of the crisis to different parts of the world including the Middle East. One of the respondents from IBs claimed that;

‘ . . . The high inflation rates in KSA were responsible for the decline of the oil prices; as such, the government with the help of SAMA has from time to time utilized monetary measures to minimize the level of inflation in the kingdom. In so doing, it has protected the banking industry from the negative effects of the crisis.’

Another respondent from CBs claimed that;

' . . . The government now uses stringent measures to tighten the liquidity level of our bank and others as a way of ensuring that they do not expose the banking industry to the crisis like the conventional banking practices in USA and other parts of the world did in 2008.'

The respondents further claimed that mechanisms had been put in place to increase reserves on demand deposits from 7 percent to 13 percent. In addition, they claimed that similar measures had been developed to increase reserves on time deposits and savings from 2 percent to 4 percent.

5.10 Chapter's summary

In line with the thesis' research questions and objectives, the chapter has provided the thesis' findings. It has established that the changes in oil prices exposed the Saudi banking industry to the crisis. As a result, the banks' unique characteristics did not expose the banking industry to the 2008/09 financial crisis; thus, the performance of Saudi CBs was not statistically different from the performance of their Islamic counterparts during and after the crisis. However, notable differences were identified in the banks' performances after the crisis implying that the banks have recovered from the effects of the crisis differently. Of particular interest was the fact that IBs have recovered faster from the crisis than CBs. The next chapter discusses the above findings in details in relation to the existing body of literature in KSA and other parts of the world.

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

6.1 Discussion

The thesis sought to determine the effect of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry by comparing and contrasting the manner in which Saudi CBs and IBs were impacted or not impacted by the crisis. In line with similar studies, it presumed that whereas CBs were impacted by the crisis, the IBs were never impacted by it because they did not charge interest rates on bank loans or even engaged in other conventional banking practices that were considered risky. In contrast to this presumption, the thesis established that both types of Saudi banks were impacted by the crisis because their performances between 2006 and 2010 were inconsistent implying that they did not remain relatively stable as the researcher presumed they remained. Additionally, the thesis established that the performances of both types of banks were on downward trend between 2006 and 2010 and that they were not statistically different from each other implying that they were impacted almost the same way. More importantly, the thesis established that both types of banks were at the risk of insolvency during the crisis because their z-scores were less than 1.8 suggesting that they were in gray areas, which were risky areas for organizations to survive. Based on these findings, the thesis concluded that both types of banks were impacted negatively by the crisis suggesting that the Islamic banking practices did not protect Saudi IBs from the effects of the crisis.

The above findings were in agreement with Kassim and Abd Majid (2010) who established that Malaysian IBs were also impacted by the crisis contrary to the long-held belief that IBs were not impacted by the crisis. This was important to the thesis because it had significant implications to policy making processes in KSA and other neighboring countries especially the Islamic states. It meant that the long-held belief that IBs were never impacted by financial crisis and that they were least susceptible to financial crisis should be revised for the sake of protecting the Saudi banking industry from the negative effects of a similar crisis in the future. Doing so would be a right move

towards protecting Islamic banking practices and Saudi banking industry as a whole from a misconception that might endanger the future of Islamic banking practices.

The findings were also in agreement with Parashar and Venkatesh (2010) who established that even if the magnitude of effect of the crisis differed from one type of banks to the other, IBs were also impacted negatively by the crisis. In agreement with Parashar and Venkatesh (2010), the thesis established that the performances of both types of banks measured in terms of ROA and ROE were downward sloping between 2006 and 2010 implying that they were affected negatively by the crisis. Once again, this was an important finding because it negated the long-held belief that IBs were not impacted negatively by the crisis. For this reason, it contributed new insights into the existing body of literature by showing that IBs were also susceptible to financial crisis. In so doing, it highlighted the need to change some of the current practices, which downplay the vulnerability of IBs to financial crisis at the expense of CBs.

Furthermore, the findings were in agreement with Ganic (2012) who established that both types of banks from Western Balkans were impacted negatively by the crisis. In line with Ganic (2012), the thesis established that the profitability of the six Saudi banks included in the analysis was impacted negatively by the crisis. This was an important finding given the manner in which the previous studies provided conflicting results some suggesting that the IBs were not impacted by the crisis. Similarly, the findings were in agreement with Saddique et al (2016) who established that both types of banks were impacted negatively by the crisis. Nonetheless, the findings differed slightly with Saddique et al. (2016) because they identified IBs as performing slightly better than CBs. The thesis did not establish any statistically significant difference between the performances of both types of banks during the crisis implying that their performances were relatively the same. Moreover, the findings were in agreement with Qureshi (2018) who established that IBs were effective at managing capital, liquidity and enhancing earnings from the time that the crisis ended. This was in relation to the fact that the study established that Saudi IBs had improved their levels of efficiency between 2011 and 2017, which the thesis defined as non-crisis period.

In spite of the above, the findings were in disagreement with Hasan and Dridi (2010) who established that IBs and CBs in GCC region were impacted by the crisis differently based on their business models. While many factors might contribute to the disagreement, it would be worth noting that the thesis narrowed its scope to Saudi Arabian banks contrary to Hasan and Dridi (2010) who considered 120 banks from GCC region. In addition, it would be worth noting that inasmuch as the larger sample size utilized by Hasan and Dridi (2010) was effective at improving the level of precision and significance level of the test, the fact remained that the study was broad. As a result, it is highly likely that the sample size affected the study's findings negatively as opposed to enhancing them. Alongside the above, it would be worth noting that because different countries were included in the analysis, it was impossible to detect the differences in the performances of both types of banks based on data variability from one country to the other. In spite of this, it would be worth noting that because Hasan and Dridi (2010) appreciated the fact that both types of banks included in the analysis were impacted differently by the crisis then they in a way acknowledged that IBs were also impacted by the crisis, which was similar to what the thesis established. While this is the case, the thesis does not downplay the critical role that conventional banking practices played in exposing US-based banks to financial crisis. It appreciates that the risky banking practices were some of the catalysts that heightened the exposure of the banks in different parts of the world to the crisis. However, the effects of the crisis differed from one country to the other because of the differing banking practices. By appreciating so, the thesis acknowledges the importance of developing effective measures for protecting both types of banks from a similar crisis that may occur in the future.

The findings were also in disagreement with Almanaseer (2014) who established that the crisis did not impact the profitability of IBs selected from GCC region. In contrast to Almanaseer (2014), the thesis established that the ROA and ROE for both types of banks, which were utilized to measure banks' performance and profitability declined throughout the study period, and that they were not statistically different from each other implying that both types of banks were impacted negatively by the crisis. While many factors could be attributed to this difference, it would be worth noting that Almanaseer (2014) utilized linear regression model to predict the extent to which banks' and region's

internal variables, which included banks' sizes, equity capital and macro-economic conditions contributed to banks' profitability measured in terms of ROA and ROE. In line with this focus, the author argued that regional and banks' internal variables enhanced the profitability of IBs from GCC region during the crisis.

Inasmuch as the thesis did not critique the manner in which Almanaseer (2014) conducted his study, it would be worth noting that Ghassan, Alhajhoj and Alaoui (2013) had established that the Saudi Arabian economy had been affected by the crisis. As a result, the presumption that the favorable economic conditions in the region shielded IBs from the negative effects of the crisis was taken out of context meaning that it was far-fetched. In spite of this, it would be worth noting that the author identified the small number of countries included in the study as part of the study's limitations; hence, recommended that further studies should be conducted to fill the gap. In line with this, the current study was conducted to fill the gap and contribute to the existing body of literature.

Furthermore, the findings were in disagreement with Jaffar and Manarvi's (2011) who suggested that IBs outperformed the CBs during the crisis. In contrast to this finding, the thesis identified both types of banks as performing relatively the same way in a downward trend that suggested that they were both impacted negatively by the crisis. Although many factors might be attributed to the disagreement between the two studies, it would be worth noting that the current study was conducted in KSA whereas Jaffar and Manarvi's (2011) conducted their study in Pakistan. This may be one of the reasons contributing to the difference in the studies' findings suggesting that IBs from different countries were impacted by the crisis differently. In addition, it would be worth noting that whereas the current study excluded Al-Inma bank from the sample because it was established in 2007; hence, it did not have financial reports for 2006, 2007 and 2008, Jaffar and Manarvi's (2011) included newly established IBs in the analysis. While the authors claim that they compared average ratios on annual basis, it is obvious that doing so had its own implications to study's findings. From this perspective, the current study did not approach its analysis from that perspective; hence, the disagreement may also emanate from that fact.

Additionally, the findings were in disagreement with Zehri, Abdelbaki and Bouabdellah (2012) who established that the performance of the IBs during the crisis was relatively stable than the performance for their conventional counterparts. In contrast to this finding, the current study established that the performance of Saudi IBs was inconsistent between 2006 and 2010, and that it was relatively the same as the performance of the Saudi CBs. In addition, contrary to Zehri, Abdelbaki and Bouabdellah (2012) who linked the better performance for IBs to Sharia business practices, the current study did not identify the Sharia banking practices as protecting the Saudi IBs from the crisis or even contributing positively to their performances. Nonetheless, this did not imply that the Islamic banking practices were ineffective at protecting the Saudi IBs from the crisis, but it depicted the extent to which the effects of the crisis affected both types of banks. This was important going forward because it highlighted the need for protecting both types of banks from financial crisis.

Similarly, the findings were in disagreement with Abdulle and Kassim (2012) who established that both types of banks performed relatively the same and that contrary to what the thesis established, the performance of IBs was on an upward trend. While the current study was conducted in KSA whereas Abdulle and Kassim (2012) conducted their study in Malaysia, it would be worth noting that both studies utilized ROA and ROE to evaluate the profitability of both types of banks. Accordingly, it was highly likely that whereas the Malaysian IBs recovered from the losses they made before the crisis, the Saudi IBs lost such gains made prior to the crisis. While this might be interpreted in different ways, it suggests that the effects of the crisis differed from one country to the other. For this reason, it would be wrong to generalize that IBs performed relatively better than the CBs during the crisis. Appreciating the fact that IBs were impacted differently from one country to the other would be important because it would highlight the need for protecting both types of banks from financial crisis.

The findings were also in disagreement with Shafique, Faheem and Abdullah (2012) who established that even if IBs were also vulnerable to the crisis, the IBs were not impacted significantly by the crisis because their systems were interest-free. In contrast to this finding, the current study established that the interest system did not expose the

Saudi CBs to the crisis or even the interest-free system protected the Saudi IBs from the crisis. Instead, it established that both types of the banks were impacted by the crisis because other factors other than banks' unique characteristics exposed the Saudi banking industry to the effects of the crisis. Nonetheless, this did not imply that Islamic banking practices were ineffective at protecting IBs from the crisis, but it implied that both types of the banks were vulnerable to financial crisis. This was an important finding because the Saudi banking industry and national economies do not exist in isolation, but they are connected in one way or the other to banking systems in the world and other international systems. As a result, a financial crisis that might occur in other parts of the world might impact the Saudi banking sector; hence, the need to protect it from such crisis.

Likewise, the findings were in disagreement with Merchant (2012) who established that both types of banks in GCC region were able to improve their Equity to Total Asset (EQTA), capital structures and Loan Loss Reserve (LLR) during the crisis. In contrast to this finding, the current study established that the Saudi banks were impacted negatively by the crisis; hence, as opposed to improving their performances, they suffered declines in their profitability, efficiency and increased their insolvency risks. In addition, the findings were in disagreement with Al-Smadi, Hamdan and Almsafir (2013) who established that Malaysian IBs performed relatively better than their conventional counterparts because their systems were competent. In contrast to this finding, the current study established that both types of banks were impacted negatively by the crisis; hence, the IBs did not improve their performances during the crisis. In spite of this, the findings showed that the Saudi IBs were able to improve their efficiency as soon as the crisis ended and even maintain their performance between 2011 and 2017.

Furthermore, the findings were in disagreement with Alshammari (2017) who identified CBs as outperforming their Islamic counterparts. In contrast to Alshammari (2017), the current study established that both types of banks were impacted negatively by the crisis and that the difference in their performance was not statistically different from each other. In addition, contrary to Alshammari (2017) who identified CBs as performing

better than IBs, the current study identified IBs as performing relatively better than CBs between 2011 and 2017.

Similarly, the findings were in disagreement with Alqahtani and Mayes (2018) who established that even if there was no statistically significant difference between the performances of both types of banks during the crisis, the IBs were impacted more than the CBs as soon as the effects of the crisis permeated to other parts of economy. In contrast to Alqahtani and Mayes (2018), the current study established that both types of banks were impacted the same way by the crisis, but IBs were able to enhance their efficiency as soon as the crisis ended. At bank level, the findings were also in disagreement with Alqahtani and Mayes (2018) who established that the effects of the crisis were applicable to large banks, but not applicable to small banks. In contrast to this argument, the current study established that the small banks that were included in the analysis were the most affected banks contrary to the large banks. While this was the case, it would be important to note that Alqahtani and Mayes (2018) collected data from GCC region meaning that KSA was also included in the sample. In spite of this, the findings from the current study contradicted what Alqahtani and Mayes (2018) established suggesting that individual banks were impacted differently.

Alongside the above, the findings were also in disagreement with Tabash and Dhankar (2014) who established that Saudi IBs were relatively stable between 2005 and 2010 suggesting that they were not impacted by the crisis. In contrast to this finding, the current study established that Saudi IBs were impacted by the crisis between 2006 and 2010; as such, their performances were not relatively stable because the banks were also impacted by the crisis. The implication was that contrary to Tabash and Dhankar (2014) who suggested that Saudi IBs had adequate capital and high levels of liquidity during the crisis then it was possible that Saudi IBs did not enjoy adequate capitals and high levels of liquidity during the crisis.

With regard to the level of efficiency, the findings were in disagreement with Ouerghi (2014) who identified IBs as less efficient than their conventional counterparts. In contrast to this finding, although the current study did not establish any statistically significant difference between the levels of efficiency of the two banks during the crisis,

it identified IBs as more efficient than CBs between 2011 and 2017. This simply suggested that the Saudi IBs were making better use of the resources available to them contrary to what their conventional counterparts were doing from the time that the crisis ended.

In spite of the above, the findings were in agreement with Aziz, Husin and Hashmi (2016) who identified IBs as enjoying higher levels of efficiency than their conventional counterparts. This was in relation to the fact that the current study identified Saudi IBs as enhancing their levels of efficiency from the time that the crisis ended contrary to their conventional counterparts whose levels of efficiency have been on the decline. In addition, the findings were in agreement with Cerovic, Nikolaj and Maradin (2017) who identified IBs as more efficient than CBs. In spite of this, it would be worth noting that the current study identified Saudi IBs as more efficient than CBs from the time that the crisis ended implying that their levels of efficiency were also impacted negatively by the crisis. Regardless, of the above, the current study did not identify banks' unique characteristics as protecting IBs from the crisis or even exposing Saudi CBs to the crisis. This was an important finding to the Saudi banking industry because it showed that both types of banks were impacted the same way by the crisis suggesting the need to protect the industry as a whole.

A review of the literature indicated that IBs offered services in a manner that was quite different from that of CBs. It indicated that while strict measures were observed in Islamic banking practices to ensure that banks did not manipulate customers at the expense of making profit, conventional banking practices were less restrictive. As a result, they allowed banks to conduct their business practices without necessarily considering customers' interests. Even though it was possible that some IBs could have been tempted by laxity in banking practices that prevailed prior to the crisis to embrace such banking practices, it was presumed that IBs in KSA were never influenced by such laxity. Accordingly, they did not compromise their banking practices because they adhered to Sharia law that guided their banking practices. This notwithstanding it would be worth noting that the literature review showed that the banking industry was affected by a variety of factors and forces that were beyond the banks' characteristics (Siraj &

Pillai, 2012). Accordingly, it was highly likely that even though banks' characteristics contributed slightly to the financial crisis, other factors also contributed to its development and its subsequent effects on some banks and regions in the world. In the light of this, the current study was carried out in KSA to determine whether there was significant difference between the performance of IBs and CBs. Besides, it was carried out to determine the extent to which those differences contributed to the performance of those banks in the event that the difference was significant.

The assumption was that it was possible that the two types of banks performed significantly differently to the extent that their characteristics contributed to differences in performance. Since most of the previous studies provided conflicting results, it was felt that there was the need to evaluate the extent to which banks' differences contributed or did not contribute to banks' performance between 2006 and 2017. This was the period slightly before, during and immediately after the financial crisis occurred in the world; as such, it was important to the current study.

Before looking at the way banks' unique characteristics exposed or protected the Saudi banking industry from the crisis, it would be important to start by appreciating the fact that the thesis sought to determine whether banks' type, which was the independent variable, contributed or did not contribute to the way Saudi banks were impacted or not impacted by the crisis. The performance of banks in terms of ROA and ROE during and after the crisis was the dependent variable. The thesis presumed that because Saudi IBs did not charge interests on bank loans or even engage in banking practices that were speculative in nature, then they were not impacted by the crisis. By presuming so, it expected that if the findings would show any effect of the crisis on Saudi banking industry, then such effect would be on Saudi CBs only. The reasoning was that the Saudi CBs would be impacted by the crisis because they engaged in conventional banking practices that led to the crisis in USA and other parts of the world.

In contrast to the above, the results indicated that both types of banks were impacted by the crisis implying that the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry did not emanate from banks' unique characteristics. While this finding is an interesting one because it negates the long-held belief that Islamic banking practices do not expose IBs

to financial crisis, it does not imply that Islamic banking practices are weak or ineffective (Kassim & Abd Majid, 2010). Instead, it suggests that other factors other than banking practices exposed the Saudi banking industry to the crisis. Under such a case, then the Islamic banking practices should not be accused of being ineffective at protecting the Saudi IBs from the crisis.

From the above understanding, it was possible that the effects of the crisis spread to KSA as they spread to other parts of the world. Under such a case, the spillover and contagion effects could be responsible for the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry (Rigobon, 2016). While looking at this issue, it would be important to appreciate the fact that the crisis that started in USA did not occur in vacuum or in seclusion to the extent that other parts of the world did notice what was going on in USA. Furthermore, it would be important to note that even though different parts of the world conduct banking practices independently, banking practices are almost similar in different parts of the world. As a result, the presumption that conventional banking practices did not expose Saudi CBs to the crisis should be evaluated cautiously because such practices are able to expose the banks to the crisis in the future.

Alongside the above, it would be important to appreciate the fact that the crisis impacted other sectors of world economy meaning that its impact was not restricted to banking industry alone. Appreciating this fact helps one acknowledge that other sectors of the global economy were impacted by the crisis, and that it was possible that they transferred their effects to other sectors and other parts of the world. From that perspective, it was possible that the Saudi banking industry was impacted by the Saudi oil industry that was impacted negatively by the decline in oil prices and demand for oil throughout the world during the crisis.

The thesis also sought to compare and contrast the way Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the crisis. In line with previous studies, it presumed that both types of banks performed in a consistent manner before and during the crisis. In addition, it presumed that because IBs did not engage in the banking practices that CBs engaged in; which were presumed to contribute to the crisis, then the IBs were not impacted by the crisis. In contrast to this presumption, the thesis established that both types of banks

were impacted by the crisis. As a result, as opposed to their performances remaining relatively stable, they declined significantly during the crisis. In this respect, the first and second null hypotheses that presumed that both types of banks performed consistently during and after the crisis were not supported by the findings. In so doing, the study established that both Saudi IBs and CBs were impacted negatively by the crisis.

The above was in line with Kassim and Abd Majid (2010), Parashar and Venkatesh (2010), Ganic (2012) and Saddique et al. (2016) who established that both types of banks were impacted negatively by the crisis. However, it was in disagreement with Hasan and Dridi (2010), Almanaseer (2014), Jaffar and Manarvi's (2011) and Zehri, Abdelbaki and Bouabdellah (2012) among others who argued that IBs were not impacted by the crisis. Even though most of the null hypotheses were not supported by the study's findings, it would be imperative to acknowledge the fact that the third null hypothesis that presumed that there was no statistically significant difference between the performances of the two types of banks during the crisis was supported by the findings. Although this was the case, it would be important to note that by presuming so, the null hypothesis assumed that both types of banks were not impacted by the crisis because they were not located in USA, which was the epicenter for the crisis. However, because the null hypothesis was supported by the study's findings, then it implied that the characteristics for Saudi CBs did not expose them to the crisis like they did to the US-based banks. Similarly, they implied that the characteristics for Saudi IBs did not expose them to the effects of the crisis.

While many factors could be attributed to the effects of the crisis on both types of banks, it was quite evident that the effects of the crisis were contagious because they affected several areas of world economy as opposed to limiting their effects to US banking sector alone. From this understanding, it would be worth noting that they affected negatively the oil industry by decreasing oil prices and reducing the demand for exports from GCC countries and KSA in particular (Abdelbak, 2010). This reduced economic growth and net exports in KSA for a period of about three years (Ghassan, Alhajhoj & Alaoui, 2013). In addition, it affected investment in KSA because investors did not have money to invest or even deposit to banks. Even though investors had such resources, it

would be worth noting that some of them were hesitant to invest them because of the uncertainty at the time. Accordingly, its effects spread even to IBs contrary to the long-held belief that IBs were never impacted by the crisis (Kassim & Abd Majid, 2010). This was an important finding because it depicted the severity of the crisis to KSA and other parts of the world.

According to Latif et al. (2016), the IBs were more efficient than CBs during the crisis. However, the findings suggested that the level of efficiency between the two types of banks was almost similar because it did not differ statistically from each other. It was possible that Saudi IBs were not efficient during the crisis meaning that they did not utilize resources effectively. Alternatively, it was possible that their level of efficiency was impacted negatively by the crisis. More importantly, it was possible that CBs utilized their resources effectively during the crisis contrary to IBs that utilized them ineffectively. Each of these likelihoods has notable implications to the future of Saudi banking industry. In the event that the Saudi IBs were not able to utilize their resources effectively during the crisis, then it means that a similar crisis will impact their performance in the future negatively (Parashar & Venkatesh, 2010). Such an incidence would be disastrous to the Saudi banking industry and the banking practices that would be adopted from the presumption that Islamic banking practices are less vulnerable to financial crisis. In the event that the level of efficiency between the two types of banks was not statistically different from each other during the crisis because Saudi CBs utilized their resources effectively during that time, then this would be disastrous to the Saudi banking industry as well. It would mean that CBs should be allowed to engage in exploitative practices if they engaged in them during the crisis to enhance their efficiency (Ganic, 2012). In the event that the level of efficiency was impacted negatively by the crisis, then there would be the need to take precautionary measures to protect the Saudi banking industry from the crisis now and in the future.

Regardless of the possible scenario, it would be worth noting that the ROE that was utilized to measure the level of efficiency between the two types of banks can be decomposed into its constituents to explain the cause of the difference between the two types of banks during and after the crisis. With the help of this analysis, it would be

possible to decompose ROE into ROA and leverage (Hasan & Dridi, 2010). Based on the two constituents, it could be possible that Saudi IBs have over the years enhanced their ROE by improving their ROA or even making better use of financial leverage from the time that the crisis ended in 2010. In the event that they have done so by improving their ROA, this would mean that their ROA are relatively higher than they were during the crisis (Saddique et al., 2016). Nevertheless, the results suggested that they dropped by about 1 percent between 2011 and 2017 implying that the Saudi IBs that were included in the analysis did not enhance their efficiency after the crisis by improving their ROA.

Since the thesis did not evaluate banks' levels of leverages between 2011 and 2017, it would be wrong to suggest that Saudi IBs improved their efficiency by making better use of financial leverages. However, in the event that this was the case, then it could be said that the Saudi IBs have over the years enhanced their levels of efficiency by making better use of liabilities (Latif et al., 2016). Because it would be wrong to reach to such a conclusion so fast, it would be necessary to decompose ROE further into leverage, total asset turnover and net profit margin. The net profit margin in this case represents the level of profitability whereas the total asset turnover represents the level of efficiency in each type of bank (Hasan & Dridi, 2010).

Since the ROE for the IBs that were included in the analysis rose from 14 percent to 14.16 percent during and after the crisis whereas the ROE for CBs dropped from 16.92 percent to 12.02 percent during the same period, then Saudi IBs have enhanced their levels of efficiency from the time that the crisis ended. This suggests that the increase in ROE has been a function of improving banks' levels of efficiency and profitability. Without necessarily going to the final step of evaluating the effect of tax and interest burdens, it would be possible that Saudi IBs enhance their ROE by enhancing their levels of efficiency and profitability (Hasan & Dridi, 2010). In contrast, it is possible that Saudi CBs reduce their ROE by decreasing their asset utilization and operating efficiency. In spite of this, additional research would be required to identify the cause for the decrease in CBs' ROE especially after the crisis. This would be important going

forward because it would highlight what Saudi CBs need to do now and in the future to enhance their performances.

Regardless of the above, the apparent difference in the level of efficiency between the two types of banks for the period between 2011 and 2017 could be because of chance, but it would be important to appreciate the fact that it is consistent with previous studies. It is in agreement with Latif et al (2016) who identified IBs as more efficient than CBs. This suggests that from the time that the crisis ended, Saudi IBs have been utilizing their resources better than Saudi CBs. While this issue would be debatable based on the number of banks included in the analysis, it suggests the need to ensure that both types of banks utilize their resources effectively to enhance their continuity in the future. In addition, it suggests the need to ensure that Saudi banks utilize financial leverages effectively based on existing capital structure policies.

The Altman z-score analysis, which was conducted to depict the manner in which both types of banks were impacted by the crisis, established that the z-score scores for both types of banks were relatively low during the crisis. Even if none of the Saudi banks filed for bankruptcy like some of the US banks did during the crisis, this was an indication that most of them were impacted significantly by the crisis. It suggested that most of the banks experienced liquidity challenges during the crisis, and that they were at the point of failing to meet their banking responsibilities (Erfani & Vasigh, 2018). Even though the issue of newness of Bank Al-Bilad, which was established in 2004 as an Islamic bank, could be raised as one of the factors that impacted the performance of Saudi IBs during the crisis, it would be worth noting that the bank had been in business for about three years before the crisis occurred. As a result, it had already established itself as one of effective IBs in KSA given the dominance of Islamic banking practices in the kingdom.

Alongside the above, it would be worth noting that even though the study did not focus much of its attention on evaluating the level of insolvency between 2011 and 2017, the z-scores for most of the banks included in the analysis were relatively low. Accordingly, even though most of them might not be encountering liquidity challenges, they might be vulnerable to financial challenges if the current measures would be violated (Erfani & Vasigh, 2018).

The thesis also evaluated the forces emanating from the crisis that contributed to the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry. It presumed that other factors other than banks' unique characteristics could have exposed the Saudi banking industry to the crisis. While the presumption could appear far-fetched, it was important to the contribution of the study's findings to the body of existing literature because it enabled the study to look at other factors that exposed Saudi banking industry to the crisis. Theoretically, the study presumed that it was possible that the spillover and contagion effects could have been responsible for the effect of the crisis that was felt in KSA among the Saudi banks. The spillover effect was identified as the way events in one part of the world spread to other parts of the world due to world interconnectedness (Rigobon, 2016). On the other hand, the contagion effect was identified as the simultaneous effect that was felt in Saudi banking industry out of the banking crisis in USA without necessarily emanating from the interconnectedness of the world financial system.

The theoretical framework identified global banks in form of foreign banks as the major vehicles for spreading the effects of financial crisis. In spite of this, the foreign banks based in KSA were not included in the analysis implying that the effects of the crisis that was identified in the study did not emanate from them. For this reason, other factors other than foreign banks contributed to the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry. Prior to looking at the other factors, it would be important to appreciate the fact the theoretical framework with the help of the contagion effect theory suggested that it was possible that the effects of the crisis spread to Saudi banking industry based on interrelation of the financial systems (Rigobon, 2016). Inasmuch as this was possible, the results did not link the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry to interrelation of the financial systems because the effects did not emanate from banks' unique characteristics.

The theoretical framework also identified information as one of the factors that facilitate the spread of spillover effects to different parts of the world. It asserted that information in one country was able to influence investors in another country to take actions that align with information obtained from another country (Rigobon, 2016). From this

perspective, it might be argued that the Saudi banking industry was impacted by the crisis because Saudi investors based most of their decisions on information they obtained from USA. Inasmuch as it might be true that Saudi investors and even Saudi CBs took various actions based on the information they obtained from USA or other parts of the world that had already been impacted by the crisis, the current study did not evaluate the influence of that information. As a consequence, it does not link the impact of the crisis on Saudi banking industry to the information obtained from USA and other parts of the world that were impacted by the crisis (Abdelbaki, 2010). More importantly, it would be important to appreciate the fact that the effects did not emanate from political contagion between USA and KSA because the two countries do not have close political ties.

Alongside the above, the theoretical framework established that some crises were never contagious meaning that their effects did not occur simultaneously without depending on something that can be identified (Rigobon, 2016). By establishing so, it identified the level of business ties between different countries and parts of the world as the source of the effects of the crisis. It argued that if the level of business tie between different countries is high, then the effects of the crisis could be high and vice versa (Abdelbaki, 2010). To some extent, business ties between KSA and other parts of the world could be the main factor that contributed to the effect of the crisis on Saudi banking industry. This is in relation to the fact that the results suggested that most of the banks that were included in the study were impacted by the crisis because some of their businesses depended on oil industry, which was impacted negatively by the crisis.

One may argue that banks' dependence on oil industry was not the main factor that contributed to the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry because effort has been made to diversify the Saudi economy from the time that the crisis ended. However, inasmuch as the Saudi government has over the years tried to diversify its economy, majority of Saudi businesses depend heavily on oil industry between 2006 and 2010. In line with this, it would be important to note that the level of uncertainty in the banking sector and other financial sectors heightened as soon as two of the major family owned groups in the kingdom namely Al Gosaibi and Saad defaulted paying their

debts on time (Ghassan, Alhajhoj, & Alaoui, 2013). While the study did not focus its attention on the groups, it would be worth noting that five of the research participants highlighted the two as part of the notable effects of the crisis in KSA. They claimed that their banks were impacted by the crisis because it affected the groups' abilities to repay their debts on time. By claiming so, they linked the crisis to the challenges their banks went through during the crisis. Inasmuch as the effect was indirect, it would be imperative to appreciate the fact that the research participants who were notable people in the industry linked such effects to the crisis.

Embarking on the issue of business ties between KSA and other parts of the world, it would be important to appreciate the fact inasmuch as the level of business ties with other parts of the world is relatively low, KSA supplies oil to them. In addition, it would be important to appreciate the fact that oil prices plummeted during the crisis (Abdelbaki, 2010). As a result, inasmuch as KSA was not at the epicenter for the crisis, the impact on the oil industry spread to other sectors of its economy. Appreciating this fact helps one to acknowledge the way the effects of the crisis spread to Saudi banking industry without necessarily depending on banks' unique characteristics. Even though the study did not measure the level of effect of the crisis on Saudi banking industry, it would be important to appreciate the fact that it was slightly high because the Saudi economy depended heavily on the oil industry (Tabash & Dhankar, 2014). This effect spread to banking industry because most of economic activities in KSA depended on oil and its related byproducts (Abdelbaki, 2010).

In line with the above, it would be worth noting that the fundamental view of the theoretical framework observes that whenever countries are struck by crisis that reduce their consumption levels, they tend to reduce their imports. The reduction in imports does not only affect businesses in the host countries, but it also affects trade partners (Rigobon, 2016). To a large extent, this is what happened to the Saudi Arabian case because most of the countries that imported oil during the crisis were impacted negatively by the crisis (Abdelbaki, 2010). As a result, they reduced their oil imports, which to a large extent resulted to reduction in oil prices. According to Ghassan, Alhajhoj and Alaoui (2013), the reduction in oil prices resulted to declines in economic

growth in KSA, which affected other sectors of the economy including the banking sector.

Alongside the above, it would be important to appreciate the fact that inasmuch as KSA does not have strong ties with USA in various businesses, USA remains an important consumer for the oil. While one may argue that USA is not the only major consumer of oil in the world, it would be important to appreciate the fact that its demand for oil in the world economy matters a lot (Agénor & Pereira da Silva, 2018). In addition, it would be important to appreciate the fact that other parts of the world especially developed countries and China were impacted in one way or the other by the crisis. As a result, they impacted negatively the demand for oil, which the Saudi economy and banking industry, depended heavily for their business practices (Rigobon, 2016). By appreciating this, it would be easier to see the way conventional channels especially the trade ones contributed to the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry.

Since the world financial system were interconnected in one way or the other even though banks in different parts of the world operated independently, the results suggested that the spillover effect could have been responsible for the effect of the crisis that was felt in Saudi banking industry. The analysis showed that when other sectors of the economy were impacted by the crisis, they impacted the banking sector indirectly. This was in line with Abdelbak (2010) who showed that the crisis affected significantly oil prices, which was an instrumental factor in the Saudi economy. By decreasing oil prices and demand for most of exports from GCC region and KSA in particular, the banking sector was impacted indirectly; hence, the decline in the performance of Saudi banks included in the analysis.

Having determined that the Saudi banking industry was impacted by the crisis as a whole, then it was necessary to determine the manner in which current banking practices had been transformed to protect the industry from a similar crisis. From the qualitative study that was conducted to complement the secondary quantitative data, the study established that several measures had been taken from the time that the crisis ended. Some of the measures included increasing the reserve levels for time deposits, savings and demand deposits. Other measures included the monetary measures that

SAMA issues from time to time among other measures. From this perspective, it would be worth noting that since 2008, SAMA has assumed power to promulgate rules and regulations that ought to be followed in KSA relating to lending limits, market risks and capital adequacy ratios (Tanim-UI-Islam & Ashrafuzzaman, 2015). While the rules may appear insignificant in protecting Saudi banking industry from similar effects in the future, they play vital roles ensuring that banks do not overstep their mandates in providing banking services. In so doing, they limit the growth of credit risks that may expose Saudi banks to financial crisis as it happened in USA prior to the crisis occurred.

In spite of the above, it was evident that even if research participants appreciated the effectiveness of the measures in place in protecting Saudi banking industry from financial crisis, most of them highlighted the need for localizing some of the measures. This did not mean that the research participants downplayed the importance of executing the current measures, but it highlighted the need for making sure that the vulnerability of the Saudi economy to external forces was minimized. To a large extent, one might argue that such measures have been put in place because the Saudi government has made effort from the time that the crisis ended to diversify the economy. While this is the case, it would be important to appreciate the fact that most of the banks included in the analysis including the IBs were impacted by the crisis because they depended heavily on the oil industry (Al-Deehani, El-Sadi & Al-Deehani, 2015). As a result, it would be vital for Saudi banks to also diversify their businesses like the Saudi government has done. Doing so would be critical in protecting them from the effects of external financial crises.

Throughout the study, the thesis presumed that if the Saudi banking industry was impacted negatively by the 2008/09 financial crisis, then the banks' unique characteristics were responsible for the impact. By presuming so, the thesis expected that the performance of Saudi CBs would be significantly different from that of the Saudi IBs between 2006 and 2017. The rationale behind this presumption was that the moral failure in conventional banking practices that resulted in imprudent lending, excessive leverage, supervision failure and excessive debts exposed Saudi CBs to the crisis (Alqahtani & Mayes, 2018). Conversely, it was presumed that the Islamic banking

principles protected Saudi IBs from the crisis by prohibiting interests, uncertainty and gambling in banking practices. Contrary to this presumption, the thesis established that both Saudi IBs and CBs were impacted negatively by the 2008/09 financial crisis. A critical look at the issue demonstrated that changes in oil prices were responsible for the impact of the Saudi banking industry. As the conceptual framework hypothesized, other factors other than banks' unique characteristics exposed the Saudi banking industry to the 2008/09 financial crisis. For the Saudi banking industry, the changes in oil prices exposed it to the crisis; thus, the banks' unique characteristics did not play critical roles in protecting the Saudi IBs from the crisis.

6.2 Findings' implication to policy development

For many years, there has been a presumption that IBs are least susceptible to financial crisis because they do not charge interest rates on bank loans and even engage in the speculative banking practices that CBs engage in. However, contrary to this presumption, the thesis established that both Saudi IBs and CBs were impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis. The findings have several implications to policy development going forward. Firstly, the fact that the two types of banks were impacted negatively by the financial crisis, then it would be prudent to evaluate the risk management practices utilized by both types of banks on a continuous basis. This would ensure that effective measures would be developed and put in place to protect the Saudi banking industry from the effects of financial crisis. The IBs on their part should focus on making sure that they develop measures that address their unique risk challenges without presuming that they would be secure without developing such measures. Accordingly, it would be vital for them to include different groups of people ranging from Sharia scholars to government institutions mandated with overseeing the management of IBs in the process of developing such measures. A similar strategy should be utilized among CBs to ensure that both types of banks would be secure from financial crisis in the future.

Secondly, the findings highlight the need for protecting the Saudi economy from external forces especially those related to changes in oil prices. Even though it might be impossible to thwart those forces completely given the interconnectedness of the world economy and the critical role that oil plays in the global economy, there would be the

need for the Saudi government to diversify the economy. The diversification in this case would minimize the overreliance of the major sectors in the economy on oil; thus, reduce the impact of financial crisis from other parts of the world on Saudi banking sector and other sectors.

6.3 Chapter's summary

The chapter has discussed the study's findings by comparing them with similar studies conducted in other parts of the world. Special attention was directed to specific research questions to determine the extent to which the study had answered or not answered the questions. The thesis established that the findings were in agreement with some of the studies whereas part of its findings was in disagreement with other studies. Explanations were provided where necessary to explain the differences in the findings. It was determined that while banks' unique characteristics exposed banks in other parts of the world to the 2008/09 financial crisis, the conventional banking practices did not expose the Saudi CBs to the crisis as hypothesized throughout the study. Additionally, it was determined that the Islamic banking practices did not protect the Saudi IBs from the crisis because they too were impacted by the crisis like their conventional counterparts. A critical discussion was provided to indicate how changes in oil prices exposed the Saudi banking industry to the 2008/09 financial crisis. The chapter concluded by discussing the findings' implications to policy development going forward. The next chapter concludes the thesis by summarizing the findings and recommending the way forward.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION

7.1 Chapter's overview

The overall aim of this thesis was to advance an understanding of the way Saudi banking industry was impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis by comparing the performance of the Saudi IBs with the performance of Saudi CBs during and after the crisis. The specific research objectives included;

1. Evaluating critically the unique characteristics of the Saudi IBs and CBs that contributed or did not contribute to the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry.
2. Comparing and contrasting the way Saudi IBs and CBs performed during and after the 2008/09 financial crisis.
3. Evaluating the insolvency risk for Saudi CBs in relation to that for Saudi IBs during the crisis.
4. Identifying the forces emanating from the 2008/09 financial crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry
5. Formulating recommendations that could be used to minimize the effects of a probable financial crisis in the future on Saudi banking industry

This section of the chapter revisits the above research objectives by way of summarizing the thesis' main findings and offering the main lessons that can be drawn from the findings. It then proceeds to recommending the way forward before concluding the thesis by clarifying the thesis' contribution to the existing body of knowledge. With the help of this structure, it is hoped that it will be possible to conclude the thesis by depicting the way various research objectives were met throughout the analysis and even highlighting the contribution of the current study to the existing body of literature. Guidance will also be offered on how the current work can be progressed.

7.2 Research objectives

7.2.1: Research objective 1: Banks' unique characteristic

7.2.1.1 Summary

The thesis established that even though the 2008/09 financial crisis did not start in Saudi Arabia or in Middle East, it impacted negatively the Saudi banking industry. This was in contrast to the presumption that the effects were restricted to Saudi CBs alone. Contrary to this presumption, the effects spread even to Saudi IBs, and they ranged from decline in banks' performance in terms of ROA and ROE to increase in insolvency risks among both types of banks. The notable effect was that even though none of the Saudi banks filed for bankruptcy during and after the crisis, most of the banks were at high risks of insolvency. Even though the study did not evaluate the insolvency risk from the time that the crisis ended, evidence showed that the condition had not changed much since the crisis ended. In spite of this, very little has been done to strengthen the banking practices and protect them from financial crisis that may occur in the future.

Alongside the above, even if both types of banks were impacted by the crisis contrary to the presumption that Saudi IBs were not impacted by it, the thesis established that Saudi IBs were significantly different from Saudi CBs. It established that contrary to the CBs that charged interests on loans, Saudi IBs did not charge interests on banks' loans. Instead, they added markup profits on their various products, which they then shared with people who invested their money with them. In so doing, they engaged in partnership relationships with investors as opposed to engaging in lender-borrower relationships with them that Saudi CBs engaged in with their respective customers.

Furthermore, contrary to CBs that did not expect to make losses in the event that entrepreneurs made losses from their business enterprises thereby did not care much about the businesses they engaged in, Saudi IBs shared losses with entrepreneurs. As a result, they gauged business risks as they offered loans to entrepreneurs and even monitored the way entrepreneurs invested the money they offered to them. More importantly, they offered banks products and services that were less speculative in

nature; as such, most of their products had tangible resources to secure them. In contrast, the Saudi CBs offered less tangible products and services because of their banking practices. Moreover, the contracts that Saudi IBs engaged in with customers involved giving and taking; hence, they were not speculative or even derivative in nature like most of CBs in different parts of the world engaged in. Despite the differences, the thesis did not link the conventional banking practices to the effects of the crisis on Saudi CBs and Saudi banking industry in general. It established that other factors other than banking practices exposed the Saudi banking industry to the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis.

7.2.1.2 Main lesson

The main lesson that can be drawn from the effects of the crisis on the Saudi banking industry is that both Saudi IBs and CBs are vulnerable to financial crisis that occur in other parts of the world. Even though the effects might vary from type of bank to the other, the fact remains that other factors other than banks' unique characteristics might expose Saudi banks to financial crisis. As a result, it would be wrong to presume that Saudi IBs may not be impacted by financial crisis because they do not engage in speculative banking practices. Acknowledging this fact would be critical at protecting the Saudi banking industry as a whole from the negative effects of a financial crisis. In addition, it would be important in determining the different measures that work effectively for both types of banks.

Additionally, it was evident that different parts of the world were exposed to the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis by different factors. As a result, it would be wrong to presume that conventional banking practices, moral failure, excessive debts and imprudent lending were the only factors that exposed the Saudi banking industry to the crisis. Such a presumption would be ill-advised because it would hinder effort made so far to protect the industry from the crisis in the future. In addition, it would misguide the measures that would be taken in the future to protect the Saudi banking industry because it would consider Islamic banking practices as less susceptible to financial crisis and conventional banking practices as highly susceptible to financial crisis. By so doing, it would result to protective measures that may expose the Saudi banking

industry to other financial crisis in the future because the measures that would be developed may not focus much of their attention on Islamic banking practices.

7.2.1.3 Recommendation

In view of the above, the thesis recommends that effort should be made to protect both types of banks from financial crisis without considering Saudi Islamic banks as less vulnerable to financial crisis. Doing so would minimize the vulnerability of the Saudi banking industry to financial crisis that may occur in other parts of the world. In addition, it would minimize the risk of the industry from financial risks that may emanate from Islamic banking practices either from neighboring regions or within KSA.

7.2.2 Research objective 2: The performance of Saudi IBs and CBs during and after the crisis

7.2.2.1 Summary

In contrast to the presumption that IBs were not impacted by the crisis, the thesis established that the performances of both types of banks were inconsistent during the crisis. Of great concern was the fact that the ROA and ROE for both types of banks declined between 2006 and 2010, which was considered to be the crisis period in the thesis. A similar trend was also identified after the crisis, which was defined as the period between 2011 and 2017. The trend showed that the ROA for both types of banks have been inconsistent from the time that the crisis ended meaning that they have been going up and down. While such a trend is expected in any economy, the trend is worrisome because it is downward especially among CBs. Even though the performance for both types of banks was not statistically different from each other in terms of ROA from the time that the crisis ended, it was statistically different from each other in terms of ROE. Of great concern was the fact that even though the ROE for IBs had not improved much, the ROE for CBs had declined substantially implying that it had been on a downward trend from the time that the crisis ended.

7.2.2.2 Main lesson

The main lesson that can be drawn from this research objective is that even though both types of banks were impacted by the crisis, the effects of the crisis have been persistent on Saudi CBs more than on Saudi IBs. While the dominance of Islamic banking practices in Saudi Arabia could be responsible for the difference in the performance of both types of banks, the fact remains that something needs to be done to enhance the continuity of Saudi CBs. As a result, it would be wrong to sit back and watch the performance of Saudi CBs decline even after the crisis ended about ten years ago.

7.2.2.3 Recommendation

To address the above challenge, the thesis recommends that the SAMA, which regulates banking in KSA, should force the Saudi CBs to narrow their scopes to commercial banking practices without extending their services to investment practices. Under such a practice, the banks would determine whether they wish to operate as investment banks or as commercial banks. As commercial banks, the Saudi CBs would attract deposits from the members of the public and convert the deposits into long-term loan facilities without engaging in activities designated to investment banks. On the other hand, the banks that opt to engage in investment activities would thereby not finance their illiquid assets by short-term credits. Under such a practice, CBs would be separated from investment banks thereby reduce the risk of financial crisis spreading to other financial institutions. Additionally, it would ensure that the Saudi CBs would be subject to normal bank regulations and deposit insurance thereby reduces their vulnerability to financial crisis. By recommending so, the study acknowledges that if nothing is done at the moment, the future of Saudi banking industry might be at risk given the persistent insolvency risk identified among the majority of the banks that took part in the study. Accordingly, something should be done now to protect the future of the Saudi banking industry particularly in areas related to conventional banking practices.

Alongside the above, the SAMA should evaluate both types of banks continuously to ensure that they maintain the minimum capital requirements. The thesis recommends

that even if the minimum capital requirements have been adjusted accordingly to meet the international standards, the SAMA should from time to time even without the knowledge of the banks evaluate their balance sheets to ensure that they do not violate the new regulation. Additionally, it should encourage the banks to maintain relatively higher capital ratios than the minimum ones. Doing so would ensure that the banks would be ready to avert the possible negative effects that would emanate from unforeseen financial challenges thereby minimize the risk of financial crisis in the Saudi banking industry.

7.2.3: Research objective 3: Banks' insolvency risk during the crisis

7.2.3.1 Summary

Even though none of the Saudi banks filed for bankruptcy during the crisis, the thesis established that most of the banks in KSA were at the risk of insolvency during the crisis. This was in relation to the fact that most of their Altman's z-scores were below 1.80 indicating that they were at high risk of going bankrupt. Even if the thesis did not evaluate the persistence of the insolvency risks after the crisis, the data showed that most of banks were still at that risk even after the crisis.

7.2.3.2 Main lesson

The main lesson from this research objective was that even if Saudi banks were able to survive the financial crisis and even continue offering services even at the time that the current study was conducted, there was the need to secure individual banks. The fact that most of the Saudi banks have all along being at the gray zones of liquidating should be a wakeup call to relevant authorities that regulate the banking industry.

7.2.3.3 Recommendation

The thesis recommends that that further studies should be conducted to determine the insolvency risks of the banks. Doing so would determine the insolvency risks of various banks in Saudi Arabia; hence, play an important role at strengthening the future of the

Saudi banking industry and minimizing the likelihood of banks filing for bankruptcy unexpectedly.

7.2.4: Research objective 4: Forces emanating from the crisis that impacted the Saudi banking industry

7.2.4.1 Summary

The thesis established that even if banks' unique characteristics were not responsible for the effects of the crisis on Saudi banking industry, there were unique forces from the crisis that impacted both types of banks. The unique forces included the external forces from USA and other parts of the world that impacted the Saudi oil industry and other major industries in Saudi Arabia that in turn impacted the banking industry.

7.2.4.2 Main lesson

The main lesson that can be drawn from this research objective is that other forces other than banks' unique characteristics may expose Saudi banks to the effects of financial crisis. Since the other factors may be external in nature or unforeseen, then it would be wrong to presume that Saudi Islamic banks may not be vulnerable to financial crisis that may occur in the future or in Saudi Arabia. Acknowledging this fact would be critical in safeguarding the future of the Saudi banking industry because it would inform the measures that would be taken in the future to protect the banks from possible crisis.

7.2.4.3 Recommendation

To minimize the effects of financial crisis on Saudi banking industry, the thesis recommends that effort should be made to diversify the Saudi economy. While recommending so, the thesis acknowledges the fact that effort has been made to diversify the economy, but it appreciates that more needs to be done to strengthen the economy and Saudi banking practices in particular.

In terms of policy change, the thesis established that a lot has been done to enhance the sustainability of the Saudi banking industry. It established that most of the policies adopted in other parts of the world have been adopted in KSA. This gives an impression

that the Saudi banking industry like any other banking industry in the world is safe from financial crisis. However, the thesis identified the need to address the unique challenges that face the Saudi banking industry by designing policies that address local challenges. The thesis appreciates that even if much has been done to protect the Saudi banking industry from financial crisis in the future; something needs to be done to protect the industry from internal crisis. This could go a long way in strengthening the banking industry and protecting it from crisis that may strike internally. In addition, it could go a long way safeguarding the industry from external financial crisis.

7.3: Contribution to existing body of knowledge

Most of the studies that evaluate the impact of the financial crisis on different parts of the world and partly in KSA base their arguments on the role that banks' unique characteristics played in exposing banking industry to the crisis. While the thesis based part of its argument on banks' unique characteristics, it went a step further to evaluate the other factors that exposed Saudi banking industry to the crisis. It established that effects emanating from the oil industry were responsible for the impact of the crisis that was observed among Saudi banks. In so doing, it highlighted the need for developing mechanisms that would protect the banking industry from financial crisis by dealing with issues emanating from the oil industry and other industries that exposed the banking industry to financial crisis. Alongside the above, it depicted that inasmuch as banks' unique characteristics especially the Islamic ones were critical at minimize the effects of financial crisis, there was the need to protect both types of banks. In so doing, it minimizes the intensity of the myth that identifies Islamic banking practices as least vulnerable to financial crisis. By minimizing the intensity of the myth that identifies Islamic banking practices as least vulnerable to financial crisis, it contributes to the body of existing literature by identifying the need to protect both IBs and CBs from financial crisis.

Apart from the above, the empirical research work in the thesis was unique because from the time that the crisis ended no other study has been conducted in KSA to depict the manner in which the crisis impacted the current banking practices. The lack of empirical data in KSA to support the research theory was identified in the literature

review. The thesis has addressed this challenge in a number of ways that are critical to the existing body of knowledge. Firstly, it identified the major theoretical backgrounds that could be utilized to depict the manner in which different parts of the world including KSA were impacted or not impacted by the crisis. It particularly identified the spillover and contagious effects theories as some of the theories that could be utilized to explain the manner in which the effects of the crisis spread to different parts of the world. In addition, it identified the decoupling theory as the other theory that can be utilized to explain the way other parts of the world were not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis. Secondly, it identified the manner in which Saudi banking industry was impacted by the crisis. While such a finding might appear negligent because every part of the world could be expected to be impacted by the crisis, knowledge derived from the thesis could educate and even inform debates on the impact of the crisis on Saudi banking industry. Furthermore, it could inform policy making processes in KSA aimed at protecting the Saudi banking industry from vulnerability to financial crisis.

7.4 Limitations

In spite of what the thesis has established, it would be important to appreciate the fact that the thesis had several limitations some of which obviously impacted its overall findings. To begin with, due to unavailability of the online data that was utilized to conduct the study, only 3 IBs and 3 CBs were included in the analysis. Even though this number was reasonable given that it came from a pool of 4 IBs and 9 CBs, the sample was small; hence, it impacted the study's precision power to detect the source of error and even enhance the study's accuracy.

Additionally, it would be important to appreciate the fact that the quota sampling method, which was utilized to select the 3 CBs that took part in the study, was non-random in nature. While the issue of unavailability of data could be utilized to justify the sampling process, the fact remains the non-random nature of the sampling method affected the selection of the banks included in the analysis. For this reason, even though the study's findings provided an overview of the way the Saudi banks were impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis, it would be important to appreciate the fact that the findings can only be limited to the six banks that took part in the study. In this

respect, the generalization of the study's findings was carried out carefully to minimize the likelihood of providing misleading results. In spite of this, it would be worth noting that an effective matching process was carried out throughout the process of selecting the 3 CBs that took part in the study. The process entailed selecting CBs that were almost similar to the Islamic ones in terms of banks' sizes and years of doing business in Saudi banking industry. As a result, even though the study's findings could not be generalized, they at least provided a better overview of the way the banking industry was impacted by the crisis.

Apart from the above, it would be important to appreciate the fact that other factors that impacted the Saudi banking industry were not included in the quantitative data that was utilized to evaluate the effect of the crisis on Saudi banks. Even though some of those factors were evaluated through qualitative analysis, it would be worth noting that because the crisis took place about ten years ago then most of the research participants probably did not remember their effects on their respective banks accurately. More importantly, it would be important to appreciate the fact that because the study was conducted after the crisis had occurred, then the researcher did not have control over the variables included in the analysis. For these reasons, the study does not downplay the effect that types of banks had on exposing or not exposing Saudi banks to the effects of the crisis. In this respect, the researcher recommends that further studies should be carried out in KSA and other Islamic states to determine the effect that banking practices had on exposing and protecting IBs from the effects of the crisis.

The above being the case, the thesis recommends that if it would be possible to obtain the financial results from individual banks physically, which the researcher was unable to do due to banks' sensitivity to the issue, then a similar study that would include all Saudi banks should be carried out. While the thesis appreciates the fact that such a study would be more accurate than the current one, it also appreciates the fact that the study would also not provide a clear overview of the issue because the Saudi foreign banks would still be excluded from the analysis. To make the matter worse, it would still be practically impossible to get the people who worked in the banking industry between 2006 and 2010 to get a clearer picture of the issue from them.

Furthermore, the study was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic. Although effective measures were put in place to minimize the pandemic's effects on the data collection process, the interview process was not in-depth as intended. As a result, it is possible that the participants did not express their views adequately due to the short time used to collect the data. For this reason, similar studies that would probe research participants should be conducted in the future.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Introductory letter

My name is _____. I am a PHD student from _____ University. In line with academic requirements, I am conducting a study on the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry. To help me fulfill this responsibility, kindly allow me to conduct the study within your institution. The study process will entail identifying the people to include in the study and requesting them to take part in the study on voluntary basis.

Thank you in advance

Yours faithfully,

Appendix B: Consent form

The current study evaluates the effects of the 2008/09 financial crisis on Saudi banking industry. Being one of the people who work in the industry, kindly read the consent form and sign it before taking part in the study.

Consent statement

1. I take part in the study on voluntary basis
2. I understand that there will be no direct benefits to me for taking part in the study
3. I understand that the study will be entirely anonymous; hence, my identity will not be revealed anywhere in the final report.
4. I understand that information obtained from me will not be shared with anyone or used for any other purpose other than the one it is collected for
5. I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any point without giving reasons
6. I confirm that I have read and understood the nature of my participation in the study

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Appendix C: Interview schedule

Demographic questions

A: Please indicate the gender of the respondent

1. Male
2. Female

B: Kindly request the respondent to provide his/her age

1. 21 – 30
2. 31 – 40
3. 41 – 50
4. 51 – 60
5. 61 and above

C: Kindly request the respondent to provide his/her highest level of education

1. High school
2. Bachelor level
3. Master's level
4. PHD level

Research questions

1. Between 2006 and 2010 when the 2008/09 global financial crisis occurred, were you working in the Saudi banking industry?

1. Yes
2. No

2. If yes, were you working for this bank or another bank? What were your specific duties that time? Please explain including the number of years you had worked in the bank industry by the time the crisis occurred.

3. Because you were already in the banking industry, could you give me a brief history of the 2008/09 financial crisis from a Saudi perspective?

4. Do you think this bank or the bank that you were working for at that time was impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis in any way? How was the bank impacted or not impacted by the crisis? Please explain your response/answer.

5. To what extent do you think the bank's processes in terms of policies, structures and the way it offered banking services to customers contributed to the way your bank was impacted or not impacted by the 2008/09 financial crisis? Please explain.

6. Do you feel that Islamic banks dealt with the financial crisis better or worse than conventional banks? Please explain

7. What measures do you think the Saudi government with the help of relevant authorities has taken since 2008/09 to protect the Saudi banking industry from similar financial crisis? Please explain

8. What is your view of the current measures taken by the government to protect the Saudi banking industry from financial crisis and its possible effects? Do you think the measures are good or bad? Why or why not? Please explain.

9. What would you recommend to be done to protect the banking industry from the effects of financial crisis in the future? Please explain

Thank you